

D5.5

Final Strategic Exploitation Plan

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The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf.

Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
Open RRI	Open and Responsible Research and Innovation
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
GA	Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
EA	Exploitable Asset
EM	Exploitation Manager
JOA	Joint Ownership Agreement

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1 Executive Summary

This report presents the Final Strategic Exploitation Plan of the PATTERN project (Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101094416), delivered at M42 as the concluding instalment of the project's exploitation strategy, building on the First Strategic Exploitation Plan submitted at M13 (D5.4).

PATTERN counts a total of 12 results to be included in the final Results Ownership List (ROL) across its 42-month lifetime: eight thematic training courses covering Open Access, FAIR Research Data Management, Citizen Science, Research Integrity, Gender Non-discrimination and Inclusion, Science Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Research Results, and Mental Health and Leadership; two digital platforms (OpenPlato and the Projects platform); a Trainers Directory; and a cumulative set of Policy Recommendations. All results are released under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International licence (CC BY 4.0), ensuring maximum accessibility, reusability and long-term availability. Five results are jointly owned, with joint ownership arrangements formalised through three dedicated instruments (a Joint Ownership Agreement (JOA), a Side Letter, and an E-Learning Courses Joint Ownership Agreement), each calibrated to the specific technical and legal characteristics of the result it governs.

A key development in the final phase of the project was the identification of the Trainers Directory as a new Key Exploitable Result, emerging from the last Open Studio session held in Brussels in April 2026. This result opens a concrete pathway to post-project commercial exploitation through a brokered training-as-a-service model led by SciLink, through which institutional clients can access PATTERN-certified expertise in Open and Responsible Research and Innovation training on a fee-for-service basis.

The project engaged with the Horizon Results Booster (HRB) on two occasions. The first engagement was a joint Go-to-Market (G2M) service with the REINFORCING and ECS projects, which produced Value Proposition Canvases and Market Definition Canvases for two cross-project Key Exploitable Results (a joint platform hub and a joint training offer) and generated expert recommendations on prioritisation and joint exploitation strategy. The second was a PATTERN-specific G2M service that developed the exploitation characterisation of three project KERs, directly informing the present report.

Individual exploitation plans are provided in Chapter 4 and demonstrate a range of concrete post-project uptake routes.

The report also documents an early exploitation success story: SCOIR, an external organisation connected to OpenAIRE operating in the Irish research support landscape, made active use of PATTERN's Open Access training

materials during the project period — before its conclusion — adapting them to the Irish policy environment and feeding national expertise back into the European ecosystem. This case validates both the practical utility of the CC BY 4.0 licensing model and the capacity of PATTERN's outputs to attract independent third-party uptake organically, without formal transfer mechanisms.

2 Introduction

The European Research Area (ERA) envisions a successful transition to a sustainable, digital, and resilient Europe. Research and innovation in the European Union (EU) are grounded in shared values and principles, encompassing pursuit of excellence, value creation, ethics and the integrity of research and innovation, freedom of scientific research, gender equality, equal opportunities and inclusiveness, free circulation, coordination, coherence, commitment, global outreach, and societal responsibility.

One of the ERA's top priorities is to train researchers to actively contribute to a closer relationship between science and society and enhance trust in science. Simultaneously, it aims to equip them with the necessary skills for the labour market, focusing on upskilling and reskilling through targeted training. This aligns with the Horizon Europe framework and the European Skills Agenda, which recognise the significance of transferable skills in facilitating intersectoral mobility and knowledge transfer.

The overarching goal of the PATTERN project is to cultivate inclusive and sustainable practices in Open Science (OS) and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), through promoting researcher training in the relevant transferable skills. According to the European Commission: 'Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) implies that societal actors (researchers, citizens, policy makers, business, third sector organisations, etc.) work together during the whole research and innovation process in order to better align both the process and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society'. The key components are public engagement, gender equality, social justice and inclusion, ethics and research integrity, science education, open science, governance, and sustainability.

PATTERN has a focus on eight main transferable skills within the context of OS and RRI. These eight skills comprise Open Access, FAIR data Management, Citizen Science, Research Integrity, Gender, non-discrimination and inclusion in research, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results, Science Communication (towards media and policy makers), and Management and Leadership. At the core of PATTERN are the mapping and quality assessment of state-of-the-art training opportunities for researchers (Work Package 1, WP1), along with an analysis of policy at institutional, national, and European levels (WP4). These aim to identify existing gaps and to enhance capacity within the ERA to address societal challenges and foster a closer dialogue between science, policy and society.

WP5 (Dissemination, Communication and Engagement) has the objectives of ensuring wide visibility of the project; clustering and creating synergies with other EU initiatives and paving the way for the exploitation of PATTERN project results. To achieve the last objective of WP5 in this report, the

Exploitation Manager (EM) LOBA, provides with the support of project partners an initial overview of PATTERN IPR management strategy which takes into consideration background IP of PATTERN Consortium partners, foreground IP to be developed by the project, Exploitable Assets and potential exploitation plans per asset.

3 PATTERN's updated exploitable results

3.1 IP management

The methodology for the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management of PATTERN exploitable assets has not changed from D5.4.

No changes in the background IP has been detected compared to D5.4 and the Consortium Agreement.

In general, the Consortium agreed to apply the open licence CC BY 4.0 to all project's exploitable results with the following common licence disclaimer:

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3.2 PATTERN's updated key exploitable results

The main key exploitable results of PATTERN, as identified by the consortium, are presented in Results Ownership List (ROL) below (Table 1). The key changes from D5.4 consist in the splitting of the former "PATTERN Trainings" result into all the different training courses, clustered around the 8 transferrable skill them. Same goes for the former "PATTERN Platform", which was divided into Open Plato and Projects platform.

Result name	Single or joint owner result	Result owner	Contributor	Will the owner/s/ contributors exploit the result?	In which form will the result be made available to other consortium members and/or third parties?	Does the exploitation of the results require access of one or several consortium members?	Does the exploitation of the results require access to third party IPR?	IPR applied to the Result
Mental Health and Leadership training	Joint	SciLink	OpenAIRE	Yes	Open access	No	No	CC BY 4.0
Citizen Science training	Joint	AU	OpenAIRE	Yes	Open access	No	No	CC BY 4.0
Dissemination & Exploitation training	Joint	APRE	LOBA, OpenAIRE	Yes	Open access	No	No	CC BY 4.0
FAIR Research Data Management training	Joint	DANS	HEAL-Link, RBI, UDEBREC HEN,	Yes	Open access	No	No	CC BY 4.0

			OpenAIRE					
Gender, non-discrimination and inclusion training	Joint	UnISR	ESF, OpenAIRE	Yes	Open access	No	No	CC BY 4.0
Open Access training	Joint	uMinho	UMinho; HEAL-Link; RBI, IZTECH, OpenAIRE	Yes	Open access	No	No	CC BY 4.0
Research Integrity training	Joint	EARMA	AU, OpenAIRE	Yes	Open access	No	No	CC BY 4.0
Science Communication training	Joint	SISSA	RBI, OpenAIRE	Yes	Open access	No	No	CC BY 4.0
Open Plato platform	Single	OpenAIRE		Yes	Open access	No	No	CC BY 4.0
Projects platform	Single	LPI		Yes	Open source	No	No	CC BY 4.0
Trainers directory	Single	SciLink		Yes	N/A	No	No	Controlled-access service
PATTERN Policy briefs and recommendations	Single	ESF		Yes	Open access	No	No	CC BY 4.0

Table 1 - Result Ownership List

3.3 Key Exploitable Results descriptions

3.3.1 Mental Health and Leadership training

The Mental Health and Leadership training is a PATTERN result designed to equip early career researchers with knowledge and skills to support mental health in academic and research environments at individual, institutional and systemic levels. The training consists of three half-day modules, which may be followed either sequentially or independently.

The first module introduces mental health in academia and examines the individual and contextual factors affecting researchers' wellbeing. The second module focuses on institutional support, stigma reduction and the development of networks of allies. The third module addresses systemic challenges, including legal and policy frameworks, advocacy and leadership for change at national and international levels.

The training is initially piloted as a two-day hybrid workshop, combining in-person participation with remote attendance. By the end of the course, participants are expected to understand the relevance of mental health in academic settings, identify strategies to support wellbeing, recognise obstacles in research environments, assess institutional resources, engage with relevant stakeholders and develop leadership skills to promote mental health awareness. The training material produced by training events has been collected and adapted to OpenPlato e-learning platform as a Trainer's Guide course.

The main target groups are early career researchers, supervisors and senior researchers, and research managers or institutional staff. The result is particularly relevant for organisations seeking to strengthen researcher wellbeing, improve institutional support mechanisms and foster inclusive and sustainable research cultures.

The short training modules in Mental Health and Leadership contain six different topics, all are preferably in a face-to-face format to an ideal size of group of 8-16 early-stage researchers, PhD candidates. The topics are the following, each 2 hours long and interactive. All these training modules were piloted during a full day event, named the 1st PhD Wellbeing Festival in Amsterdam.

Boosting Resilience – where participants learn to analyse challenging situations and regain control in order to move forward. Career planning: Finding your fit – is to discover what gives energy at work, evaluate fit with the current position, and leave with inspiration for a next career move. Fostering your work-life balance as an early-career researcher – aims to learn how to build a healthier work-life balance by discovering key life roles, setting priorities, and creating a personal action plan. Imposterism – aims to explore

imposter thoughts through scenarios, uncover the fears fuelling them, and build concrete and practical cognitive and behavioural strategies to respond with confidence. Identity – Thriving Within and Beyond Academia – is an opportunity to identify boundaries and apply effective communication to protect time and energy, analyse sources of isolation, evaluate ways to nurture both academic and non-academic identities, and reflect on joining or initiating project groups beyond formal structures. Navigating Ethical Dilemmas and Power Dynamics – helps to identify and analyse real cases of clashing values, unfair treatment, and ethical discrepancies in research.

Mental Health and Leadership training materials are available [here](#).

3.3.2 Citizen Science training

The Citizen Science training is a PATTERN result that provides researchers with an introduction to Citizen Science (CS) and practical guidance on participant recruitment and community engagement. The course consists of two modules. The first, Introducing Citizen Science: Fundamental Principles and Interactive Cases, is a foundational module covering the history of CS, participation levels, the ten principles of CS, its role in Open Science and tools to get started. The second, Participant Recruitment and Community Engagement, is an intermediate-level module building upon the first, focusing on volunteer recruitment and management, ethical considerations, communication strategies and inclusivity in CS projects.

By completing the course, participants are expected to identify and describe the contributions of citizen science to research objectives across scientific fields; discuss the societal roles and impacts of citizen science in promoting engagement and facilitating change; relate citizen science principles and practices to those of open and responsible research and innovation (open RRI); develop practical skills in participant recruitment, fostering engagement and collaboration with attention to participants' motivations and training needs; gain knowledge of ethical principles related to participatory research; and develop effective communication skills, with a particular focus on two-way dialogue. The training material produced by training events has been collected and adapted to OpenPlato e-learning platform as a Trainer's Guide course.

The course is designed for researchers at different career stages. First-stage researchers and students, including PhD candidates, will find foundational knowledge of CS methodologies and their application in research, supporting those looking to expand the scale and societal relevance of their work. Early-career researchers, such as postdoctoral researchers, are expected to engage with the practical implementation of CS and develop concrete project ideas, driven by an interest in societal impact and career recognition. Established researchers, including senior academics and project leaders, will find

advanced content suited to taking leadership roles in CS initiatives and enhancing the broader impact and recognition of their research.

Citizen science training materials are available [here](#).

3.3.3 Dissemination & Exploitation training

The Dissemination and Exploitation training is a PATTERN result designed to strengthen researchers' capacity to maximise the impact of research projects through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation strategies. With a specific focus on Horizon Europe proposals and projects, the course provides practical tools to support the development of structured CDE plans and enhance project visibility.

The training is free and modular, articulated in two modules and four lessons, which may be followed independently or combined as a complete course. It uses practical case studies, interactive learning and examples from real Horizon Europe proposals to support participants in applying key concepts to research and innovation projects.

By completing the course, participants are expected to understand the differences between communication, dissemination and exploitation; identify appropriate tools and channels; use social media strategically; visually pitch research results; and apply these skills both in proposal development and project implementation.

The course is primarily addressed to doctoral and postdoctoral researchers, early-career researchers and established researchers involved in Horizon Europe proposals or projects. It is also relevant for administrative and research support staff, including research managers and grant office personnel.

Dissemination & Exploitation training materials are available [here](#)

3.3.4 FAIR Research Data Management training

The FAIR Research Data Management training is a PATTERN result designed to introduce researchers and research support professionals to the principles and practices of FAIR RDM. The course focuses on the application of the FAIR principles, Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable, to support high-quality, well-managed and reusable research data.

The training is free and consists of five sessions covering the foundations of FAIR RDM, Data Management Plans, metadata, file formats, data publication, persistent identifiers, repositories, licensing, data citation and research integrity. Each session includes interactive discussions, exercises and project-based learning activities, enabling participants to apply FAIR principles in practical research contexts. These five sessions has been separated into two different self-paste courses hosted into OpenPlato e-learning platform, one

for beginners' level (session 1 to 3) and the second for intermediate learners (sessions 4 to 5).

By completing the course, participants are expected to understand the benefits of research data sharing, create Data Management Plans, identify metadata and documentation practices, use repositories and persistent identifiers, apply appropriate licences and data citation practices, and recognise research integrity considerations linked to FAIR RDM.

The course is designed for master's students, PhD candidates, early-career and established researchers, as well as research support professionals such as librarians, data stewards and administrators. It is particularly relevant for those seeking to improve data sharing, research reproducibility and alignment with institutional and funder requirements.

FAIR Research Data Management training materials are available [here](#).

3.3.5 Gender, non-discrimination and inclusion training

The Gender, Non-discrimination and Inclusion training is a PATTERN result designed to support the integration of gender equality, non-discrimination and inclusion principles into research practice and research environments. The course provides researchers and institutional actors with conceptual knowledge and practical tools to recognise bias, promote inclusive professional interactions and embed the gender dimension in research.

The training consists of three self-standing modules addressing: gender bias from a social-cognitive perspective; risks linked to informal relationships in the workplace; and the integration of sex and gender as scientific variables in biomedical research projects. These three different modules have been adapted into one self-paced e-learning course for several stakeholder of the research community. The course combines practical examples, case studies, design-thinking approaches and self-reflection exercises to support application across disciplines.

By completing the course, participants are expected to recognise unconscious bias, stereotypes and privilege in research settings; identify problematic behaviours in informal work environments; apply strategies for respectful and inclusive interactions; implement gender equality planning practices; and integrate sex and gender considerations across the research lifecycle, from design to dissemination.

The course is designed for first stage, recognised and established researchers, as well as research support and administrative staff, senior management, research funding organisations and research policy professionals. It is relevant across disciplines, including biomedical, health, social and interdisciplinary research, and supports institutions in promoting research quality, inclusiveness and compliance with funding requirements.

Gender, non-discrimination and inclusion training materials are available [here](#).

3.3.6 Open Access training

The Open Access training is a PATTERN result designed to provide researchers with a comprehensive understanding of Open Access publishing and responsible publishing practices. The course addresses key aspects such as funder requirements, copyright retention, Open Peer Review, publishing routes and the identification of trusted publishers. The introductory self-paced course has been translated and adapted into four separate courses in the following languages: Portuguese, Greek, Turkish, Hungarian, and Croatian.

The training consists of multiple modules covering Horizon Europe and national Open Access requirements, Open Peer Review, Open Access publishing models, rights retention, licensing options and strategies to avoid predatory publishing. It supports researchers in complying with institutional and funder policies while maximising the visibility, credibility and societal impact of their research outputs.

By completing the course, participants are expected to understand the benefits of Open Access, distinguish between Gold, Green and Diamond Open Access routes, comply with funder mandates, retain copyright, apply appropriate licensing options, identify trusted publishers and engage in responsible peer review practices.

The Open Access thematic area provides training materials for trainers on retaining copyright, making informed publishing choices, and maximising the visibility, reuse and impact of Open Access publications. A complementary thematic area focuses on understanding and meeting funder requirements, including Open Access obligations, rights retention, licensing, and compliance with research funding policies.

The main course material is designed for first stage, recognised and established researchers, including PhD candidates, postdoctoral researchers, academics, senior researchers and research leaders. It is particularly relevant for those involved in publishing, project implementation and funding applications, and for researchers responsible for guiding teams on Open Access strategies and research integrity.

Open Access training materials are available [here](#).

3.3.7 Research Integrity training

The Research Integrity training is a PATTERN result designed to introduce researchers and research professionals to the fundamental principles of research integrity and good scientific practice in the context of responsible research and innovation. The course supports participants in upholding

ethical standards, preventing research misconduct and promoting transparency in scientific work.

The training covers key topics including research ethics, data management, authorship, plagiarism, responsible Open Science, supervision practices, current developments in research integrity and relevant international regulatory frameworks. It combines case-based exercises and reflective discussions to support the practical application of good scientific practice.

By completing the course, participants are expected to understand the core principles of research integrity, identify ethical challenges, recognise research misconduct and questionable research practices, apply best practices in data management, authorship and Open Science, and facilitate discussions on responsible research within their institutions.

The course is designed for PhD candidates, early-career researchers, research professionals, advanced researchers, supervisors, research managers and ombudspersons. It is particularly relevant for those seeking to strengthen ethical research environments, support institutional compliance and foster a culture of responsible research practice.

Research Integrity training materials are available [here](#).

3.3.8 Science Communication training

The Science Communication training is a PATTERN result designed to introduce researchers to effective communication with non-scientific audiences, with a focus on media and policymakers. The course supports researchers in improving the visibility of their work, engaging with public discourse and contributing to evidence-based policy discussions.

The training consists of four independent modules covering the foundations of science communication, writing for the media, interacting with the media and communicating with policymakers. Each module combines theoretical insights with practical elements, while additional materials are provided for further study. Training materials have been organised into one self-paced course and a trainer's guide for these aspects.

By completing the course, participants are expected to understand the aims of science communication, recognise how media and policymakers operate, adapt research content to different formats, communicate clearly in media interviews and present research findings effectively to policy audiences.

The course is available as a self-paced programme on OpenPlato and through materials for trainers interested in organising live lectures or practical workshops, including resources available on OpenPlato, Zenodo and the Projects platform. It is designed for researchers at different career stages with limited experience in science communication, particularly those seeking to

communicate their research to wider audiences and reflect on their role as experts in society. Two additional practical activities are also available on the [Project platform](#).

Note: The Science Communication training listed in the ROL refers to the core training package developed by SISSA and RBI, comprising slide decks, lecture notes, practical activity materials and trainer guidelines. It does not include the project-based learning materials developed by Aarhus University (AU) and stored on the Projects platform, which constitute a separable and independently attributable contribution by AU. As AU's authorship of these materials can be separately identified, they do not give rise to joint ownership within the meaning of Article 16.4 of the GA and remain the single-owned result of AU. Accordingly, AU retains full ownership of these materials, and they are released under CC BY 4.0 under AU's sole authority.

Science Communication training materials are available [here](#).

3.3.9 Open Plato platform

OpenPlato is the learning platform used within PATTERN to host, organise and disseminate the project's training offer. Developed by OpenAIRE, it is a modular learning platform supporting training in Open Science, Research Data Management and related topics, providing self-paced courses with SCORM learning packages, Train the Trainers live sessions and community-oriented training resources for research communities around Europe and beyond.

Within PATTERN, OpenPlato hosts the project's training materials across the eight thematic areas: Open Access, FAIR RDM, Citizen Science, Science Communication, Research Integrity, Gender Equality, Non-discrimination and Inclusion, Dissemination and Exploitation of Research Results, and Mental Health Leadership. The platform enables learners to access PATTERN courses and supports the long-term availability, discoverability and reuse of the training materials.

Open Plato platform is available [here](#).

3.3.10 Projects platform

The Projects platform is a PATTERN result supporting project-based learning activities during and after the training modules. It enables users to work collaboratively on practical exercises and use cases, document project work, share resources and interact with peers or trainers in a structured online environment.

Within the PATTERN digital ecosystem, Projects functions as a collaborative working space connected to the broader platform for training and knowledge exchange. It supports co-creation, mentoring, sharing of internal and external

resources, and the identification of synergies among users and communities of practice. The platform is also used to host practical activities linked to PATTERN trainings, allowing participants to apply course content to concrete cases and continue working on learning tasks beyond the training session.

Project Platform is available [here](#).

3.3.11 Trainers directory

The Trainers directory is a Key Exploitable Result identified in the last trimester of the project during the last Open Studio session held in Brussels in April 2026.

This result consists of an aggregated “PATTERN trainer and facilitator directory”, bringing together the experts who have designed and delivered PATTERN training activities across the project’s lifespan and the eight transferable skills themes. This result potentially **enables the commercialisation of PATTERN training content**, as well as access to verified, high-quality expertise in Open and Responsible Research and Innovation-related capacity building. As PATTERN has developed and piloted trainings in eight transferable skills key areas, this creates a strong basis for tailored institutional offers in the post-project period.

Service delivery model: The service would operate through a brokered institutional delivery model led by **SciLink** through the following key steps:

1. Training requests would be submitted via the PATTERN website and routed to SciLink.
2. SciLink would assess the client’s needs and identify the most appropriate trainer(s) or facilitator(s) from the PATTERN directory (depending on the transferable skill theme and training delivery mode).
3. After contacting the PATTERN expert (we define “PATTERN experts” as all trainers and facilitators belonging to the directory), SciLink prepares and sends the fully burdened (i.e. including overhead) offer to the client.
4. If the offer is accepted, SciLink manages contracting, administration and invoicing.

The selected trainer would deliver the service under the SciLink umbrella, while SciLink would handle the financial, logistical, and organisational interface with the client.

This model was conceived to align with and leverage SciLink’s existing role as a provider of courses, tailored institutional training packages, and onsite or online delivery for research institutions and networks.

Target users: The primary target users comprise universities, doctoral schools, research-performing organisations, European project consortia and research networks seeking tailored training in Open Science and Open RRI. Secondary target users include research support offices, research manager and administrator communities, research project managers, science-policy organisations, and other institutions involved in researcher professional development.

Revenue model: The pathway follows a **fee-for-service revenue model**. The client pays SciLink as the contractual service provider for the fully burdened training package, including scoping, coordination, delivery and administration. SciLink then remunerates or reimburses the trainer on a freelance basis according to its internal framework, while retaining a service margin to cover coordination, client management, and organisational costs. Depending on market demand, the offer may be priced as:

- a fixed-fee workshop
- a daily-rate service
- a multi-session package
- a broader institutional package

This model may reveal to be a concrete financially sustainable route to post-project exploitation and may enable PATTERN's training expertise to remain available as a professional service and professional network beyond project funding.

Operational and legal feasibility: As many PATTERN trainers are employed by universities or public bodies and may face restrictions on direct commercial engagement, revenue collection, or external service provision, by designating SciLink as the contracting and invoicing entity, the pathway reduces administrative complexity and creates a clearer commercial structure. However, participation of individual trainers would remain subject to their employer's internal rules on outside work, remuneration, and conflict of interest. For that reason, trainer engagement should be formalised on a case-by-case basis under clear terms of collaboration.

3.3.12 PATTERN Policy briefs and recommendations

The PATTERN Policy Recommendations constitute a cumulative, evidence-based policy framework developed iteratively across the full project lifetime (2023–2026) through three cycles of co-creation activities involving consortium partners, sister projects, learners, trainers, policymakers, and Communities of Practice, grounded in empirical evidence from two pilot learning cycles across 14 research performing organisations.

The three deliverables form a progressive, interconnected sequence. The [First Policy Brief \(D4.2, 2024\)](#) established the foundational policy gap analysis

across European, national and institutional levels, identifying seven overarching gaps including unsustainable funding, absence of holistic Open RRI approaches, uneven coverage of themes, insufficient monitoring mechanisms, and the weak integration of Open Science practices into research evaluation. [The Second Policy Brief \(D4.3, 2025\)](#) refined these findings following the first pilot learning cycle, shifting focus toward institutional embedding, accreditation pathways, persona-based learner design, modular curricula aligned with career stages, and strengthened EU-level certification mechanisms. The final [Policy Recommendations document \(D4.4, 2026\)](#) synthesises all prior evidence into a comprehensive, three-tiered framework of structured, actionable recommendations addressed to the European Commission, national policymakers, and research performing institutions respectively.

Collectively, the three deliverables address ten key dimensions of Open RRI training policy: training topics and inter-thematic synergies, evaluation and feedback mechanisms, teaching methods and delivery formats, accessibility and inclusiveness, training of trainers; customisation and adaptability, tools and resources; scalability, certification and recognition and funding and sustainability. The recommendations are explicitly related to existing EU frameworks including ResearchComp, RMComp, EQF, ESCO, CoARA/ ARRA, EOSC, and the ERA Policy Agenda (2025–2027) to maximise uptake, cross-border portability, and long-term relevance beyond the project lifecycle.

3.4 IP ownership management

PATTERN ROL has four results with single ownership, while eight with joint ownership (all trainings).

The Consortium was provided by LOBA, as exploitation manager, with three instruments to manage joint ownership of results:

For static documents

1. Joint Ownership Agreement (JOA) template (Annex 1)
2. Side Letter (Annex 2)

Both the Joint Ownership Agreement (JOA) and the Side Letter are written instruments designed to fulfil the same legal obligation: the requirement under Article 16.4 of the Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement that joint owners record in writing the allocation and terms of exercise of jointly owned results. Both instruments confirm joint ownership of a specific result, release it under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Public License (CC BY 4.0), waive the default 45-day prior-notice requirement and compensation entitlement of Article 16.4, and regulate attribution, third-party material, derivative works, and parallel licensing.

Their difference is one of formality and documentary weight, not of legal substance or effect. The JOA is a full standalone contract, structured with numbered articles, recitals, representations and warranties, an explicit versioning and maintenance clause designating a coordinating owner, indemnity provisions, and detailed conflict-of-laws rules. It is appropriate where the result is composed of multiple formats and components, where ongoing versioning is anticipated, or where parties prefer a comprehensive and self-contained instrument. The Side Letter is a shorter instrument conceived as a targeted addendum to the existing governance framework of the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement. It records the same core undertakings, ownership confirmation, CC BY 4.0 release, attribution form, third-party material carve-out, and dispute resolution, in a more compact form, without the granularity of the JOA's warranty and indemnity structure or versioning regime. It is better suited to simpler results where the parties' relationship is already fully governed by existing project agreements and where a lighter documentary footprint is preferred. In both cases, the instrument constitutes the written agreement required by Article 16.4 and prevails over the Consortium Agreement on matters of joint ownership and licensing of the specific result to which it applies.

For e-learning courses

- E-Learning Courses Joint Ownership Agreement (Annex 3)

The E-Learning Courses Joint Ownership Agreement (E-Learning JOA) serves the same legal function — compliance with Article 16.4 of the HE MGA — but differs from the JOA and Side Letter in both scope and structure, reflecting the specific technical and operational characteristics of the e-learning courses produced under PATTERN's Work Package 2.

The JOA and Side Letter are each drafted to govern a single static result: a training package consisting of documentary outputs such as slide decks, trainer guides, participant materials, and associated files in standard document formats. The E-Learning JOA, by contrast, governs all eight PATTERN e-learning courses in a single consolidated instrument, with a course-by-course breakdown of contributing parties set out in an Annex. This consolidated approach was chosen because all courses share a common technical production infrastructure, they were all authored in OpenAIRE's Articulate Rise 360 cloud account and deployed on the OpenPlato platform. Making a single overarching agreement more practical than eight separate instruments.

The Articulate Rise 360 authoring environment introduces a structural asymmetry that does not arise for static documents and that the E-Learning JOA specifically addresses. For static materials, all contributing parties can independently access, modify, and redistribute their copies of the result

without operational dependency on any other party. For e-learning courses built in Rise 360, native editing and updates require access to OpenAIRE's Rise 360 account, since the source files are hosted there. The E-Learning JOA manages this asymmetry through a dedicated Clause 4, which establishes OpenAIRE's obligations as account custodian and platform operator: it must keep the account active for at least three years post-project, provide SCORM/xAPI and PDF export packages to any other party on request within 15 calendar days, maintain public accessibility on OpenPlato, and refrain from withdrawing or materially altering course content without the prior consent of the content-contributing parties. These obligations have no equivalent in the JOA or Side Letter, which do not need to address platform custody or export rights.

The E-Learning JOA also formalises a two-tier ownership structure that reflects how the courses were actually produced: OpenAIRE holds joint ownership of all eight courses by virtue of its instructional design and technical production contribution, while content-contributing partners hold joint ownership only of the specific courses to which they contributed substantive educational material. This differentiated ownership topology — a single technical partner across all courses combined with varying content partners per course — has no counterpart in the JOA or Side Letter, where ownership shares are allocated among parties whose contributions, though jointly inseparable, are treated as equivalent in kind. Clause 8 of the E-Learning JOA explicitly delineates its scope: it governs the interactive courses only, while the static training materials remain governed by the JOA or Side Letter as applicable.

In compliance with the Grant Agreement Annex 5, Article 16, partners were required to have a written agreement on the allocation and terms of exercise of jointly owned results. The consortium was given freedom on the form of that written record; use of the three instruments described above was strongly recommended. In practice, partners expressed different preferences, and one result required a different approach.

For the FAIR Research Data Management training, the number of contributing partners (DANS, HEAL-Link, RBI, UDEBRECHEN and OpenAIRE) agreed to fulfil the Article 16.4 obligation through an email correspondence process: a single email setting out the joint ownership confirmation and CC BY 4.0 release terms was to be sent by LOBA to all contributing partners, with each partner requested to reply with an explicit written confirmation. This approach is legally equivalent to a signed instrument for the purposes of Article 16.4: the email exchange, comprising the originating message and the individual confirmations, constitutes the written record required by the GA. The e-learning component of the FAIR RDM training is separately governed

by the E-Learning Courses Joint Ownership Agreement, to which OpenAIRE is a party.

The preferences of all partners as regards the written agreement instrument are reflected in Table 2 below

Result name	Single or joint ownership result	Result owner	Contributor	Ownership agreement	written
Mental Health and Leadership training	Joint	SciLink	OpenAIRE	Side letter	
Citizen Science training	Joint	AU	OpenAIRE	Side letter	
Dissemination & Exploitation training	Joint	APRE	LOBA, OpenAIRE	JOA	
FAIR Research Data Management training	Joint	DANS	HEAL-Link, RBI, UDEBR ECHEN, OpenAIRE	E-mail correspondence	
Gender, non-discrimination and inclusion training	Joint	UniSR	ESF, OpenAIRE	Side letter	
Open Access training	Joint	uMinho	UMinho; HEAL-Link; RBI, IZTECH, OpenAIRE	Side letter	
Research Integrity training	Joint	EARMA	AU, OpenAIRE	Side letter	
Science Communication training	Joint	SISSA	RBI, OpenAIRE	Side letter	

It should be noted that, for the purposes of the Result Ownership List (ROL), each PATTERN training is presented as a single consolidated result (for example, "Citizen Science training"), encompassing both its static components (slide decks, trainer guides, participant materials and associated documentary outputs) and its interactive e-learning version produced in Articulate Rise 360 and deployed on OpenPlato. This consolidation reflects the fact that the two formats constitute a single pedagogical offering addressing

a common set of learning objectives and target groups, and that separating them in the ROL would artificially fragment results that are functionally and thematically unified. The distinction between static and e-learning components is, however, preserved at the level of IP management, where separate instruments govern their respective joint ownership arrangements: the JOA or Side Letter for static materials, and the E-Learning Courses Joint Ownership Agreement for the Articulate-based courses.

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4 Individual exploitation plans

This chapter presents the individual exploitation plans of PATTERN consortium partners, detailing how each organisation intends to make use of, integrate, or further develop the project's results beyond the grant period.

Organisartion	Exploitaion plan
UniSR	<p>UniSR has permanently integrated two PATTERN training modules — the Social-Cognitive Perspective on Gender Bias and the dedicated lessons on Science Communication and Citizen Science — into its PhD educational offer. While the annual programme is reviewed each year, the institutional embedding of these modules provides a stable basis for their continued delivery and creates opportunities for ongoing review and adaptation of the materials in light of evolving research and policy contexts. The Gender Dimension in Research Funding module has achieved formal recognition at the national level, having been accredited by the relevant Italian authorities. As a result, participants from the medical field in Italy are eligible to receive ECM (Educazione Continua in Medicina / Continuing Medical Education) credits upon completion. This module, together with the module on Risks of Informal Relationships in the Workplace, will form part of the mandatory gender equality training programme explicitly foreseen in UniSR's Gender Equality Plan (GEP), ensuring continued institutional uptake beyond the project's lifetime.</p>
EARMA	<p>EARMA will integrate selected elements of the PATTERN Research Integrity training module into the EARMA Academy, its online training hub designed for research managers and administrators at different career stages, from RM1 to RM4. The integration will be carried out in alignment with the Research Management Competency Framework (RMComp), ensuring that the incorporated content meets the professional development standards expected within the research management community in Europe. This exploitation route extends the reach of PATTERN's research integrity training to a professional audience that operates across institutional and national boundaries, with the EARMA Academy providing an established and recognised channel for sustained dissemination.</p>
LPI	<p>The Projects platform, developed by LPI as part of the PATTERN infrastructure, has already secured post-project institutional uptake beyond the consortium. The platform is now actively used by several new universities, including</p>

	<p>Sorbonne University and the University of Strasbourg, demonstrating concrete demand from research-performing organisations beyond the original pilot network. In addition, the platform supports newly launched European initiatives, including the ERASMUS+ funded PROVEST and COFOREST projects, which provide a sustained operational context and user base for the platform in the years following PATTERN's conclusion.</p>
AU	<p>AU will continue to draw on PATTERN training materials in Citizen Science, Science Communication and Research Integrity — specifically the Authorship module — in its educational offerings for natural science students across all levels, from bachelor to PhD. The materials, made openly available through Zenodo and through the relevant modules on the Projects platform, provide a reusable and adaptable resource base that AU will deploy within its existing curricula, ensuring continued institutional use of PATTERN outputs within a leading European research university context.</p>
APRE	<p>APRE will continue to use the Dissemination and Exploitation training materials, piloted and refined through the PATTERN methodology, in its offer for Italian research and innovation actors, including APRE members. Having contributed to the development and quality improvement of these materials throughout the project, APRE is well positioned to embed them into its ongoing training and capacity-building activities directed at Horizon Europe applicants and beneficiaries, ensuring that the practical guidance on dissemination and exploitation developed within PATTERN reaches a relevant and receptive professional audience at the national level.</p>
UMinho	<p>The University of Minho will reuse and incorporate the PATTERN training materials on Open Access and FAIR Research Data Management into its community training programmes, including summer and winter schools, the Doctoral College and the annual Open Access Week activities. These channels provide a structured and recurring institutional framework for the continued delivery of PATTERN content to researchers and doctoral candidates. In addition, UMinho will actively promote its contribution to PATTERN and raise its profile within the national open science community, contributing to wider awareness of the project's outputs and to the consolidation of open science training capacity at the national level in Portugal.</p>
LOBA	<p>As Exploitation Manager and contributing partner to the Dissemination and Exploitation training, LOBA intends to</p>

	<p>make direct use of the training materials developed and refined through PATTERN in its post-project activities. LOBA's exploitation strategy centres on exploring a training-as-a-service model targeting Portuguese clients within its existing portfolio, including universities, research centres, technology transfer offices and Horizon Europe beneficiaries, who face a persistent need for practical guidance on dissemination and exploitation of research results.</p> <p>Building on the open CC BY 4.0 licence and the modular structure of the training, LOBA will assess the feasibility of packaging selected modules as a standalone professional service offer, combining access to the openly licensed materials with instructor-led sessions and customised guidance for specific client needs. This represents a commercially grounded exploitation route that complements the open dissemination pursued at consortium level, demonstrating that open licensing and viable business models can effectively coexist when training materials address a concrete and well-documented market need.</p>
<p>OpenAIRE</p>	<p>As part of its individual exploitation pathway, OpenAIRE will sign the joint ownership and open licensing arrangement with the relevant PATTERN partners for the “Open Access training” result, confirming the shared ownership and CC BY 4.0 release of the training materials while clarifying the terms for reuse, attribution, third-party content, derivative works, and future updates. OpenAIRE’s role is particularly connected to the long-term technical and content maintenance of the training result through OpenPlato, which serves as the main delivery and preservation environment for the self-paced learning materials. OpenAIRE is also the responsible party maintaining the Articulate Rise 360 account through which the SCORM packages have been produced, adjusted, and prepared for deployment as self-paced courses. In collaboration with affiliated partners belonging to the NOADs network and the wider OpenAIRE training community, OpenAIRE will continue to support the adaptation, updating, hosting, and exploitation of these materials beyond the grant period, ensuring that the PATTERN training outputs remain reusable, accessible, and integrated into OpenAIRE’s broader Training-as-a-Service and Open Science capacity-building activities.</p>
<p>ESF</p>	<p>ESF has extensive expertise in the development of policy recommendations across a variety of research and innovation fields, particularly through participatory</p>

	<p>processes such as policy dialogues and co-creation activities. PATTERN policy outputs will be reused and built on in other EU-funded projects and further research ESF is involved in. The policy outputs will continue being disseminated after the project ends, to highlight their relevance to Quadruple Helix representatives (policymakers, academia, civil society and private sector) and contribute to widespread of PATTERN training as well as to a broader understanding of policy mechanisms needed for the trainings' successful embedding and reuse.</p>
ZSI	<p>ZSI led the design and implementation of PATTERN's evaluation framework, including the development of the participant questionnaire and evaluation activity, the facilitator reflection tool, and the interview methodology. This body of evaluation expertise and the tested instruments are directly reusable. ZSI can provide this expertise and methodologies in evaluation design as part of future Open Science and RRI training initiatives, both in European projects and through national funding programmes. Further, the evaluation instruments will be made available as an open, adaptable instrument for other programme evaluators. ZSI will further exploit the findings by publishing the evaluation methodology and results in academic and practitioner-oriented outlets.</p>
SISSA	<p>In line with its well-established and comprehensive programme of talent valorisation initiatives targeting PhD students and postdoctoral researchers, SISSA will keep promoting on its website all PATTERN training material, with particular emphasis on self-paced courses. Asynchronous courses on Science Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Research Results, Gender Equality Non-Discrimination and Inclusion may also find additional space in specific sections (private or public) of the website managed, respectively, by the Communications Office, the Research office and the Equal Opportunities and Wellbeing Committee. SISSA will also keep using the materials developed for the Pattern course on Science communication for internal or external training opportunities, when needed. Building on the open CC BY 4.0 licence, the School may also expand its offer by delivering dedicated training courses on topics previously piloted or other topics of strategic importance for both research environments and career development – such as those mentioned above</p>
DANS	<p>As a Dutch national centre of expertise and repository for research data, DANS plays an important role in the Dutch training landscape on FAIR RDM. DANS has a dedicated</p>

	<p>training team with a wide range of expertise in Open Science, research data management, and research infrastructures. We offer both disciplinary-specific and general training as in-person, online, and asynchronous sessions/courses.</p> <p>The trainings materials developed in the PATTERN project fit seamlessly in our training portfolio and the modular structure will allow us to select appropriate topic depending on the various events and audiences that we aim to reach and teach.</p> <p>Our network of training partners includes Research Data Netherlands (RDNL), Open Science NL (OSNL), The National Coordination Point Research Data Management (LCRDM) the Data Stewards Interest Group (DSIG), the Netherlands Open Science Communities. For all these partners partial reuse of the PATTERN FAIR RDM training materials in (shared) training events is relevant and made possible because all materials are sustainably stored on Zenodo and OpenPlato will ensure long term access to the eLearning modules, whereas the license allows for any adaptation and updating if appropriate.</p>
RBI	<p>Moving forward, RBI will systematically utilize and build upon existing Science Communication and Open Access materials, seamlessly integrating these practices and curricula into our institutional processes and long-term strategies. These resources will serve as a cornerstone for the continuous organization of winter schools, specialized workshops, and other tailored educational initiatives designed to empower researchers at all stages of their careers. The materials made available under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0. licence in Zenodo and the RBI's institutional repository will further promote PATTERN's legacy.</p>
SciLink	<p>SciLink will integrate the PATTERN Mental Health and Leadership training into its existing portfolio of professional development courses for researchers, supervisors, doctoral schools and research managers. The course will be offered to institutional clients requiring tailored interventions on researcher wellbeing, leadership and healthy research cultures.</p>

Table 2 - Individual exploitation plans

4.1 An “early-exploitation” success story

One of the most concrete demonstrations of PATTERN's exploitation potential during the project's lifespan came from outside the consortium itself. SCOIR, a project in the Irish research support landscape and connected to OpenAIRE,

made active use of PATTERN's Open Access training materials hosted on the OpenPlato platform during the project period. This represents a clear instance of early, unsolicited third-party exploitation, where an external actor independently identified value in PATTERN's outputs and integrated them into its own activities without requiring any formal transfer or commercialisation process.

SCOIR enriched the PATTERN Open Access materials with guidance drawn from the Irish legal and policy environment, adapting them to support alignment between everyday research practice and national open access frameworks. At the same time, this use fed Ireland-specific expertise and implementation experience back into the broader European ecosystem, illustrating how openly licensed training resources can simultaneously serve local needs and strengthen pan-European knowledge exchange.

This case is significant for two reasons. First, it validates the accessibility and practical utility of the CC BY 4.0 licensing model adopted for PATTERN's training outputs: the open licence enabled a third party to reuse and adapt the materials without administrative friction, exactly as intended. Second, it demonstrates that the exploitation of PATTERN results does not begin at project closure but can and does occur organically during implementation, when materials are of sufficient quality and visibility to attract independent uptake. SCOIR's use of the Open Access training materials stands as an early proof of concept for the wider exploitation ambitions described in this chapter.

5 Horizon Results Booster

The PATTERN Project engaged with the Horizon Results Booster (HRB) service on two separate occasions during the project lifecycle, each targeting a different stage of exploitation maturity and a different scope of KER development.

5.1 Joint Go-to-Market Service with REINFORCING and ECS

The first HRB engagement took the form of a Go-to-Market (G2M) service carried out jointly by PATTERN, REINFORCING and the European Citizen Science (ECS) project. The three beneficiaries involved in this joint service were Fondazione Giannino Bassetti ETS (representing REINFORCING), ECSA (representing ECS), and APRE/ LOBA (representing PATTERN). The Expert was appointed in April 2025, with service delivery running across two modules: Module A (Kick-off) and Module B (Unique Value Proposition and Key Exploitable Results).

The rationale for a joint application was the thematic overlap between the three projects, all operating in the field of open and responsible research and innovation (ORRI), and the strategic interest in exploring whether their respective platforms and training offerings could be jointly exploited as a coherent ecosystem rather than as three separate outputs.

Two joint Key Exploitable Results were identified and developed throughout the service.

- KER1 was focused on the digital ecosystems and platforms of the three projects (the ORRI Platform of REINFORCING, the PATTERN OpenPlato and Projects Platform and the ECS Platform). The three platforms were grouped as a one centralised hub providing visibility, practical guidance and community support on open RRI practices of the three projects.
- KER2 was focused on the training activities, curricula and guides of the three projects (ORRI Trainings/Guidelines, PATTERN Trainings and ECS Academy). The three set of training and guidelines results were, grouped into a joint offering targeting researchers, research support professionals, civil society organisations and policy practitioners.

During Module A, an Exploitation Pillars training session was held in October 2025, where the basic concepts of exploitation were introduced, the final list of joint KERs was agreed, and the target adopter groups were discussed and refined. The session produced improved Exploitation Intentions tables for both KERs, clarifying common end user segments, competitive advantages, use models, and relevant partner roles. During Module B, two Unique Value Proposition (UVP) workshops were held in January 2026, one per KER, producing Value Proposition Canvases and Market Definition Canvases for

each. These tools were applied to multiple end user profiles, researchers, funding agency officers, and CSO professional, enabling a granular mapping of customer jobs, pains, gains, pain relievers and gain creators for each joint KER.

The expert's final recommendations highlighted that the platforms and training outputs are already operational and in active use, which represents a significant advantage in terms of exploitation readiness. However, the expert noted that fully-fledged joint exploitation would require the three consortia to define a shared vision, goals, roadmap, milestones and measurable targets. For KER1, the recommendation was to formalise a joint portfolio of services across the three platforms and prioritise specific adopter segments, with businesses identified as an underexplored group, before broadening outreach. For KER2, the expert recommended narrowing the joint exploitation focus to a selected subset of the most complementary training offerings rather than aggregating all outputs and developing a joint training catalogue to support market positioning.

The report is provided in Annex 4.

5.2 PATTERN Go-to-Market Service

The second HRB engagement was a G2M service carried out by PATTERN independently, building on the exploitation foundation established in the First Strategic Exploitation Plan (D5.4). This service focused on three PATTERN-specific Key Exploitable Results.

KER1 covered the PATTERN Platform, the federated training and discovery infrastructure built on OpenPlato (Moodle/Django/Vue.js), hosted by OpenAIRE and Projects hosted by LPI. The Market Definition Canvas developed for this KER identified institutional training owners and platform administrators at research-performing organisations as the primary job executors, whose core job-to-be-done is to deliver, federate and track OS/RRI training at scale across institutions with compliant federation and long-term persistence. KER2 covered PATTERN's modular training offer (eight thematic training packages spanning Open Access, FAIR Research Data Management, Research Integrity, Gender Non-discrimination and Inclusion, Science Communication, Citizen Science, Dissemination and Exploitation, and Management and Leadership) packaged with trainer/learner kits, micro-credentials and SCORM/xAPI-compatible LMS bundles. The Market Definition Canvas for KER2 identified researchers and R&I support staff as the primary job executors seeking to acquire and evidence OS/ RRI competencies required by funders while fitting busy schedules and local institutional contexts. KER3 covered PATTERN's analytical output (the open report, machine-readable dataset and dashboard mapping and analysing RRI/Open Science trainings across Europe) with institutional training decision-makers

at universities and research-performing organisations identified as the primary users, whose job-to-be-done is to benchmark and prioritise their institution's RRI/OS training portfolio across the European landscape to guide investments and compliance.

The Exploitation Intentions table produced during this service complemented the KER mapping with a structured overview of exploitation claims per asset, IP status, relevant partners, timing and use models. This work fed directly into the preparation of the present Final Strategic Exploitation Plan and informed the updated exploitation plans presented in Chapter 5.

All documentation is provided in Annex 5.

6 Conclusions

This Final Strategic Exploitation Plan represents the concluding deliverable of PATTERN's exploitation strategy, submitted at M42 upon project completion. It substantially expands upon the First Strategic Exploitation Plan (D5.4, M13), reflecting the full maturation of the project's results, the consolidation of its IP management framework and the concrete exploitation commitments made by consortium partners for the post-project period.

Over its 42-month lifetime, PATTERN has generated eleven Key Exploitable Results spanning eight thematic training courses, two digital platforms, a Trainers Directory and a cumulative policy framework. All results have been released under CC BY 4.0, ensuring their continued accessibility, reusability and adaptability beyond the grant period. The IP management framework developed and applied throughout the project (grounded in the Grant Agreement, the Consortium Agreement, and three dedicated joint ownership instruments) has provided the consortium with a legally sound and operationally practical basis for managing both single and jointly owned results, including the technical specificities introduced by the Articulate Rise 360 e-learning environment.

The project's exploitation trajectory has been actively supported by two engagements with the Horizon Results Booster, which provided structured methodological tools (Exploitation Intentions tables, Value Proposition Canvases and Market Definition Canvases) that sharpened the consortium's understanding of its target markets, competitive advantages and exploitation pathways, both at the level of individual PATTERN KERs and in the context of joint exploitation with sister projects REINFORCING and ECS.

The individual exploitation plans presented in Chapter 4 confirm that PATTERN's results will not remain confined to the project period. Consortium partners across all organisations have made concrete commitments to sustained use, including institutional curriculum integration, national accreditation, professional training programme embedding, platform uptake by new universities and European initiatives, and the exploration of commercially grounded training-as-a-service models. The early exploitation case of SCOIR further demonstrates that the project's open licensing approach has already enabled independent third-party uptake during the project's own lifetime. A meaningful indicator of the quality, accessibility and practical relevance of PATTERN's training outputs.

The identification of the Trainers Directory as a new Key Exploitable Result in the final trimester of the project points to an important direction for post-project sustainability: the conversion of PATTERN's accumulated training expertise into a structured professional service offer. This model, if pursued, would represent a transition from open resource dissemination to active knowledge brokering, enabling PATTERN's impact to reach institutional clients who require tailored, delivered training rather than self-directed access to open materials.

Taken together, the results documented in this report demonstrate that PATTERN has fulfilled its exploitation objectives: producing high-quality, openly licensed training outputs across eight transferable skill areas; establishing a sound IP management architecture; engaging systematically with exploitation support services and securing concrete post-project uptake commitments from all consortium partners. The foundation laid by the project provides a credible basis for continued impact in the European open science training landscape well beyond the conclusion of the grant.

7 Annexes

7.1 Annex 1 Joint Ownership Agreement template

JOINT OWNERSHIP AND OPEN LICENSING AGREEMENT

Concerning a Training Result Generated Under the PATTERN Project

Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101094416

Call: HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01

“Piloting open and responsible Activities and Trainings Towards the Enhancement of Researchers Networks” (PATTERN)

DRAFTING NOTE ,REMOVE BEFORE SIGNATURE. All 14 PATTERN beneficiaries are pre-listed in Article 1 below for convenience. Joint ownership only arises among the beneficiaries that *actually contributed* to the training Result and whose contributions cannot be separately attributed (HE MGA Art. 16.4). **DELETE the entries for any beneficiary that did not contribute to this specific training.** The signature blocks at the end must match the list in Article 1.

1. The Parties

This Joint Ownership and Open Licensing Agreement (hereinafter the “Agreement”) is entered into by and between the following beneficiaries of Grant Agreement No. 101094416 ,PATTERN, who have jointly generated the training Result described in Article 3 and are hereinafter collectively referred to as the “Joint Owners” and individually as a “Joint Owner”:

- **AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA (APRE)**, PIC 999514191, established in VIA CAVOUR 71, ROMA 00184, Italy (Coordinator of the Project), represented by [name, position];
- **AARHUS UNIVERSITET (AU)**, PIC 999997736, established in NORDRE RINGGADE 1, AARHUS C 8000, Denmark, represented by [name, position];
- **GLOBAZ, S.A. (LOBA)**, PIC 983211983, established in LARGO LUIS DE CAMOES EDIFICIO RAINHA PISO 12, OLIVEIRA DE AZEMEIS 3720-232, Portugal, represented by [name, position];
- **FONDATION EUROPEENNE DE LA SCIENCE (ESF)**, PIC 999987939, established in QUAI LEZAY MARNESIA 1, STRASBOURG CEDEX 67080, France, represented by [name, position];
- **ZENTRUM FÜR SOZIALE INNOVATION GMBH (ZSI)**, PIC 940719872, established in LINKE WIENZEILE 246, WIEN 1150, Austria, represented by [name, position];
- **SCUOLA INTERNAZIONALE SUPERIORE DI STUDI AVANZATI DI TRIESTE (SISSA)**, PIC 999850878, established in VIA BONOMEA 265, TRIESTE 34136, Italy, represented by [name, position];
- **CENTRE DE RECHERCHE INTERDISCIPLINAIRE (CRI)**, PIC 919923460, established in 8-10 RUE CHARLES V, PARIS 75004, France, represented by [name, position];
- **OPENAIRE AMKE (OpenAIRE)**, PIC 903914192, established in 6 ARTEMIDOS STR and EPIDAVROU, MAROUSI 15125, Greece, represented by [name, position];
- **EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION OF RESEARCH MANAGERS AND ADMINISTRATORS (EARMA)**, PIC 954279114, established in RUE JOSEPH II 36-38, BRUXELLES 1000, Belgium, represented by [name, position];

Joint Ownership and Open Licensing Agreement – PATTERN (GA 101094416)

- **UNIVERSITA VITA-SALUTE SAN RAFFAELE (UniSR)**, PIC 999854467, established in VIA OLGETTINA 58, MILANO 20132, Italy, represented by [name, position];
- **KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN - KNAW (KNAW)**, PIC 999518362, established in KLOVENIERSBURGWAL 29 HET TRIPPENHUIS, AMSTERDAM 1011 JV, Netherlands, represented by [name, position];
- **RUDER BOSKOVIC INSTITUTE (RBI)**, PIC 999875031, established in Bijenicka cesta 54, ZAGREB 10000, Croatia, represented by [name, position];
- **STICHTING SCILINK (SciLink)**, PIC 904112460, established in VAN DER PALMKADE 121, AMSTERDAM 1051 RH, Netherlands, represented by [name, position];
- **UNIVERSIDADE DO MINHO (UMinho)**, PIC 999995505, established in LARGO DO PACO, BRAGA 4704-553, Portugal, represented by [name, position];

2. Recitals

WHEREAS the Joint Owners are beneficiaries of Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101094416 (the “Grant Agreement” or “GA”), signed with the European Research Executive Agency (REA) under call HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01, for the implementation of the project “Piloting open and responsible Activities and Trainings Towards the Enhancement of Researchers Networks” (acronym: PATTERN), of 42 months duration starting on 1 January 2023;

WHEREAS the overall aim of PATTERN is to promote Open and Responsible Research and Innovation by developing and piloting training activities for researchers, with Work Package 2 (WP2) dedicated to the production of training materials and a training and discovery platform;

WHEREAS the Joint Owners have jointly generated, in the context of WP2 / Task [TASK NUMBER] / Deliverable [D-NUMBER], a training result consisting of a set of educational materials further described in Article 3 (the “Result”);

WHEREAS each Joint Owner has contributed to the generation of the Result in a manner that cannot be separately attributed to one Joint Owner only, such that the Result qualifies as a jointly owned result within the meaning of Article 16.4 of the Grant Agreement (Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement, hereinafter “HE MGA”);

WHEREAS Article 16.4 of the HE MGA requires joint owners to agree in writing on the allocation and terms of exercise of their joint ownership, and permits them to depart from the default regime set out in that Article;

WHEREAS the Joint Owners wish to disseminate the Result as widely as possible by releasing it under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Public License (“CC BY 4.0”), in line with the open science and dissemination obligations of Article 17 of the Grant Agreement, the European Commission’s open science policy and the PATTERN project’s commitment to open and responsible research;

NOW, THEREFORE, the Joint Owners agree as follows:

3. Definition and Scope of the Result

3.1 The “Result” means the PATTERN training package entitled “[TRAINING TITLE]”, designed to be delivered in both synchronous and asynchronous modes to researchers and other learners, made available on the OpenPlato training platform (openplato.eu) and on Projects platform (pattern.projects.directory) deposited on Zenodo as part of the EU Open Research Repository under DOI [10.5281/zenodo.XXXXX], version [vX], dated [DATE]. The Result includes without limitation:

- Slide decks ,.pptx + .pdf renderings
- Trainer / session-planning docs ,.docx + .pdf
- Participant / activity materials ,.docx + .pdf
- Assessment and evaluation materials ,.docx + .pdf
- Adapted or original graphical assets ,.ai, .eps, .svg, .png, .jpg
- Audiovisual content ,.mp4, .mp3, .wav (where applicable)
- Image-credit and licensing metadata ,.txt, .md, .pdf
- LMS-ready packages ,SCORM, xAPI, IMS Common Cartridge

3.2 The Result comprises the original textual content, instructional design, session structure, graphical adaptations and audiovisual works authored by the Joint Owners in the course of PATTERN WP2. The CC BY 4.0 release under Article 5 applies to those original contributions and to such adaptations as are themselves protectable and produced in accordance with the source-material licences.

3.3 The Result **does NOT** include, and the CC BY 4.0 release under Article 5 does NOT extend to: (i) underlying third-party graphical, audiovisual, textual or software assets incorporated into the Result (including, by way of example, stock images sourced from providers such as Freepik, Unsplash, Pexels, Adobe Stock or equivalent; fonts; icons; quoted text; datasets); (ii) trademarks, logos or service marks of any party; or (iii) the OpenPlato platform, the Zenodo platform, the PATTERN project website and any other third-party tools or platforms used to host or deliver the Result. Such excluded items remain subject to their own respective licence terms, as documented in Annex II.

3.4 The Lesson Package as deposited on Zenodo is the authoritative version of the Result. Any prior internal working version (including drafts circulated within WP2 or among the Joint Owners) is superseded by, and does not form part of, the Result for the purposes of this Agreement.

4. Joint Ownership and Shares

4.1 The Joint Owners hereby acknowledge and confirm that they are the joint owners of the Result, in the following undivided ownership shares (to be completed by the consortium; equal shares apply by default in the absence of agreed allocation):

- [Beneficiary X]: [XX] %;
- [Beneficiary Y]: [XX] %;
- [etc.].

4.2 Notwithstanding Article 4.1, the Joint Owners agree that the allocation of ownership shares shall not affect, restrict or modify the rights and obligations set out in Articles 5 to 8 of this Agreement, which apply **equally** to all Joint Owners.

5. Release of the Result under CC BY 4.0

5.1 The Joint Owners hereby unanimously and irrevocably agree to release the Result to the public under the **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Public License (CC BY 4.0)**, available at <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>.

5.2 This Agreement constitutes the prior written agreement required under Article 16.4 of the Horizon Europe (HE) Model Grant Agreement (MGA). The Joint Owners expressly waive the default joint-ownership regime of Article 16.4 of the HE MGA, in particular: (i) any requirement of prior notice to the other Joint Owners before granting non-exclusive licences to the Result; and (ii) any entitlement to fair and reasonable compensation in respect of the CC BY 4.0 release of the Result.

5.3 Each Joint Owner shall ensure that, where the Result is made publicly available, including through the PATTERN project website, the PATTERN training and discovery platform, the EU Open Research Repository, Zenodo (where OpenAIRE deposit obligations apply under Article 17 of the GA), or any other repository, the CC BY 4.0 licence notice is prominently displayed alongside the Result, together with the attribution information set out in Article 6.

5.4 The Joint Owners acknowledge that CC BY 4.0 is irrevocable with respect to copies of the Result already distributed under that licence, and that any later decision to cease distribution does not terminate licences already granted to third parties.

6. Attribution Form

6.1 In accordance with Section 3(a) of CC BY 4.0, the required attribution for any use of the Result shall be in the following form (or a reasonable equivalent depending on the medium):

This document is published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) licence. You are free to share (copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format) and adapt (remix, transform, and build upon the material) for any purpose, including commercially, provided that appropriate credit is given and any changes are indicated. If you adapt or build upon this material, you must indicate the changes made and may not suggest that the PATTERN Consortium endorses your version. Full licence terms: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

This document was developed by the PATTERN project funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101094416. The content reflects only the views of the PATTERN Consortium; the

European Union and the granting authority bear no responsibility for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

6.2 The order of listing of the Joint Owners in the attribution shall be alphabetical by short name. In addition, the funding statement “Funded by the European Union” and the EU emblem shall accompany the attribution wherever feasible, in accordance with Article 17.2 of the Grant Agreement. The standard disclaimer required by Article 17.3 (“Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”) shall be included where appropriate.

6.3 The names, logos and trademarks of the Joint Owners, of the PATTERN project, of the European Union and of REA are **not** licensed under this Agreement or under CC BY 4.0 (see Section 2(b)(3) of CC BY 4.0). Their use beyond the attribution required by Article 6.1 and the visibility obligations of Article 17.2 of the GA requires the prior written consent of the relevant rights holder.

7. Third-Party Material and Background

7.1 The Joint Owners acknowledge that the Result may incorporate third-party material that is not owned by any Joint Owner, including but not limited to: images, icons, fonts, stock photographs, software screenshots, quoted text, datasets and Background (within the meaning of Article 16.1 of the GA).

7.2 Any such third-party material is identified in Annex II and remains subject to its own licence. The CC BY 4.0 release under Article 5 applies only to the original contributions of the Joint Owners and does NOT purport to relicense any third-party material.

7.3 Each Joint Owner warrants that the material it has contributed to the Result is either (i) original to that Joint Owner and free of third-party rights that would prevent its release under CC BY 4.0, or (ii) duly cleared for such release. Each Joint Owner shall indemnify the other Joint Owners against third-party claims arising from a breach of this warranty in relation to the material it contributed.

8. Derivative Works and Parallel Licensing

8.1 Derivative works by third parties. Pursuant to Section 2(a)(1)(B) of CC BY 4.0, third parties may reproduce, share and adapt the Result, including for commercial purposes, provided they comply with the attribution requirements of Article 6 and indicate whether changes were made. Adaptations and derivative works produced by third parties may be released under any licence chosen by the adapter, including more restrictive licences; the original Result, however, remains available under CC BY 4.0.

8.2 Derivative works by Joint Owners. Each Joint Owner is entitled to create and disseminate derivative works of the Result (for example, translations, updates, sector-specific or institutional adaptations, integration into other training programmes, deployment on the PATTERN platform or successor platforms). Such derivative works may be released under CC BY 4.0 or, where they constitute genuinely new and substantial works, under any other licence chosen by the Joint Owner producing

them. In all cases, the original Result remains available under CC BY 4.0 and must be attributed in accordance with Article 6.

8.3 Parallel commercial / alternative licensing. The CC BY 4.0 release is non-exclusive. Each Joint Owner expressly retains the right to use, reproduce, distribute, communicate, perform, modify and exploit the Result, in whole or in part, under terms different from CC BY 4.0 (including, without limitation, under proprietary, commercial or restricted-access terms), provided that:

- such alternative use does not compromise or revoke the CC BY 4.0 release of the Result already made under Article 5;
- such alternative use complies with the open science, dissemination and exploitation obligations of the Grant Agreement (in particular Articles 16 and 17); and
- such alternative use does not misrepresent the Result as being subject to terms more restrictive than CC BY 4.0 in respect of copies of the Result distributed under CC BY 4.0.

8.4 Revenue. Each Joint Owner is entitled to retain any revenue it generates from its own parallel commercial or alternative licensing under Article 8.3, without any obligation to account to or compensate the other Joint Owners, save where otherwise agreed in writing in the PATTERN Consortium Agreement.

9. Updates, Versioning and Maintenance

9.1 The version of the Result to which this Agreement applies is Version [X.Y], dated [DATE], as listed in Annex I.

9.2 Subsequent versions of the Result shall be released under CC BY 4.0 on the same terms, unless the Joint Owners unanimously agree otherwise in writing. The Joint Owner responsible for publishing each version (the “Coordinating Owner”) shall be [BENEFICIARY SHORT NAME, typically the WP2 leader], or such other Joint Owner as the consortium may designate.

9.3 The obligations of this Agreement survive the end of the PATTERN project (currently scheduled for 30 June 2026), in line with the post-project obligations under Articles 16 and 17 of the Grant Agreement.

10. Representations, Warranties and Liability

10.1 Each Joint Owner represents and warrants that it has full power and authority to enter into this Agreement and to grant the rights set out herein.

10.2 Save for the warranty in Article 7.3, the Result is released “as is”, in accordance with Section 5 of CC BY 4.0, without any warranty of fitness, accuracy or non-infringement, to the maximum extent permitted by applicable law.

10.3 Nothing in this Agreement limits or excludes any liability that cannot be limited or excluded under applicable mandatory law, including liability for fraud, gross negligence or wilful misconduct.

11. Relationship to the Grant and Consortium Agreements

11.1 This Agreement is concluded in implementation of, and is subject to, the Grant Agreement and the PATTERN Consortium Agreement.

11.2 In the event of any conflict between this Agreement and the Grant Agreement, the Grant Agreement shall prevail. In the event of any conflict between this Agreement and the PATTERN Consortium Agreement regarding the joint ownership and licensing of the Result, this Agreement shall prevail as the specific written agreement contemplated by Article 16.4 of the HE MGA, save for matters expressly reserved to the Consortium Agreement.

12. Term, Governing Law and Disputes

12.1 This Agreement enters into force on the date of last signature and remains in force for the duration of the copyright in the Result. The irrevocable nature of CC BY 4.0 survives the termination of this Agreement.

12.2 In accordance with Article 43 of the Grant Agreement, this Agreement shall be governed by the applicable EU law, supplemented if necessary by the law of Belgium.

12.3 Any dispute arising out of or in connection with this Agreement shall, first, be resolved amicably in accordance with the dispute resolution mechanism set out in the PATTERN Consortium Agreement. Failing amicable settlement, disputes shall be brought, for EU beneficiaries, before the General Court of the European Union (with appeal to the Court of Justice of the European Union) and, for non-EU beneficiaries, before the Courts of Brussels, Belgium, in accordance with Article 43 of the Grant Agreement, unless an international agreement provides for the enforceability of EU court judgements in the relevant jurisdiction.

13. Execution

This Agreement is executed in as many originals as there are Joint Owners (one for each Joint Owner) or, alternatively, by qualified electronic signature in accordance with Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 (eIDAS), each of which shall constitute an original.

For AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA (APRE)

Name of Authorised Signatory: _____

Position / Title: _____

Date: _____ Place: _____

Signature: _____

For AARHUS UNIVERSITET (AU)

Name of Authorised Signatory: _____

Position / Title: _____

Date: _____ Place: _____

Signature: _____

For GLOBAZ, S.A. (LOBA)

Name of Authorised Signatory: _____
Position / Title: _____
Date: _____ Place: _____
Signature: _____

For FONDATION EUROPEENNE DE LA SCIENCE (ESF)

Name of Authorised Signatory: _____
Position / Title: _____
Date: _____ Place: _____
Signature: _____

For ZENTRUM FUR SOZIALE INNOVATION GMBH (ZSI)

Name of Authorised Signatory: _____
Position / Title: _____
Date: _____ Place: _____
Signature: _____

For SCUOLA INTERNAZIONALE SUPERIORE DI STUDI AVANZATI DI TRIESTE (SISSA)

Name of Authorised Signatory: _____
Position / Title: _____
Date: _____ Place: _____
Signature: _____

For CENTRE DE RECHERCHE INTERDISCIPLINAIRE (CRI)

Name of Authorised Signatory: _____
Position / Title: _____
Date: _____ Place: _____
Signature: _____

For OPENAIRE AMKE (OpenAIRE)

Name of Authorised Signatory: _____
Position / Title: _____
Date: _____ Place: _____
Signature: _____

For EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION OF RESEARCH MANAGERS AND ADMINISTRATORS (EARMA)

Name of Authorised Signatory: _____
Position / Title: _____
Date: _____ Place: _____
Signature: _____

For UNIVERSITA VITA-SALUTE SAN RAFFAELE (UnISR)

Name of Authorised Signatory: _____
Position / Title: _____

Joint Ownership and Open Licensing Agreement – PATTERN (GA 101094416)

Date: _____ Place: _____
Signature: _____

For KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN - KNAW (KNAW)

Name of Authorised Signatory: _____
Position / Title: _____
Date: _____ Place: _____
Signature: _____

For RUDER BOSKOVIC INSTITUTE (RBI)

Name of Authorised Signatory: _____
Position / Title: _____
Date: _____ Place: _____
Signature: _____

For STICHTING SCILINK (SciLink)

Name of Authorised Signatory: _____
Position / Title: _____
Date: _____ Place: _____
Signature: _____

For UNIVERSIDADE DO MINHO (UMinho)

Name of Authorised Signatory: _____
Position / Title: _____
Date: _____ Place: _____
Signature: _____

Annex I ,Inventory of Materials Constituting the Result

[List each file / module with: title, format, version, date, contributing Joint Owner(s), repository URL (PATTERN platform / Zenodo / project website), DOI if assigned.]

Annex II ,Third-Party Material Embedded in the Result

[List each third-party item with: description, source, rights holder, applicable licence (e.g. CC BY-SA, royalty-free stock licence, fair-dealing/quotation), and the location within the Result where it appears.]

7.2 Annex 2 Side Letter

\PATTERN — Joint Ownership Side Letter (GA 101094416)

JOINT OWNERSHIP SIDE LETTER

FAIR Research Data Management Training

PATTERN — Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101094416

Date: [DATE]

Place: [PLACE]

Between:

- **AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA (APRE)**, PIC 999514191, established in VIA CAVOUR 71, ROMA 00184, Italy (Coordinator of the Project), represented by [name, position];
- **AARHUS UNIVERSITET (AU)**, PIC 999997736, established in NORDRE RINGGADE 1, AARHUS C 8000, Denmark, represented by [name, position];
- **GLOBAZ, S.A. (LOBA)**, PIC 983211983, established in LARGO LUIS DE CAMOES EDIFICIO RAINHA PISO 12, OLIVEIRA DE AZEMEIS 3720-232, Portugal, represented by [name, position];
- **FONDATION EUROPEENNE DE LA SCIENCE (ESF)**, PIC 999987939, established in QUAI LEZAY MARNESIA 1, STRASBOURG CEDEX 67080, France, represented by [name, position];
- **ZENTRUM FUR SOZIALE INNOVATION GMBH (ZSI)**, PIC 940719872, established in LINKE WIENZEILE 246, WIEN 1150, Austria, represented by [name, position];
- **SCUOLA INTERNAZIONALE SUPERIORE DI STUDI AVANZATI DI TRIESTE (SISSA)**, PIC 999850878, established in VIA BONOMEA 265, TRIESTE 34136, Italy, represented by [name, position];
- **CENTRE DE RECHERCHE INTERDISCIPLINAIRE (CRI)**, PIC 919923460, established in 8-10 RUE CHARLES V, PARIS 75004, France, represented by [name, position];
- **OPENAIRE AMKE (OpenAIRE)**, PIC 903914192, established in 6 ARTEMIDOS STR and EPIDAVROU, MAROUSI 15125, Greece, represented by [name, position];
- **EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION OF RESEARCH MANAGERS AND ADMINISTRATORS (EARMA)**, PIC 954279114, established in RUE JOSEPH II 36-38, BRUXELLES 1000, Belgium, represented by [name, position];
- **UNIVERSITA VITA-SALUTE SAN RAFFAELE (UnISR)**, PIC 999854467, established in VIA OLGETTINA 58, MILANO 20132, Italy, represented by [name, position];
- **KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN - KNAW (KNAW)**, PIC 999518362, established in KLOVENIERSBURGWAL 29 HET TRIPPENHUIS, AMSTERDAM 1011 JV, Netherlands, represented by [name, position];
- **RUDER BOSKOVIC INSTITUTE (RBI)**, PIC 999875031, established in Bijenicka cesta 54, ZAGREB 10000, Croatia, represented by [name, position];

- **STICHTING SCILINK (SciLink)**, PIC 904112460, established in VAN DER PALMKADE 121, AMSTERDAM 1051 RH, Netherlands, represented by [name, position];
- **UNIVERSIDADE DO MINHO (UMinho)**, PIC 999995505, established in LARGO DO PACO, BRAGA 4704-553, Portugal, represented by [name, position];

hereinafter individually a “Party” and collectively the “Parties”.

Context

The Parties have jointly developed, in the framework of Work Package [WP NUMBER] of the PATTERN project (Horizon Europe Grant Agreement (GA) No. 101094416, call HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01), a training lesson entitled “Open Access training” (the “Result”), comprising slide decks, trainer guides, participant materials, adapted graphical assets, image-credit files and related materials, deposited on Zenodo under DOI [10.5281/zenodo.XXXXX] (version [vX], dated [DATE]) and delivered through the OpenPlato platform.

Contributions of the Parties to the Result cannot be separately attributed to one Party only, with the consequence that the Result is jointly owned by the Parties within the meaning of Article 16.4 of the PATTERN Grant Agreement (the “GA”).

In view of the affiliated-entity relationship between the Parties under Article 8 of the GA, and of their shared commitment to open science, the Parties wish to record their joint ownership and licensing arrangements in the form of this side letter, while ensuring full compliance with Article 16.4 of the GA.

The Parties agree as follows:

- 1. Joint ownership.** The Parties confirm that they are the joint owners of the Result in equal undivided shares. This side letter constitutes the written agreement required by Article 16.4 of the GA.
- 2. Open licensing.** The Parties agree to release the Result to the public under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Public License (CC BY 4.0), available at <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>. The Parties expressly waive, between themselves, the default joint-ownership regime of Article 16.4 of the GA, including the 45-day prior-notice requirement and the entitlement to fair and reasonable compensation, insofar as such regime would apply to the CC BY 4.0 release or to any other non-exclusive licence consistent with CC BY 4.0.
- 3. Attribution.** Both Parties shall be credited in any public use of the Result, in the following form (or a reasonable equivalent depending on the medium):

“This document is published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) licence. You are free to share (copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format) and adapt (remix, transform, and build upon the material) for any purpose, including commercially, provided that appropriate credit is given and any changes are indicated. If you adapt or build upon this material, you must indicate the changes made and may not suggest that the PATTERN Consortium

endorses your version. Full licence terms:
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

This document was developed by the PATTERN project funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101094416. The content reflects only the views of the PATTERN Consortium; the European Union and the granting authority bear no responsibility for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

The funding statement “Funded by the European Union” and the EU emblem shall accompany the attribution wherever feasible, in accordance with Article 17.2 of the GA. The disclaimer under Article 17.3 of the GA shall be included where appropriate. The names, logos and trademarks of the Parties and of the PATTERN project are not licensed under CC BY 4.0 and remain subject to their respective owners’ control.

4. Third-party material. The CC BY 4.0 release applies only to the original contributions of the Parties to the Result. It does not extend to third-party material embedded in the Result (including without limitation graphical assets sourced from Freepik or similar providers, fonts, icons, quoted text and datasets), which remains subject to its own respective licence. Each Party warrants that the material it contributed is either original and free of third-party rights preventing CC BY 4.0 release, or duly cleared for such release.

5. Derivative works and parallel licensing. Each Party may, independently and without prior notice to or compensation of the other Party, create and disseminate derivative works of the Result (including translations, institutional adaptations, integration into other training programmes) and may license its own use of the Result, in whole or in part, under terms other than CC BY 4.0 (including for commercial or restricted-access purposes), provided that the original Result remains available to the public under CC BY 4.0 and is attributed in accordance with Clause 3. Each Party retains any revenue it generates from such parallel use.

6. Updates. Subsequent versions of the Result released within the PATTERN project shall be released under CC BY 4.0 on the same terms, unless the Parties otherwise agree in writing (including by email exchange). [OpenAIRE / xxx — specify the Party responsible for publishing updates] shall act as coordinating owner for the purpose of publishing updates.

7. Relationship to the GA and Consortium Agreement. This side letter is concluded in implementation of Article 16.4 of the GA and is subject to the GA and to the PATTERN Consortium Agreement. In the event of conflict, the GA prevails, followed by this side letter (for matters concerning joint ownership and licensing of the Result), then the Consortium Agreement.

8. Governing law and disputes. This side letter is governed by EU law, supplemented if necessary by the law of Belgium, in accordance with Article 43 of the GA. The Parties shall first attempt to resolve any dispute amicably; failing which, the dispute resolution mechanism of the PATTERN Consortium Agreement applies.

9. Duration and form. This side letter enters into force on the date of last signature and remains in force for the duration of the copyright in the Result. The irrevocable nature of CC BY 4.0 survives

\PATTERN — Joint Ownership Side Letter (GA 101094416)

termination. The side letter may be signed in counterparts and by qualified electronic signature under Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 (eIDAS), each of which constitutes an original.

Signatures

For xxx

Name: _____
Position: _____
Date: _____ Place: _____
Signature: _____

For xxx

Name: _____
Position: _____
Date: _____ Place: _____
Signature: _____

For xxx

Name: _____
Position: _____
Date: _____ Place: _____
Signature: _____

For xxx

Name: _____
Position: _____
Date: _____ Place: _____
Signature: _____

7.3 Annex 3 E-Learning Courses Joint Ownership Agreement

PATTERN — E-Learning Courses Joint Ownership Agreement (GA 101094416)
JOINT OWNERSHIP AGREEMENT
E-Learning Courses — Work Package 2
PATTERN — Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101094416

Date: [DATE]

Place: [PLACE]

Among:

- **AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA (APRE)**, PIC 999514191, established in VIA CAVOUR 71, ROMA 00184, Italy (Coordinator of the Project), represented by [name, position];
- **AARHUS UNIVERSITET (AU)**, PIC 999997736, established in NORDRE RINGGADE 1, AARHUS C 8000, Denmark, represented by [name, position];
- **GLOBAZ, S.A. (LOBA)**, PIC 983211983, established in LARGO LUIS DE CAMOES EDIFICIO RAINHA PISO 12, OLIVEIRA DE AZEMEIS 3720-232, Portugal, represented by [name, position];
- **FONDATION EUROPEENNE DE LA SCIENCE (ESF)**, PIC 999987939, established in QUAI LEZAY MARNESIA 1, STRASBOURG CEDEX 67080, France, represented by [name, position];
- **ZENTRUM FUR SOZIALE INNOVATION GMBH (ZSI)**, PIC 940719872, established in LINKE WIENZEILE 246, WIEN 1150, Austria, represented by [name, position];
- **SCUOLA INTERNAZIONALE SUPERIORE DI STUDI AVANZATI DI TRIESTE (SISSA)**, PIC 999850878, established in VIA BONOMEA 265, TRIESTE 34136, Italy, represented by [name, position];
- **CENTRE DE RECHERCHE INTERDISCIPLINAIRE (CRI)**, PIC 919923460, established in 8-10 RUE CHARLES V, PARIS 75004, France, represented by [name, position];
- **OPENAIRE AMKE (OpenAIRE)**, PIC 903914192, established in 6 ARTEMIDOS STR and EPIDAVROU, MAROUSI 15125, Greece, represented by [name, position];
- **EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION OF RESEARCH MANAGERS AND ADMINISTRATORS (EARMA)**, PIC 954279114, established in RUE JOSEPH II 36-38, BRUXELLES 1000, Belgium, represented by [name, position];
- **UNIVERSITA VITA-SALUTE SAN RAFFAELE (UniSR)**, PIC 999854467, established in VIA OLGETTINA 58, MILANO 20132, Italy, represented by [name, position];
- **KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN - KNAW (KNAW)**, PIC 999518362, established in KLOVENIERSBURGWAL 29 HET TRIPPENHUIS, AMSTERDAM 1011 JV, Netherlands, represented by [name, position];

- **RUDER BOSKOVIC INSTITUTE (RBI)**, PIC 999875031, established in Bijenicka cesta 54, ZAGREB 10000, Croatia, represented by [name, position];
- **STICHTING SCILINK (SciLink)**, PIC 904112460, established in VAN DER PALMKADE 121, AMSTERDAM 1051 RH, Netherlands, represented by [name, position];
- **UNIVERSIDADE DO MINHO (UMinho)**, PIC 999995505, established in LARGO DO PACO, BRAGA 4704-553, Portugal, represented by [name, position];

[REMOVE PARTNERS]

hereinafter individually a “Party” and collectively the “Parties”.

Recitals

(A) The Parties are beneficiaries under the PATTERN project (Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101094416, call HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01) and have jointly developed, under Work Package 2 and Work Package 3, a series of eight self-paced e-learning courses listed in the Annex to this Agreement (each a “**Course**” and collectively the “**Courses**”).

(B) Each Course was produced through a division of labour between two categories of contribution: (i) the content contribution, consisting of the substantive educational material, text, learning objectives, examples and associated assets developed by the content partners identified for each Course in the Annex; and (ii) the instructional design and technical production contribution, consisting of the conversion of that content into an interactive e-learning format using Articulate Rise 360 and its deployment on the OpenPlato platform, carried out by OpenAIRE.

(C) Within each category of contribution, the individual inputs of contributing partners cannot be separately attributed, with the consequence that each Course is jointly owned by its respective contributing Parties within the meaning of Article 16.4 of the GA and Annex 5 thereof.

(D) The Courses are authored and stored in OpenAIRE’s Articulate Rise 360 account and deployed on the OpenPlato platform operated by OpenAIRE. OpenAIRE’s role as account holder and platform operator does not affect the joint ownership of the Courses by all contributing Parties; it gives rise to specific operational obligations set out in Clause 4 of this Agreement.

(E) The Parties wish to record their joint ownership and licensing arrangements in this Agreement, which constitutes the written joint ownership agreement required by Article 16.4 of the GA and Annex 5 thereof.

The Parties agree as follows:

1. Joint ownership.

1.1 Each Course is jointly owned by the Parties that contributed to it, as identified in the Annex, in equal undivided shares as between those Parties. This Agreement constitutes the written joint ownership agreement required by Article 16.4 of the GA and Annex 5 thereof in respect of all Courses listed in the Annex.

1.2 For the avoidance of doubt, OpenAIRE is a joint owner of each Course by virtue of its instructional design and technical production contribution. Content-contributing partners are joint owners of the Courses to which they contributed content, as specified in the Annex.

2. Open licensing.

2.1 The Parties agree to release each Course to the public under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Public License (CC BY 4.0), available at <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>.

2.2 The Parties expressly waive, between themselves, the default joint ownership regime of Annex 5 of the GA, including the 45-day prior-notice requirement and the entitlement to fair and reasonable compensation, insofar as such regime would apply to the CC BY 4.0 release or to any other non-exclusive licence consistent with CC BY 4.0.

3. Attribution.

3.1 All Parties shall be credited in any public use of a Course, in the following form (or a reasonable equivalent depending on the medium):

"This course is published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) licence. You are free to share (copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format) and adapt (remix, transform, and build upon the material) for any purpose, including commercially, provided that appropriate credit is given and any changes are indicated. If you adapt or build upon this material, you must indicate the changes made and may not suggest that the PATTERN Consortium endorses your version. Full licence terms: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>."

This course was developed by the PATTERN project funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101094416. The content reflects only the views of the PATTERN Consortium; the European Union and the granting authority bear no responsibility for any use that may be made of the information contained herein."

3.2 The funding statement "Funded by the European Union" and the EU emblem shall accompany the attribution wherever feasible, in accordance with Article 17.2 of the GA. The disclaimer under Article 17.3 of the GA shall be included where appropriate. The names, logos and trademarks of the Parties and of the PATTERN project are not licensed under CC BY 4.0 and remain subject to their respective owners' control.

4. Articulate Rise 360 account and OpenPlato hosting.

4.1 **Account custody.** The Courses are authored and stored in OpenAIRE's Articulate Rise 360 cloud account. OpenAIRE shall maintain the Rise 360 account active and accessible for the duration of the PATTERN project and for a period of **at least [3] years** following its end, or for such longer period as the Parties may agree in writing.

4.2 Export on request. OpenAIRE shall, within [15] calendar days of a written request by any other Party, provide to that Party: (i) a full SCORM/xAPI export package of the requested Course(s) in a format suitable for deployment on a standard LMS; and (ii) a PDF or equivalent static export of the Course content. These exports constitute the requesting Party's operational copy for the purposes of exercising its rights under this Agreement.

4.3 Continuity of access on OpenPlato. OpenAIRE shall ensure that the published Courses remain publicly accessible on the OpenPlato platform for a period of at least [3] years following the end of the PATTERN project, unless the Parties unanimously agree otherwise in writing. Where OpenAIRE anticipates that it may be unable to maintain such access, it shall notify the other Parties at least [6] months in advance to allow for alternative hosting arrangements.

4.4 No unilateral withdrawal or modification. OpenAIRE shall not withdraw, unpublish, or materially alter the content of any Course on OpenPlato without the prior written consent of the content-contributing Parties for that Course, except where required by applicable law or by a binding decision of a competent authority.

4.5 Adaptation rights of other Parties. Each other Party's right to create and disseminate derivative works under Clause 5 shall be exercisable on the basis of the SCORM/xAPI export package provided under this Clause. The fact that the Rise 360 native authoring environment is held by OpenAIRE does not restrict any Party's legal right to adapt the Course content, but the Parties acknowledge that native re-editing in Rise 360 requires OpenAIRE's operational cooperation, which OpenAIRE shall not unreasonably withhold for updates agreed by the relevant Parties under Clause 6.

5. Third-party material.

The CC BY 4.0 release applies only to the original contributions of the Parties to each Course. It does not extend to third-party material embedded in a Course (including without limitation graphical assets, fonts, icons, quoted text, datasets, and any Articulate Rise 360 built-in assets subject to Articulate's own licence terms), which remains subject to its own respective licence. Each Party warrants that the material it contributed is either original and free of third-party rights preventing CC BY 4.0 release, or duly cleared for such release.

6. Derivative works and parallel licensing.

Each Party may, independently, create and disseminate derivative works of any Course to which it is a joint owner (including translations, institutional adaptations, and integration into other training programmes) and may license its own use of a Course under terms other than CC BY 4.0 (including for commercial or restricted-access purposes), provided that: (i) the original Course remains publicly accessible on OpenPlato under CC BY 4.0 and attributed in accordance with Clause 3; and (ii) a Party intending to distribute derivative works for commercial purposes notifies all other joint owners of that Course in writing at least [15] calendar days prior to such distribution. Such notification is informational only and does not require the consent of the other joint owners. Each Party retains any revenue it generates from such parallel use.

7. Updates.

7.1 Subsequent versions of any Course released within the PATTERN project shall be released under CC BY 4.0 on the same terms as this Agreement, unless the Parties concerned otherwise agree in writing.

7.2 Any update that materially alters the scope, structure, content or attributions of a Course requires the prior written agreement of all joint owners of that Course.

7.3 OpenAIRE shall act as coordinating owner for the purpose of implementing agreed updates in Rise 360 and publishing them on OpenPlato. Following publication of an update, OpenAIRE shall notify all joint owners and, upon request, provide an updated SCORM/xAPI export package within [15] calendar days.

8. Scope and relationship to the side letter on static materials.

This Agreement governs joint ownership of the Courses only. It does not cover the static training materials (slide decks, documents, guidelines and related outputs) developed under Work Package 2, which are governed by separate Joint Ownership Side Letter or equivalent written agreement. In the event of overlap or conflict between this Agreement and that side letter, the Parties shall resolve the issue by reference to the GA, which prevails over both instruments.

9. Relationship to the GA and Consortium Agreement.

This Agreement is concluded in implementation of Article 16.4 of the GA and Annex 5 thereof, and is subject to the GA and to the PATTERN Consortium Agreement. In the event of conflict, the GA prevails, followed by this Agreement (for matters concerning joint ownership and licensing of the Courses), then the Consortium Agreement.

10. Governing law and disputes.

This Agreement is governed by EU law, supplemented if necessary by the law of Belgium, in accordance with Article 43 of the GA. The Parties shall first attempt to resolve any dispute amicably; failing which, the dispute resolution mechanism of the PATTERN Consortium Agreement applies.

11. Duration and form.

This Agreement enters into force on the date of last signature and remains in force for the duration of the copyright in the Courses. The irrevocable nature of CC BY 4.0 survives termination. The Agreement may be signed in counterparts and by qualified electronic signature under Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 (eIDAS), each of which constitutes an original.

Signatures

For XXX

Name: _____

Position: _____

Date: _____ Place: _____

Signature: _____

For XXX

Name: _____

Position: _____

Date: _____ Place: _____
Signature: _____

For XXX

Name: _____
Position: _____
Date: _____ Place: _____
Signature: _____

[Add signature blocks for all other content-contributing partners as applicable]

ANNEX — List of Courses and Contributing Parties

The following Courses were jointly developed under Work Package 2 (Task 2.1) of the PATTERN project. OpenAIRE is a joint owner of all Courses by virtue of its instructional design and technical production contribution. Content partners are identified per Course. All placeholders must be completed before the Parties execute this Agreement.

Course No.	Title	Content Partners	OpenPlato URL	Version / Date
EC1	[Course title]	[Content partners e.g. APRE]	[OpenPlato URL]	[vX, DATE]
EC2	[Course title]	[Content partners]	[OpenPlato URL]	[vX, DATE]
EC3	[Course title]	[Content partners]	[OpenPlato URL]	[vX, DATE]
EC4	[Course title]	[Content partners]	[OpenPlato URL]	[vX, DATE]
EC5	[Course title]	[Content partners]	[OpenPlato URL]	[vX, DATE]
EC6	[Course title]	[Content partners]	[OpenPlato URL]	[vX, DATE]
EC7	[Course title]	[Content partners]	[OpenPlato URL]	[vX, DATE]
EC8	[Course title]	[Content partners]	[OpenPlato URL]	[vX, DATE]

Note: "Content Partners" identifies the Parties that contributed substantive educational content to each Course. OpenAIRE's instructional design and technical production contribution applies to all Courses and is not repeated in this column.

7.4 Annex 4 Horizon Results Booster report (PATTERN, REINFORCING, ECS)

BOOSTER

Go to Market (G2M) Service

Final Report

for

**Responsible tErritories and Institutions eNable and Foster Open
Research and inClusive Innovation for traNsitions Governance –**

REINFORCING

European Citizen Science – ECS

**Piloting open and responsible Activities and Trainings Towards the
Enhancement of Researchers Networks – PATTERN**

FONDAZIONE GIANNINO BASSETTI ETS

VEREIN DER EUROPÄISCHEN BÜRGERWISSENSCHAFTEN - ECSA E.V.

AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA

Provided by:

Raluca CIBU-BUZAC

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1 List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
ECS	European Citizen Science
ORRI	Open and Responsible Research and Innovation
PATTERN	Piloting open and responsible Activities and Trainings Towards the Enhancement of Researchers Networks
REINFORCING	Responsible tEerritories and Institutions eNable and Foster Open Research and inClusive Innovation for traNsitions Governance

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2 The Service

2.1 Executive Summary of the Service

This report summarises the process followed and the main outcomes of the Go to Market (G2M) service for the beneficiaries **FONDAZIONE GIANNINO BASSETTI ETS, VEREIN DER EUROPAEISCHEN BURGERWISSENSCHAFTEN - ECSA E.V., and AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA** involved in the **REINFORCING & ECS & PATTERN**.

It presents the different Modules and sessions carried out during the service delivery along with the agenda of each meeting and the related participants. It then introduces the terminology used, and the two main tools presented and exercised:

- Exploitation Intentions table
- Value Proposition Canvas

It also includes a template for a Memorandum of Understanding, useful for project partners to progress in agreeing on exploitation rights, building on what was signed as the Consortium Agreement (Annex 1); an overview of the overall methodology and approach used during the delivery (Annex 2); as well as general suggestions on financial and non-financial tools to be used along the go-to-market pathway (Annexes 3 and 4).

The Expert was appointed on April 7, 2025, and the following Modules were included in the G2M service:

- Module A: Kick-off (G2M-A)
- Module B: Unique Value Proposition & Key Exploitable Result(s) (G2M-B)
- Module F: Reporting (G2M-F)

The Beneficiary/ies was/were contacted on April 8, 2025.

On April 28, 2025, an introductory call with the Beneficiary/ies was organised to discuss expectations, get a first insight on the state of the art, present the service and introduce preparatory activities, and agree on a first service delivery plan, based on the Modules activated within the G2M. On the same day, the Expert sent to the Beneficiary/ies all the information and the “Exploitation Intentions” table to be shared with Participants and filled before the delivery of the “Exploitation Pillars Training”.

An additional online meeting was organised on May 22, 2025, with the aim to discuss the structuring and prioritisation of the KERs.

Drafts of the “Exploitation Intentions” tables filled in by Beneficiaries have been returned on September 29, 2025.

The “Exploitation Pillars Training” took place on October 2, 2025, where the basic concepts of exploitation were introduced by the expert, with particular attention to the concepts of KERs, use/adoption of KERs and impact generation. During the session the main discussion was held on the “Exploitation Intentions” table.

During the training, participants and experts aligned on the definitive list of KERs to be supported during the service, which is:

- *ORRI, PATTERN and ECS Platforms* as KER1
- *ORRI Trainings/Guidelines, PATTERN Trainings and ECS Academy* as KER2

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Finally, the expert introduced the main tools to be used during the next session: the Value Proposition Canvas. At the end of the training, the Expert agreed with participants to hold the UVP workshop(s) on dates to be decided upon in due course and asked them to fill in the tools presented during the training in order to provide initial comments/suggestions before the UVP workshop(s).

During Module B, two Unique Value Proposition workshops were organised and delivered according to the timing and agenda described in Section 2.2. Participants reviewed and completed the Value Proposition Canvas enabling them to better focus on target markets, identify early adopters and customers and clearly present the added value of their innovative solutions for the identified early adopters and customers. In the end, they were also able to create an effective statement expressing the Unique Value Proposition of the KERs. Some elements related to intellectual assets founded in the KERs were also discussed. Finally, the expert asked beneficiaries to send back the updated Market Proposition Canvas and Value Proposition Canvas, in order to provide further comments/suggestions.

Anonymous feedback was gathered from participants at the end of the G2M service.

The tools developed during the G2M service were filled in by the beneficiaries with feedback and suggestions from the Expert. The final version is the result of several iterations, brainstorming and discussions during the webinars and coaching sessions. The level of detail of the content presented in the present report reflects the level of maturity of the project when receiving the service.

As from the recommendations in Chapter 5, from the expert perspective, some quick remarks:

1. The three Key Exploitable Results considered for joint exploitation, at the level of the Project Group, and encompassed by KER1, are already available, operational, and used. Nevertheless, in terms of readiness for joint exploitation, the Beneficiaries ought to pursue the steps of a fully-fledged Exploitation Strategy, by defining the vision, goals, roadmap, milestones and measurable targets associated to the potential joint exploitation.
2. Even though the focus of potential collective exploitation resided, at the beginning of the Booster service, on cumulating offerings and promoting them as layers of value, one on top of the other, from the three projects, a more sound and effective approach would consist of narrowing down the focus of the joint exploitation, by picking only a few selected trainings/services. Such an approach would prioritise the offerings where collaboration would sharpen their competitive advantages.
3. At present, based on the results of the Value Proposition canvases, there is a strong indication about the impact to be reached by proceeding to exploit collectively the KERs. Nevertheless, the exploitation intentions are still to be defined by the three consortia, based on a systematic approach.

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2.2 G2M trainings and workshops

2.2.1 G2M - Module A

Exploitation Pillars training held on October 2, 2025

- **Agenda**

Ice breaking (10 min.)

Welcome, Presenting the webinar

Bridging results to the market (20 min.)

The role of D&E, general definitions

Reviewing Key Exploitable Results (50 min.)

Review of Exploitation intentions and final list of KERs

Break (10 min.)

Planning the next steps (30 min.)

Introducing the Value Proposition Canvas

Wrap-up – Q&A (15 min.)

- **Participants**

First name	Last name	Organisation
Marina	Tisner	GRUPO EMPRESARIAL INMARK SA
Carolina	Doran	VEREIN DER EUROPÄISCHEN BÜRGERWISSENSCHAFTEN - ECSA E.V.
Pietro	Rigonat	LOBA

- **Post workshop support**

Support in fine-tuning available information and provision of final comments, pre and after the workshops

The exploitation intentions table prepared and discussed during the workshop showed clear improvements in the definition of the final list of KERs to be supported:

- Further clarifying the target adopters/end users for each KER, and where do they «meet» in terms of common problems/needs.
- Pre-identifying common adopters' groups, e.g., researchers, research project managers, research support professionals, as well as other potential common groups of end users, e.g., civil society/NGO, businesses, research funding agencies.
- Providing additional insights about how the services of the platforms complement each other.
- Reflecting on which partners will lead the exploitation of the *joint KERs*.
- Describing how third parties will be engaged in training delivery, and where the specific framework/principles/guidelines will be featured.

Some elements related to the selected KERs need particular focus during the implementation of the next G2M Modules:

- Refining the overview of alternative solutions used at present by target adopters/end users, the portfolio of services to be deployed by the *joint KERs*, as well as what you aim to achieve in collaboration (i.e., that you cannot achieve as individual KERs);
- Expanding the description of the transformations that could be triggered through the joint exploitation of the KERs;
- Identifying the competitive advantage/ Unique Value Proposition (UVP), per each *joint KER*.

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2.2.2 G2M – Module B

UVP workshop for KER1 held on January 27, 2026

- **Agenda**

Introducing the day (10 min.)

Welcome, Presenting the webinar, insights on draft Value Proposition Canvas

Working together: The Value Proposition Canvas (60 min.)

Deepening the Value Proposition Canvas, defining the right UVP

Break (10 min.)

Presenting the UVP (15 min.)

Showcasing/updating the KER for the HRP

Wrap-up – Q&A (10 min.)

- **Participants**

First name	Last name	Organisation
Marina	Tisner	GRUPO EMPRESARIAL INMARK SA
Dorte	Riemenschneider	VEREIN DER EUROPÄISCHEN BÜRGERWISSENSCHAFTEN - ECSA E.V.
Pietro	Rigonat	LOBA
Beatriz	Noriega Ortega	VEREIN DER EUROPÄISCHEN BÜRGERWISSENSCHAFTEN - ECSA E.V.

- **Post workshop support**

Support in fine-tuning available information and provision of final comments, pre and after the workshops

The tools prepared and discussed during the workshop showed clear improvements by beneficiaries:

- Finetuning the selected end user group to be analysed through the Value Proposition canvas.
- Updating the list of pain relievers to be provided by the KER.
- Strengthening the definition of the centralised hub approach in view of joint exploitation of the overarching KER.

However, some elements still need further consideration in the next Modules or as actions envisaged:

- Structuring the portfolio of joint offerings;
- Prioritising the types of adopters relevant for the umbrella KER;
- Identification of exploitation actions and relevant partners' roles.

UVP workshop for KER2 held on January 28, 2026

- **Agenda**

Introducing the day (10 min.)

Welcome, Presenting the webinar, insights on draft Value Proposition Canvas

Working together: The Value Proposition Canvas (60 min.)

Deepening the Value Proposition Canvas, defining the right UVP

Break (10 min.)

A quick look at IPR (15 min.)

Wrap-up – Q&A (10 min.)

- **Participants**

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First name	Last name	Organisation
Marina	Tisner	GRUPO EMPRESARIAL INMARK SA
Magdalena	Schieferdecker	VEREIN DER EUROPÄISCHEN BÜRGERWISSENSCHAFTEN - ECSA E.V.
Pietro	Rigonat	LOBA
Beatriz	Noriega Ortega	VEREIN DER EUROPÄISCHEN BÜRGERWISSENSCHAFTEN - ECSA E.V.

- **Post workshop support**

Support in fine-tuning available information and provision of final comments, pre and after the workshops

The tools prepared and discussed during the workshop showed clear improvements by beneficiaries:

- Revisiting of the list of customer jobs, to even better reflect their main tasks and aims.
- Refining the lists of customer pains and gains, to include even more specific insights into the Value Proposition canvas;
- Sharpening the definition of the pain relievers that the KER will facilitate.

However, some elements still need further consideration in the next Modules or as actions envisaged:

- Defining the optimal approaches to showcase the training offerings;
- Prioritising the types of adopters relevant for the umbrella KER;
- Identification of exploitation actions and relevant partners' roles.

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3 MODULE A: Kick off (G2M-A)

3.1 Final list of KERs

KER1: ORRI, PATTERN and ECS Platforms

KER2: ORRI Trainings/Guidelines, PATTERN Trainings and ECS Academy

3.2 KER1: ORRI, PATTERN AND ECS PLATFORMS - Exploitation Intentions Table

KER name: ORRI, PATTERN AND ECS Platforms	Input from the Beneficiary
Description	ORRI Platform; PATTERN Platform; ECS Platform
Target market/ end users	<p>The target market includes a diverse range of organizations involved in research, innovation, and the implementation of ORRI practices. The market can be segmented as follows:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Researchers at all stages of their career: Individuals engaged in scientific inquiry, from early-career to senior researchers, interested in advancing open, responsible, and participatory research practices. 2. Research project managers: Professionals coordinating research activities, ensuring ethical standards, collaboration, and stakeholder engagement within open and citizen science initiatives. 3. Research support professionals: Experts providing administrative, technical, or strategic support to research teams, helping integrate open science, data management, and responsible innovation frameworks. 4. Research Funding Organizations and Publishers: These entities are key target groups, as they play a critical role in supporting and disseminating ORRI practices. Engaging them can drive wider adoption and visibility of ORRI standards. 5. Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs): This segment includes professional associations in the field of research and innovation, associations of universities and research-performing organizations (e.g., European University Association - EUA, European Association of Research and Technology Organizations - EARTO), and consumer protection associations. These groups are instrumental in advocating for best practices and standards within the research community. 6. Civil Society Organizations (CSOs): The platform will target environmental organizations, patient organizations, and other CSOs that have a stake in promoting transparency, inclusivity, and responsibility in research and innovation. 7. Business and Industry: This category includes business and industry associations, as well as standard-setting bodies that influence the adoption of ORRI practices across sectors. Engaging these groups will help to promote ORRI principles within the private sector. <p>Common end user groups: Then, research project managers. Then, overall scientific community. Then, research support professionals.</p>

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Competitive advantages	<p>The Unique Value Proposition (UVP) of the platforms lies in its ability to create a comprehensive, centralized hub for the target groups, uniquely combining visibility, practical guidance and tailored support in one place. The competitive advantages are listed as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build a dedicated research-oriented community: By bringing together individuals and organizations interested in mentoring or facilitating open RRI practices, the platforms foster a collaborative environment that drives innovation and knowledge-sharing. • The three platforms solve the problem of the lack of knowledge on how to practically implement open RRI practices in daily activities of professionals and organisations including tailored guidance and resources • The three platforms solve the problem of the lack of knowledge on how to comply with traditional call for proposals' requirements (e.g., ethics, data management, dissemination, etc.) • Easy user-friendly access to relevant resources and materials related to Open RRI • Increase the visibility of research projects • Easy and user-friendly access to resources and materials dealing with proper data treatment • The three platforms offer resources and materials with added value for all science domains (open RRI as a cross-cutting added value for the target groups) • The three platforms solve the problem of lack of trust among target groups on how data is collected and treated • The three platforms may attract stakeholders outside the EU • Long-term accessibility by users after the end of the three projects • Modular and multilingual content • Community-driven platforms
Use model	<p>Open access and open-source model with regular co-design and co-creation activities, maintained after the end of the three projects, freely accessible with voluntary contributions and integrations.</p> <p>The early adopters for the three platforms are the target groups, with higher engagement from researchers at different stages of their careers and citizen science practitioners.</p>
Partners	<p>OpenAIRE, LPI TECNALIA, Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT), Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus (VTT), Fraunhofer, TECNALIA, Stickydot and FGB. ECSA</p>
Timing	The platforms are already available
IP status	Open access

EXPERT COMMENTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- *The collaborative KER is comprehensively described, with extensive references to expected outcomes and sharp outline of the target market.*
- *There is a strong internal logic for jointly generating and providing value under the scope of this collaborative KER.*
- *Moreover, there is a wide range of adopters/end users envisaged, an aspect that represents an advantage in terms of joint exploitation, while at the same time prioritisation is recommended.*
- *At a first glance, researchers as a main group of end users represent an avenue to follow in view of channelling the exploitation efforts of the collaborative KER. Nevertheless, it is of significance to explore other groups of adopters/end users which are not currently served by alternative solutions, such as businesses. For example, you could consider focusing the first phase of the joint exploitation on this customer segment and monitor the outcomes.*
- *The problem analysis contains in-depth insights, that could be further substantiated with evidence and testimonials from the adopters.*

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- *The reference to regular co-design and co-creation activities within the use model could open other avenues towards joint exploitation, i.e., piloting joint co-creation activities, across the platforms.*

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3.3 KER2: ORRI TRAININGS/GUIDELINES, PATTERN TRAININGS AND ECS ACADEMY - Exploitation Intentions Table

KER name: ORRI Trainings/Guidelines, PATTERN Trainings and ECS Academy	Input from the Beneficiary
Description	ORRI Platform Trainings and ORRI Guidelines; PATTERN training modules; ECS Academy
Target market/ end users	ORRI Guidelines target market and customer segments encompass Researchers, Policy makers, Government, NGO, Civil Society, Business and industry, ORRI practitioners. The ORRI guidelines have been launched one year in the project and expected to be disseminated through trainings and other communication channels throughout the project. The ECS academy targets Citizen science practitioners and citizen scientists PATTERN trainings target Academics, researchers, policymakers, and potentially industry professionals interested in RRI areas.
Competitive advantages	ORRI Guidelines provide a comprehensive and up-to-date guidelines for the achievement of sustainable institutional changes within all areas of ORRI. The guidelines provide support to selected grantees as well as the community at large in the implementation of their ORRI initiatives. The guidelines will include 'good practice' models and principles for institutional changes, provide guidance for the efficient and sustainable implementation of ORRI and consider fast-developing trends, such as Missions and new forms of multi-stakeholder engagement. The ORRI community will be invited to provide feedback on their understandability, user-friendliness and openness to adaptation. The ECS academy delivers mostly free with instructor led courses at a charge. Users can both use and upload their contents which are moderated. Content can be tailored to different needs by the presence of an instructor, which we can find within the Academy network of trainers and educators. PATTERN trainings are built on robust open-source infrastructure (Moodle, Django, Vue.js), long-term hosting by OpenAIRE and LPI, modular and multilingual content, SCORM/xAPI compatibility, EOSC integration, institutional login, and governance via expert editorial boards. Enables co-creation, reuse, and long-term engagement with structured learning paths.
Use model	The ORRI Guidelines early adopters include researchers, ORRI practitioners as well as business and industry stakeholders will be the audience addressed first as they will be the segment with more interest in using them. The ECS Academy enable users can take any of the training and courses available, some of them will be offered at a small cost Freely available, possibly with certification options; licensed under CC-BY or CC-BY-NC.
Partners	AACHEN, AIT, FGB, VTT, Fraunhofer ECSA + ALL ALL PATTERN Consortium
Timing	They are all available since 2024
IP status	PATTERN trainings: CC-BY or CC-BY-NC

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EXPERT COMMENTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- *As shown by the first collaborative KER, commonalities could be built not only in terms of end users, but also in terms of the problems that you solve. For the case of this joint KER, it is important to include an overview of the main problems that you will solve for the adopters/end users.*
- *Furthermore, it is recommendable to include detailed information about the competitive advantages, in close connection with the above identified problems.*
- *In view of strategizing towards joint exploitation, please provide more information about main topics and type of content provided through the trainings.*
- *Given that the offerings are already into place and available for use, please add insights collected from adopters, or reference to previous early adopters' campaigns.*
- *The overall logic for potential joint exploitation ought to be revisited, with the aim of providing clarity about go to market scenarios. As previously mentioned, the approach could be different from the one applied for the joint KER1, for example by selecting the most prominent offering/value and using all results and their resources to make use of the most critical/impactful products/services.*

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4 MODULE B: Unique Value Proposition & Key Exploitable Result(s) (G2M-B)

4.1 KER 1: ORRI, PATTERN AND ECS PLATFORMS

4.1.1 Value Proposition Canvas

The Value Proposition Canvas **KER 1: ORRI, PATTERN and ECS Platform**
Researchers

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The Value Proposition Canvas KER 1: ORRI, PATTERN and ECS Platform Officers in public research funding agencies

EXPERT COMMENTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- It is excellent that you applied the Value Proposition canvas to two groups of end users that are in different positions within the value chain, as one is applying for appropriate programmes and then implementing the projects, while the other is evaluating submitted applications and then managed projects. These combined perspectives provide a clear indication for the KER's competitive advantages.
- The granularity of the customer profiles is high, thus leading to a comprehensive overview of the jobs/pains/gains and, consequently, and to defining the KER's value map with great precision.
- Moreover, you collected advanced observations about your adopters/end users, and they are reflected very well in the customer profile.
- Given the complexity of the joint KER's offerings, it is recommendable to provide a map of the services/solutions encompassed collectively by the platforms, thus facilitating the orientation by the adopters/end users.
- As part of the next steps towards joint exploitation, please consider the formalisation of the portfolio of services and afterwards its promotion.

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4.1.2 Related projects

ROSiE: Responsible Open Science in Europe

Open science is a policy priority. Creativity and trust in science increases when researchers share knowledge and data as early as possible. However, open science also raises questions about research ethics, integrity and misconduct. Responsible research promotes public engagement, ethics and good governance. In this context, the EU-funded ROSiE project will develop tools to ensure ethics and research integrity in open science and citizen science. As a multidisciplinary project, it will bring together leading experts and organisations in the field to explore, engage, guide and equip. Specifically, it will identify the ethical, social and legal challenges of open science. It will also create a community of practice and develop operational guidelines to support stakeholders in understanding responsible innovation.

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006430>

RESBIOS: RESponsible research and innovation grounding practices in BIOSciences

Responsible research and innovation (RRI) implies that researchers, citizens, policymakers, businesses, third-sector organisations and other societal actors work together during the whole research and innovation process. The aim is to better align both the process and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society. The EU-funded RESBIOS project will embed RRI practices in the field of biosciences – a sector at the crossroads between science and society – in four European countries. To achieve sustainable institutional changes in the various organisations, the project will implement RRI-oriented grounding actions (GAs). These aim to involve stakeholders in co-designing experiments, connect societal actors in the territory and inside research organisations and develop permanent spaces of integration with society.

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/872146>

HEIRRI: Higher Education Institutions and Responsible Research and Innovation

Higher Education Institutions and Responsible Research and Innovation (HEIRRI) foster an alignment of research and innovation (R&I) with the needs, values and societal expectations. The six key aspects of “Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)”-societal/public engagement, gender equality, open access, science education, ethics and governance in R&I-are transdisciplinary included at all stages of formation of scientist and engineers, and other professional fields involved in R&I.

HEIRRI will create and share on OA a stock-taking inventory constituted by a State of the Art Review and a Data Base. The inventory will gather results of other EU funded RRI projects, good cases and practices of RRI and RRI Learning. Also, different stakeholders involved and/or affected by R&I will participate in a debate and reflection process on RRI Learning through online and offline Forum actions.

Results from the inventory will represent the basis for RRI Training programs and formative materials, offering the students knowledge and skills to develop viable solutions to specific problems related to R&I, integrating theory and practice. They will be designed for the different HEI educational levels (undergraduate, MD and PhD, summer courses and MOOC), mainly based on Problem based learning methodology, and supported by multimedia materials (videos and microvideos, 2.0 materials, etc.). All results and products elaborated by HEIRRI will be uploaded on OA at RRItools Platform.

An internationalization plan will guarantee their spreading awareness and future use by HEI from Europe and beyond. A global scope and expertise on RRI will be provided by HEIRRI consortium that consists of 5 European HEI (Universitat Pompeu Fabra (UPF), Universitetet i Bergen (UiB), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Institut Fuer Hoehere Studien und Wissenschaftliche Forschung (IHS), Sveuciliste u Splitu (University of Split, UNIST)), the European network of science centres and museums (AEESTI / Ecsite), Fundació Bancaria Caixa D'estalvis i Pensions de Barcelona La Caixa (FBLC), a network of universities (Associació Catalana d'Universitats Públiques, ACUP), and a private company specialized in R&I (INNOVATEC).

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<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/666004>

4.1.3 Related patents

N.A.

4.1.4 Related standards

N.A.

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4.2 KER 2: ORRI TRAININGS/GUIDELINES, PATTERN TRAININGS AND ECS ACADEMY

4.2.1 Value Proposition Canvas

The Value Proposition Canvas KER 2: ORRI Trainings/Guidelines, PATTERN Trainings and ECS Academy
Researchers

The Value Proposition Canvas KER 2: ORRI Trainings/Guidelines, PATTERN Trainings and ECS Academy
Professionals in CSOs

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EXPERT COMMENTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- *It is very relevant that you refer to potential implications of the joint KER towards not only competence building through training, but also organisational transformation, as gaining new knowledge would imply also shifting ways to operate.*
- *Concerning the exploitation strategy itself, judging by the results of the Value Proposition canvases, there is a strong indication about the impact to be reached by proceeding to exploit collectively the KERs.*
- *It is of particular interest the focus on professionals within civil society organisations (CSO), and the diagnostic about untapped needs and unsolved problems/expectations, thus creating the premise to provide support to adopters/end users that do not have available alternative solutions at present.*
- *A catalogue of training would be highly recommendable. Furthermore, please reflect if it could bring additional value to bridge the educational material with implementation support, thus paving the way for the transformative potential at individual and institutional level*

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4.2.2 Related projects

FIT4RRI: Fostering Improved Training Tools For Responsible Research and Innovation

FIT4RRI moves from the assumption that there is a serious gap between the potential role Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and Open Science (OS) could play in helping Research Funding and Performing Organisations (RFPOs) to manage the rapid transformation processes affecting science (especially the science-in-society aspects) and the actual impact RRI and OS are currently having on RFPOs, research sectors and national research systems. FIT4RRI is precisely intended to contribute in bridging this gap, promoting viable strategies to activate institutional changes in RFPOs. The project, in particular, will act on two key factors i.e. i) Enhancing competences and skills related to RRI and OS through an improvement of the RRI and OS training offer (in terms of training tools, actions and strategies) presently available; ii) Institutionally embedding RRI/OS practices and approaches by promoting the diffusion of more advanced governance settings able to create an enabling environment for RRI and OS. With this double aim in view, FIT4RRI is organised following an overall methodology based on three main steps: an analytical strand devoted to understand what is happening in the RRI and OS practice, taking into account general trends, barriers and drivers to RRI and OS, interests and values, advanced experiences; a testing strand (observing RRI/OS in action through 4 co-creation experiments) aimed at figuring out possible solutions in terms of training approaches and governance settings; and a proactive strand, promoting changes (i.e. developing training tools and actions and easy-accessible evidence-based guidelines on governance settings functioning as enablers for RRI and OS). The project will last 36 months and includes 7 WPs: Mapping and benchmarking; Sectoral diagnosis, Co-creation experiments, Training tools and actions, Governance Setting, Communication, dissemination and exploitation of results, Management. This project involves 13 partners from 9 EC.

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/741477>

SCALINGS: Scaling up Co-creation: Avenues and Limits for Integrating Society in Science and Innovation

In the dynamic landscape of collaborative initiatives, it is more important than ever to understand the intricacies of co-creation processes and outcomes under diverse cultural, societal, and regulatory backgrounds. It is necessary to delve deep into the realms of robotics and urban energy domains. This is the aim of the EU-funded SCALINGS project. By investigating the implementation, uptake, and outcomes of co-creation instruments in robotics and urban energy domains across 10 countries, SCALINGS seeks to identify scalable and transferable practices. Armed with unique data, transformative frameworks, and a comprehensive EU Policy Roadmap, SCALINGS paves the way for widespread co-creation dissemination, fostering innovation and cross-cultural collaboration. The project will collaborate with over two dozen European co-creation initiatives.

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/788359>

Impetus: Impetus

IMPETUS will support and give recognition to citizen science (CS) in Europe. It aims to:

- * enable more diverse citizen science initiatives (CSIs) to access funding;
- * bring CS closer to society and policy makers;
- * acknowledge CS? role in tackling the greatest challenges of our times; and
- * enable CSIs to contribute to Green Deal (GD) and UN SDG commitments.

We will achieve this by:

- * funding CSIs through 3 open calls, selected on expected impacts, volunteer engagement, EDI, openness and quality data. We will offer 20k? to kick-start 100 CSIs and 10k? to sustain 25 CSIs addressing pressing needs of the European society. Each call will have 2 challenges; we will convene a citizen panel to define one and provide feedback on our work.
- * setting up an accelerator to provide the funded CSIs with an integrated programme of support, training, mentoring, and resources. The accelerator will facilitate peer learning, enable CSIs to contribute to SDG and GD targets and forge connections with quadruple helix stakeholders.

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* launching the EU Prize for Citizen Science, awarded to CSIs for outstanding achievements, allowing them to continue and expand their work and showcase it to a wider audience. We will award 3 prize categories for 3 years: outstanding achievements, diversity and innovative grassroots projects. Each time, we will reach out to advisors to identify exceptional nominations and to the citizen panel to vote in the grassroots category.

* shaping EU policy in and with CS, through horizon scanning, anticipatory policy and action research, informing policy briefs, webinars and workshops with key policy stakeholders. The aim is to foster more CS data to inform evidence-based policies and identify future directions in CS policy.

* developing impact assessment tools and assessing the impact of CSIs and our own framework, especially on GD and SDG targets. Insights will be presented within the wider CS ecosystem and feed into recommendations for national and EU policies.

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058677>

4.2.3 Related patents

N.A.

4.2.4 Related standards

N.A.

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5 Final recommendations by the Expert

KER1: ORRI, PATTERN and ECS Platforms	
Issues	Assessment and Recommendations
Maturity of the KER	The three Key Exploitable Results considered for joint exploitation, at the level of the Project Group, and encompassed by KER1, are already available, operational, and used. Nevertheless, in terms of readiness for joint exploitation, the Beneficiaries ought to pursue the steps of a fully-fledged Exploitation Strategy, by defining the vision, goals, roadmap, milestones and measurable targets associated to the potential joint exploitation.
Market definition	Given that the joint KER targets a wide range of adopters/end users, it is recommended to prioritise the actions aimed at engaging them, after preliminarily defining their specific customer profiles. Businesses represent a segment of the target market which needs further analysis and testing/validation, nevertheless managing the engagement of managers/founders would expand the scope and impact of the exploitation endeavours. As soon as data/testimonials could be collected from adopters, then more concrete insights would be gained in terms of how to optimally proceed about the exploitation strategy.
Unique Value Proposition definition	Given the complexity of the joint KER's offerings, it is recommendable to provide a map of the services/solutions encompassed collectively by the platforms, thus facilitating the orientation by the adopters/end users. Moreover, as part of the next steps towards joint exploitation, please consider the formalisation of the portfolio of services and afterwards its promotion.
Recommended next steps	At present, based on the results of the Value Proposition canvases, there is a strong indication about the impact to be reached by proceeding to exploit collectively the KERs. Nevertheless, the exploitation intentions are still to be defined by the three consortia, based on a systematic approach.

KER1: ORRI Trainings/Guidelines, PATTERN Trainings and ECS Academy	
Issues	Assessment and Recommendations
Maturity of the KER	The three Key Exploitable Results considered for joint exploitation, at the level of the Project Group, and encompassed by KER1, are already available, operational, and used. Nevertheless, in terms of readiness for joint exploitation, the Beneficiaries ought to pursue the steps of a fully-fledged Exploitation Strategy, by defining the vision, goals, roadmap, milestones and measurable targets associated to the potential joint exploitation.
Market definition	At the level of the second identified joint KER, it is advisable to still proceed to an overview of the main problems that you will solve for the adopters/end users. Furthermore, it is recommendable to include detailed information about the competitive advantages, in close connection with the above identified problems, and based on the outcomes stated in the Value Proposition canvases. Given that the offerings are already into place and available for use, it is important to add insights collected from adopters, or references to previous early adopters' campaigns.
Unique Value Proposition definition	As identified during the Unique Value Proposition workshops, the estimated impact of the joint KER consists also in institutional building/organisational transformation, as gaining new knowledge would imply shifting processes, organisational charts and

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	procedures. A catalogue of training would be highly recommendable to be featured as part of the joint KER's description and positioning on the market.
Recommended next steps	Even though the focus of potential collective exploitation resided, at the beginning of the Booster service, on cumulating offerings and promoting them as layers of value, one on top of the other, from the three projects, a more sound and effective approach would consist of narrowing down the focus of the joint exploitation, by picking only a few selected trainings/services. Such an approach would prioritise the offerings where collaboration would sharpen their competitive advantages.

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6 Annex 1 - Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)

1. Valorisation and exploitation of ... (please refer to the specific KER)

1.1 Agreement between partner, partner, partner

1.2 The following Memorandum of Understanding is made on the dd/mm/yyyy by and between

- Partner a, VAT ..., registered in ..., hereinafter referred to as ...
- Partner b, VAT ..., registered in ..., hereinafter referred to as ...
- Partner c, VAT ..., registered in ..., hereinafter referred to as ...
-

Individually referred to as a "Party" or collectively as the "Parties".

1.3 Background of the Agreement

During the [name of the project] project's life the KER was developed... *(clearly describe the KER)*

As per consortium agreement of the Project signed by the Parties, [number of Section]: Results, ... Results are owned by the Party that generates them.

Partner a, b, c, x, y and z contributed to the generation of the KER. Each one contributed in the following way:

- Partner a, ...
- Partner b, ...
- Partner c, ...
- Partners x, ...
- Partner y, ...
- Partner z, ...

Upon successful conclusion of the project activities, Parties agreed to jointly define the best way to exploit and valorise the KER.

Partners a, b, c, ... expressed the willingness to further valorise and exploit the above-mentioned KER, securing the needed resources, while partners x, y, and z agreed to give to partners a, b, c, ... the full right to exploit declaring to have nothing to claim.

Given the uniqueness and further impact potential of KER/s above mentioned, all Parties through this agreement aim to define clear roles and modalities to exploit the programme beyond the grant received from the European Commission.

1.4 Purpose of the Agreement

The agreement is therefore aimed at clarifying and regulating

- A. Scope and objectives of KER
- B. Use of the brand *(example)*
- C. Use of the data collected via the platform *(example)*
- D. Use of the DB (software) *(example)*
- E. Procedures and Roles of the Parties *(example)*

2. Scope and objectives of KER

The Parties agree that KER is ... *(KER description)*

The KER is built around... and it is implemented through:

- A. A network(s)-based outreach approach; *(example)*
- B. ...;

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- C. ...;
- D.

3. Use of the brand

....

- ...

4. Use of the data collected

...The registered data are the property of each of the Parties, who can use them for other activities in respect of GDPR and only for non-competing purposes with the current agreement (to be finetuned by partners legal offices).

5. Use of the

5.1 Procedures and Roles of the Parties

All Parties shall appoint 1 person within their respective organisation as the first and foremost contact point for ensuring swift and clear communication between the Parties and for implementation of the exploitation plan for this KER as approved by [name of the project] and annexed to this MoU.

The initial persons responsible for being the contact point are:

- Partner a: Name, email address, telephone number
- Partner b: Name, email address, telephone number
- Partner c: Name, email address, telephone number
- Partner

All partners will be informed of changes in the contact points in a timely fashion, not exceeding 5 working days from the moment the appointment from the organisation.

Partners a, b, c, ... who expressed the willingness to further valorise and exploit the KER will proactively look for potential business development opportunities. Each time one of the Parties is clearly informed by a potential customer, the Party must inform the other Parties' relevant contact points and receive organisational approval (X out of X) to proceed.

It is the responsibility of each Party to ensure the contact points of the other Parties are informed using, if necessary, more than one communication channel (e.g., email, WhatsApp, phone, etc). It is the responsibility of the other Parties to ensure the approval to proceed (or denial thereof) is communicated back to the Party in a timely fashion, not exceeding 1 working week (5 working days) from the moment the latter's communication has reached them.

5.2 Dedicated KER management (in the case of a horizontal governance set-up – to be finetuned according to the governance set up chosen by the concerned partners, before the end of the project))

The Party in charge of any new contract will inform all partners about the client, the scope of the contract and foreseen role for each partner (if possible and to different degrees). In order to progress with a new programme, partners must agree on its relevance and viability. Parties have 5 working days to register non-agreement, otherwise the proposal will be considered suitable.

When the contract is finalised, agreed by all Parties and service sold to the client, the Party in charge will act as main contract manager and coordinator, responsible and liable for the smooth implementation of the envisaged activities throughout all phases.

The partner who secures the contract should also perform a "client financial check" and all Parties will be paid promptly upon payment from the client according to the payment schedules agreed upon.

The Party will be the interface between the client and the Parties and will also be responsible for proposing the allocation of resources among partners.

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5.3 Promotion and marketing

Parties **a, b, c, ...** who expressed the willingness to further valorise and exploit the KER will ensure the proper outreach, using their networks and contacts (social media, newsletters, websites) to promote the KER toward the target markets and early adopters initially identified in the exploitation plan annexed to this MoU.

The most suitable party to deliver the communication activities will be decided on the basis of the scope of the contract and the main target audience.

Cost of marketing and sales activities will be split among partners according to the provisions of the exploitation plan for the current KER.

5.4 To summarise:

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Party responsible</i>	<i>Cost split between parties (%)</i>
<i>Programme management and coordination</i>	<i>Party who secured a contract</i>	
<i>KER and methodology management</i>	...	
<i>Innovation and IPR management</i>		
<i>KER update</i>		
<i>Outreach and communication</i>	...	
...	...	

6. Intellectual Property Rights and NDA

The Parties acknowledge that nothing in this Agreement shall affect any pre-existing (background) and future (foreground) ownership of any intellectual property rights.

Dedicated NDA will be developed and signed between Parties and customers every time needed.

7. Miscellaneous

In the event of further participation in call for proposals covering actions that fall in the scope of this Agreement, the parties mutually recognize a first right of information and best effort to bid together

This Agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent of all the Parties. This Agreement shall become effective upon signature by the authorised officials and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the Party by mutual consent. In the absence of mutual agreement by the Parties this Agreement shall remain in force for twenty-four months.

Any dispute that might arise concerning this Agreement shall be settled amicably.

8. Date & Signatures

FOR [please insert name of participant or potential or current partner]

Partner a: Name, Position

Partner b: Name, Position

Partner c: Name, Position

Partner x: Name, Position

Partner y: Name, Position

Partner z: Name, Position

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7 Annex 2 - The Lean Startup Methodology

To contribute to the sustainability plan and to dissemination activities, it is important to further focus on the problems the novel solution is addressing, who are the ones who feel this problem the most (the users of the solution, the target group of dissemination activities, your “customers”), the unique value proposition (what makes the novel solution much better than current ones, the pivot for messages to be used for the messages to be delivered during dissemination) and to identify how to reach customers/users out (use mode and distribution channels). It is also important to identify the costs of providing our target groups with the novel solution how to monitor progresses and how to cover costs incurred (sustainability).

The Lean Canvas is a tool that can help in these crucial activities. The Lean Canvas is an adaptation of Business Model Canvas by Alexander Osterwalder which Ash Maurya¹ created in the Lean Startup spirit (Fast, Concise and Effective startup). It focuses on problems, solutions, key metrics and competitive advantages.

Among the different type of canvas, the lean business model canvas, by Ash Maurya, is the most suited for R&D projects. It is a powerful tool to be used by consortia to further develop the characterization of their KERs, prepare the materials to be discussed at meetings and draft the exploitation/business plan for a KER.

7.1 How to approach the use model

The use model or “business model” is the plan for the creation of impact (successful delivery of a solution), identifying, the intended “customer” base, the result (product/service), sources of revenue and details of financing. It describes the way in which “value” can be extracted from an exploitable R&D result and impact generated.

When working on the “use” model it is important to focus on the following elements:

<p>Your objective</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why am I doing this thing? • Which are my goals? (Best and worst scenario) • Am I really better/different? 	
<p>Global market</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competitors • Incumbents • Investors (geography matters) • Level of investment 	<p>Local market</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competitors • Incumbents • Investors • Peculiarities
<p>6-12-18 months plan</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product roadmap • Cashflow • Valuation target • KPIs • Next step 	

Every “customer” has a problem, every problem has a solution

¹ For more information about this canvas, please refer to the blogpost explaining Lean Canvas and the ideas behind it on his website: <http://www.ashmaurya.com/2012/02/why-lean-canvas/>

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When working on the use model, it is crucial to start from the problem not from the solution. New initiatives (including spin-offs) fail because their offer (a product, a service, a license) is not designed for the intended users, “customers”. Every “customer” has a problem; every problem has a solution. Vice versa, not every solution has a problem, not every problem has a customer. Brainstorm and identify the problem (forget the solution) focus on the problem, identify a common definition.

Early Adopters

To develop the exploitation model, it is important to look at early adopters and how to go from early adopters to “early majority”. Innovators are the ones that “use” the “alfa” version (2,5%, often the industrial partner in an R&D project); early adopters are the customers ready to “use” the “beta” version (13,5%). Next step is to reach the “early majority” (34%). New initiatives fail before reaching out the early majority and this is connected with the capability to reach early adopters.

Identify the “customers”, who will pay, focus on the riskier ones and describe them in the most specific way. Why that customer has that problem is the way to select the assumptions (how they deal with the problem, what are they looking for). Focus on the most important one, the one that, if not validated, will make everything fall down.

UVP

The Unique Value Proposition, or Unique Selling Proposition (USP), is a clear statement describing the benefits of the novel offer, how you solve your customer's needs and what distinguishes you from the competition. It is clearly related to the customers' needs and how their problems are solved so far.

In defining the UVP you do not want a “point of parity” when your features are similar to the ones of the competitors”. What counts are the points of difference, what you do, that the others do not and that matters to the customers. You do not want to be better than your competitors, you want to be better for your customers. Do not imitate/mirror competitors. Keep in mind customers, not competitors.

7.2 The Lean Canvas

For preparing the Exploitation Plan (your business plan) of a R&D result and define the use mode, it is useful to work with the Lean Canvas. The Lean Canvas is an adaptation of Business Model Canvas by Alexander Osterwalder which Ash Maurya² created in the Lean Startup spirit (Fast, Concise and Effective startup). Lean focuses on problems, solutions, key metrics and competitive advantages.

The canvas is a good tool to focus on the exploitation model and start collecting information for the exploitation plan. Among the different type of canvas, the lean business model canvas, by Ash Maurya, is the most suited for R&D projects. It is a powerful tool to be used by the partners to further develop the characterization of their KERs, prepare the materials to be discussed at consortium meetings and draft the exploitation/business plan for a KER.

The lean canvas helps to fine-tune and develop the exploitation strategy for a KER having in mind four questions:

- 1) Who is my “customer”?
- 2) What is “her/his” problem?
- 3) How does “She/he” solve the problem now?
- 4) Is our solution more efficient than the current one?

7.3 How to fill out a Lean Canvas

The end goal of the lean canvas is that an unknowing third-party will be able to review the information provided and understand what the KER and its use is about. They will understand the problem in focus, the customer groups that you

² For more information about this canvas, please refer to the blogpost explaining Lean Canvas and the ideas behind it on his website: <http://www.ashmaurya.com/2012/02/why-lean-canvas/>

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target, the solution you provide, how it differentiates from competitors, how you intend to create value, etc. The lean canvas is very important for an effective implementation of dissemination actions. Due to this, it is very important to avoid the use of highly technical language, abbreviations etc. They can result in third parties not understanding the nature of your KER.

Below a description of the main steps to draft the canvas.

1) PROBLEM - find 3 main problems you are addressing.

Explain: **What** is the problem and **why** is it a problem.

Additionally, attempt to add numbers or quantifiable measures that will clearly highlight the scale of the problem.

Describe EXISTING ALTERNATIVES - Find out how they are solving the problem now (today's alternatives)

2) CUSTOMER SEGMENT - identify who has the problem, define target customers (do not confuse with users).

Be clear on explaining the geographic location of your customers, the industry in which they are operating in, as well as connecting them to the problem in question.

EARLY ADOPTERS - find a small niche that is having the biggest problem, the ones that suffer the most (early adopters).

These will be the first customers of your solution; Be sure to find as much information about these as possible. Explain the geographic location, connect them to the problem, explain exactly why these will be the first adopters, clarify your current connection to them etc.

3) UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION

Define your UVP based on the today's alternative, what makes your product/service more efficient for your customers, a single and compelling sentence that makes everybody understand why you are far better (your features need to be compelling to the customers' needs, otherwise are irrelevant to clients).

Ensure that you clearly define how you differentiate from alternative solutions, and why the customer will come to you; Explain the **uniqueness** of your solution.

Provide facts and data, explaining the performance of your product compared to alternative solutions (efficiency increase of 20%, decreased energy consumption of 10%, 30% fewer development costs etc.).

4) SOLUTION – outline the main features of your solution.

When your features are similar of the ones of the competitors, this is an equality. What matters are the points of difference! What you do, that the others do not do and are what matters to the clients.

Be sure to explain the format of your solution (is it a machine, an equipment, a software, a service, a process, etc.), what it does, and how it does it.

5) CHANNELS – How will you reach your customers?

Be sure to investigate whether the chosen channels are suitable for your choice of customers and consider whether they will be enough to establish the needed reputation on the market.

6) KEY METRICS

key activities you will measure to track the success (e.g. units sold, users registered, retaining users, paying customers, number of complaints ...)

7) UNFAIR ADVANTAGE – what is it that gives you an advantage in front of the competition? Something that can't be easily copied or bought.

This could be IPR, being first movers on new technology that takes years to develop etc. Be sure to explain, *why* the listed points provide you with an advantage. It can be difficult for third parties to understand if they do not have a wide array of knowledge regarding your industry.

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8) COST STRUCTURE

which will be the main costs when the solution is ready for the market (e.g. customer acquisition costs, distribution costs, hosting, people etc). As with revenues, estimate the total costs issued after 6 months and 3 years along with the estimated cost of each “cost-entity”. This will connect your revenues to your costs.

9) REVENUE STREAMS

Which will be the main revenue streams when the solution is ready for the market. Explain how each of them will generate revenue and how much you expect to generate from each stream.

Estimate revenues for seed stage after 6 months and after 3 years. Quantify amounts and prices by detailing, for example, the expected number of services provided and paid, number of licenses sold at which prices etc.

After you finish the exercise, test your hypothesis “out the lab”, with at least 2 to 3 real potential customers. Validate the following assumptions:

- Are the problems you assume really the ones? Is your solution to solving their problem?
- Are the features your solution is offering the ones the market needs and looks for?
- Are the explanations provided in the canvas sufficient to provide the customer with an understanding of your project?

Write down the feedback and update, revise, iterate the Canvas accordingly.

An example of Lean Canvas by Ash Maurya

<p>Problem 1) 1) For 95% of solar cell manufacturers there is the need to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reduce Silver cost of 90% 2. Reduce carbon footprint of 95% 3. Increase efficiency of solar cell of 1%-3% <p>2) For 5% of solar cell manufacturers there is the need to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reduce CapEx and OpEx impact for copper deposition <p>Alternative Solutions Copper deposition using protective mask (no cost reduction respect Silver metallization)</p>	<p>Solutions 4) Top 3 features</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.No resist or mask necessary to plate copper 2. Only one plating equipment is necessary and no other support equipment or added process 3.Low footprint <p>Key Metrics 6) Key activities you measure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100MW Unit sold yearly • Copper consumed per 100MW: monthly • Yield of equipment: monthly 	<p>Unique Value proposition 3) The advanced micro turbines »plug and play« micro generator allows providers of electronic systems to offer off grid real time monitoring and control solutions with the highest reliability over time and across operating conditions, with no need of permission for installing generators unlike solar panels</p>	<p>Unfair Advantage 7) • Patent pending • Breakthrough in electroplating concept</p> <p>Channels 5) Path to customers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exhibition and Fair • Commercial agreement with big companies • Technical Workshop with selected customers 	<p>Customer segment 2) Target customers HJT cells manufactures; currently the only European Community company that produce Heterojunction are EGP and one Hungarian company plus one Russian customer</p> <p>Early Adopters R&D Centers, University, Corporate laboratories to test the new technology and develop new cell structures due to the unique future offered by Rise technology (Europe and Worldwide) Currently the R&D Institute in Europe is around 12 and main countries that will be prioritized are France, Germany and Switzerland.</p>
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Cost structure (when solution is ready for the market) 8)			Revenue Streams (after 6 months and 3 years) 9)		
Cost	6 months	3 years	Two possible revenue models:		
Direct Labor	300k€	4M€	1) Ink-Jet Printer		
Material	300k€	5M€	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multi-year service contracts (5 years) 6 months after seed stage → 1.5M\$ 3 years after → 10M\$/year (5-year contracts) 		
Manufacturing overhead (indirect material)	30k€	500k€	2) Selling Equipment		
Manufacturing overhead (indirect labor)	30k€	100k€	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6 months after seed stage → 1.5M\$ 3 years after → 20M\$ (10 equipment) 		
Manufacturing overhead (other)	150k€	200k€			

7.4 The Market Definition Canvas

According to Ulwick and Ted Thayer all markets can be described by what job the user wants to get done. The Jobs-to-be-Done Market Definition Canvas make the Lean Startup methodology more effective in better finding and defining a market up front. Generally, people buy products and services to get a “job” done, where a job is defined as a task people are trying to accomplish, a goal or objective they are trying to achieve, a problem they are trying to resolve, something they are trying to avoid. According to this assumption, a market is best defined as a group of people and the job they are trying to get done. Such concept assumes more importance when dealing with New and Disruptive Markets.

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7.5 How to fill out the Market Definition Canvas

The Market Definition Canvas works for both B2C and B2B applications. While it is optimized to define single-sided markets, it can be used twice to define both sides of a double-sided market. For component manufacturers who sell to OEMs or who are at the top of a long distribution chain, a canvas can be completed for each constituent in the distribution chain, including the end-user, as each constituent has its own unique job to get done.

The definition of a market as a Job to Be Done, is structured in 8 steps:

- **1. Traditional market definition**

During this phase, research teams have to define what is the product/service/idea they seek to innovate. This is used as the grounding point, as the subsequent steps will help transition from a product view to a jobs-to-be-done view of the market.

- **2. Job executor determination**

The focus on “jobs to be done” begins with this step by asking who's using the product (or who would use the product once released) to get a job done. The goal is to reveal the diverse set of potential product users by producing a list of all the categories of people who use or would use the product to extract its value. The focus here is on the job executors, not on influencers, economic buyers, people who support the product throughout its lifecycle, or other customer types. For example, if we address circular saw market, we can conclude that finish carpenters, framers, roofers, general contractors, electricians, and plumbers use circular saws (all categories of people who use circular saws).

- **3. Abstracted job executor**

Next research teams have to define the one overarching term that can be used to classify or describe all people using, or potentially using, the product as a single group. Since the definition of a market needs a group of people + the job-to-be-done, when defining the group of people, it is not suggested to use an actual job title. Instead, an all-inclusive term that encapsulates all job executors, usually a higher-level, generic term has to be found. Following the previous example, abstracted roofers, framers, plumbers, finish carpenters, etc., can be grouped into a higher-level category using the term “tradespeople”. For consumer product goods, the job executors are often referred to simply as “consumers.”

- **4. Job executor**

Since more than one way to describe the “group of people” could be identified, at this stage research teams have to choose a label that fits all types of people using the product, service, or idea. Some examples include the use of the term surgeons over cardiac surgeons, tradespeople over tradesmen, educators over teachers, accountants over tax preparers, or consumers over adults, to be more inclusive. It is important to define the “group of people” before defining the job-to-be-done, as representatives of the group will be interviewed to determine, from them alone, the way they define the job they are trying to get done.

- **5. Function of the product**

Products don't have jobs-to-be-done; people do. But to uncover the targeted group's job-to-be-done, it is often helpful to start by understanding what function/job the innovative product performs.

The typical question is: what does/will the new product or service help the group of people accomplish from a functional perspective? This can be investigated internally or, better, by going directly to the “group” of people (defined in step 4). Responses have to be collected into a single statement according to this formula: “The product will help the group of people [verb] + [object of the verb] + [contextual clarifier (optional)]”. For example, a boiler may be used to “heat + water + to the desired temperature,” or a dental drill may be used to “contour + the shape + of a tooth.”

This is not the customer's job-to-be-done yet. It is the function or the job that the product gets done, which is often only part of the job the customer is trying to get done. For example, while people may use a kettle to “heat water to the desired temperature,” the overall job they are trying to get done may be to “prepare a hot beverage for consumption.”

The goal of the market definition canvas is to help innovators uncover the job-to-be-done as perceived by the customer, not the product developer.

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• 6. Other products used and their functions

To get a feel for the entire job customers are trying to get done, research teams have to analyse what other products they use immediately before, while, and immediately after using the innovative product/service. For example, when tradespeople use a circular saw to “cut wood,” what other products are they using in conjunction with a circular saw? Perhaps they are also using a T-square, a measuring tape, sandpaper, and (or) a pencil. Once this list of products is ready, the functions / jobs that each of these other products gets done for the group of people has to be documented, using the same format used previously: [verb] + [object of the verb] + [contextual clarifier (optional)].

For example, it can be found through customer interviews that while the function of the circular saw is to “cut wood” (a job statement), that tradespeople use a T-square to ensure they “make a cut in a straight line” (a job statement), and that they use a pencil to “mark the cut path” (a job statement).

• 7. Abstracted job statement

Putting all the pieces together helps reveal the customer’s ultimate job-to-be-done at the right level of abstraction. It is assumed that the new product is getting part of a job done and people are using other products to complete the entire job-to-be-done. The customer’s job-to-be-done has to be defined in a way that includes the new product’s function (job) and rationalizes why customers are using all these other products as they cobble together a complete solution. For example, tradespeople are using a circular saw along with other products so they can “cut wood in a straight line” (the abstracted job statement); accountants use tax preparation software in conjunction with other products so they can “formulate and execute a tax strategy for a client” (the abstracted job statement).

Defining the market at this level of abstraction allows an evolvement of the new product over time to help customers get more, and eventually all, of their job done. It offers the innovator a built-in path and vision for growth, tied directly to what customers are trying to accomplish.

• 8. Customer’s Job-to-be-Done

Now the customer’s job can be documented. If there are multiple versions of the job statement, research teams will have to work with job executors to gain consensus on the best version.

Steps 5-8 need the use of customer interviews. If the job of the product is not represented, might be the job statement was abstracted to too high a level.

The market defined as a Group of people (Step 4) + Job-to-be-Done (Step 8) will facilitate the application of the Lean Startup approach and better use further tools.

7.6 The Value Proposition Canvas

The Value Proposition Canvas (VPC)³ is used to facilitate R&I projects clarifying the customer needs & how to create value for them. Osterwalder introduced this concept at depth in his book Value Proposition Design. The Value Proposition Canvas helps teams deepen their understanding of target customers. This allows to avoid one of the most common mistakes when developing an innovation: building something that nobody wants.

The Value Proposition Canvas is a plug-in tool to describe the Value Propositions and the target Customer Segments in more detail and evaluate the “fit” between the value the solution intends to create and the expectations the selected customers’ segment. The Value Proposition Canvas can be used before, during and after developing an in-depth knowledge of the customers. If used before, it will highlight what is needed to learn about customers and test about value propositions. If used after, it will help analyse and evaluate the “fit”. The Value Proposition Canvas can be applied to new and existing value propositions and customer segments alike.

³ <https://www.strategyzer.com/library/the-value-proposition-canvas>

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7.7 How to fill out the Value Proposition Canvas

The VPC is based on 2 main concepts:

- the Value Map: the set of value proposition benefits that are designed by R&I projects to attract customers.
- the Customer Profile: the set of customer characteristics that R&I projects assume, observe and verify in the market.

The Customer profile section has to be filled in by making assumptions on:

- jobs: it specifies what target customers are trying to get done. As an example, in case of taxi passengers as customers, they generally try to call a taxi, find a taxi, pay the taxi driver, etc.
- customers pains: it makes assumptions on what annoys the customer before, during & after getting job done. This is the space to uncover and document what frustrates target early adopters. There is the need to detail what creates friction and to learn about the things early adopters are desperate to solve. Following the previous example, taxi passengers may not want to wait for long time, be with an unsafe driver, etc.
- customers gains: it makes assumptions on what outcomes & benefits customers want. In the previous examples, taxi passengers may want to arrive on time, a fair price, an easy payment.

By doing this, an effective Customer Profile Summary will be created, which allows to have an immediate visualization of the customer profile.

Then it is the turn of the Value Map which describes explicitly how a product/service creates value, by specifying:

- products/services: This is how the value proposition manifests itself. In this space it's possible to be more specific about the proposed innovation.

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- pain relievers: they specify exactly which customers pains the proposed products/services alleviate specifically. This space is useful to document how the innovative product or service could relieve the existing customer pains.
- gain creators: it describes how the innovative product or service could fulfil the desired customer gains.

The “Pain relievers” and “Gain creators” spaces are not designed to describe features. Rather, they are designed to describe ways in which the desired outcome (relieved pain, desired gain or jobs to be done) could be fulfilled.

Finally, the Customer Profile and the Value Map have to be used to establish fit. Strategyzer defines fit as: “when your value map meets your customer profile-when your products and services produce pain relievers and gain creators that match one or more of the jobs, pains and gains that are important to your customer.”

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8 Annex 3 - Follow-up funding opportunities

8.1 EIC Transition

The **EIC Transition** funding scheme supports the maturation and validation of promising research results and helps bring technologies closer to market. It focuses on advancing technology readiness while supporting the development of business plans for commercialisation.

EIC Transition funds innovation activities that go beyond experimental proof of concept in the laboratory and supports both:

- **The maturation and validation of novel technologies**, moving them from the laboratory to relevant application environments.
- **The development of business models and market readiness**, helping innovations become commercially viable.

Grants of up to **€2.5 million** are available to validate and demonstrate technology in application-relevant environments and to develop market readiness. In some cases, **additional booster grants of up to €50.000** may also be awarded.

EIC Transition provides **open funding across all fields of science and technology**, without predefined thematic priorities. Projects must build on results generated by eligible EU-funded research projects.

Applications may be submitted by **single applicants** (SMEs, spin-offs, start-ups, research organisations, or universities) or by **small consortia** (minimum two and maximum five partners from at least two different EU Member States or associated countries).

For more information, visit:

https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-funding-opportunities/eic-transition_en

8.2 EIC Accelerator

The EIC Accelerator supports individual Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), in particular Startups and spin-out The **EIC Accelerator** supports individual Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), in particular start-ups and spin-out companies, to develop and scale up game-changing innovations. In some cases, small mid-caps (up to 499 employees) may also participate under the **investment-only option**.

The EIC Accelerator provides substantial financial support through:

- **Grant funding (non-dilutive)** of up to **€2.5 million** for innovation development costs, including demonstration and validation in relevant environments.
- **Equity investments of up to approximately €15 million** (through the EIC Fund) for scale-up and commercial deployment. Higher amounts may be available through the **STEP Scale-Up scheme** for strategic technologies.

In addition, selected companies receive **coaching, mentoring, access to investors and corporates**, and other opportunities through the **EIC Business Acceleration Services (BAS)**.

Applications can be submitted at any time through the EIC platform. Applicants must submit a **short application**, including a video pitch, a slide deck, and responses to a set of questions about their innovation and team.

Applications that meet all evaluation criteria but are not funded may receive a **Seal of Excellence**, which can help secure alternative funding from other sources. Companies awarded a Seal of Excellence may also access Business Acceleration Services.

Applicants must be established in **EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon Europe**. Applications are typically submitted by **single companies rather than consortia**.

For more information, visit: https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-funding-opportunities/eic-accelerator_en

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8.3 EIC Prizes

The **EIC Prizes** reward individuals or organisations that can most effectively address a predefined challenge, without prescribing how the challenge should be solved. These prizes aim to stimulate breakthrough innovation across sectors by encouraging cutting-edge solutions that bring significant benefits to citizens and society.

Key EIC Prizes include:

- **EU Prize for Women Innovators** – recognises women entrepreneurs behind breakthrough innovations. The prize includes awards of **€100,000, €70,000 and €50,000** in the main category, as well as a **€50,000 Rising Innovator prize** for a promising young innovator.
https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-prizes/european-prize-women-innovators-powered-eic-eit_en
- **European Capital of Innovation Awards (iCapital)** – recognises cities that successfully promote innovation ecosystems and connect citizens, public organisations, academia and businesses. The prize has a **total budget of €1.8 million**, with **€1 million awarded to the European Capital of Innovation winner**.
https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-prizes/european-capital-innovation-awards_en

For more information, visit:

https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-prizes_en

8.4 Fast Track and Plug-In schemes to apply for the EIC Accelerator

The **Fast Track scheme** ('Fast Track') and the **Plug-in scheme** ('Plug In') are two mechanisms under Horizon Europe. They allow funding bodies managing other parts of the Horizon Europe) and Horizon 2020 programmes (the Fast Track), as well as funding bodies managing certified national or regional programmes (Plug In), to submit projects from their portfolios directly to the **full application stage of the EIC Accelerator**.

To do so, eligible programmes must first carry out a dedicated **project review** of an ongoing (or recently completed) project and the proposal stemming from that project. This review must use **award criteria equivalent to those applied at the EIC Accelerator short application stage** and follow an evaluation process that ensures an **independent assessment**, in compliance with Horizon Europe rules.

Under the Fast Track and Plug In schemes, applicants do not apply directly to the EIC Accelerator call. Instead, the eligible programmes assess whether a project is suitable for EIC Accelerator support and, if selected, allow the project to **submit a full proposal directly**, bypassing the short application stage.

Proposals submitted through the Fast Track or Plug In schemes are **evaluated in the same way as all other full proposals**, and evaluators are **not informed whether an application originates from a Fast Track or Plug In scheme**.

For more information, visit:

https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-funding-opportunities/eic-accelerator/fast-track-and-plug-schemes-eic-accelerator_en

8.5 Booster grants for EIC Pathfinder and EIC Transition grant holders

The grant holders of **EIC Pathfinder projects** (including grants resulting from certain EIC pilot Pathfinder, FET-Open and FET-Proactive calls) and **EIC Transition projects** are eligible to receive **booster grants** with fixed amounts of up to **EUR 50,000**, as specified in the relevant call sections of the **EIC Work Programme**.

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In line with **Article 47(3)(b) of the Horizon Europe Regulation**, these grants may be awarded **outside the main calls**. They reflect the need and possibility for the EIC to proactively support—at any stage of project implementation—the assessment of potentially innovative leads stemming from an EIC Pathfinder project, or to reinforce the coordination and management of a portfolio where necessary.

These booster grants fund either:

- **complementary activities to explore potential pathways to commercialisation** (for EIC Pathfinder grant holders), or
- **portfolio activities** (for both EIC Pathfinder and EIC Transition grant holders).

These ad hoc grants do **not** fund research or activities that were already foreseen in the original project.

A maximum of **three booster grants** may be awarded for each **EIC Pathfinder project**, although more than three may be granted in **exceptional and duly justified cases**. A maximum of **one booster grant** may be awarded for each **EIC Transition project**.

Such ad hoc grants may be awarded to **an individual grant holder or a group of grant holders**.

EIC grant holders **may apply for a booster grant** following a discussion with an **EIC Programme Manager** or after a **project review**.

For more information, see:

https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-funding-opportunities/eic-pathfinder_en

https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-funding-opportunities/eic-transition_en

8.6 The InvestEU Programme

The **InvestEU Programme** builds on the successful model of the Investment Plan for Europe (the Juncker Plan). It brings together, under one framework, the European Fund for Strategic Investments and 13 other EU financial instruments. By triggering more than **€372 billion in additional investment over the period 2021–2027**, the InvestEU Programme aims to boost sustainable investment, innovation and job creation across Europe.

The Programme consists of three components:

- **The InvestEU Fund**, which aims to mobilise more than **€372 billion of public and private investment** through an EU budget guarantee of **€26.2 billion**. It supports investments carried out by implementing partners such as the European Investment Bank (EIB) Group and other financial institutions.
- **The InvestEU Advisory Hub**, which provides advisory support and technical assistance, including capacity building, to project promoters and organisations—both public and private. It helps with the preparation, development, structuring and implementation of investment projects.
- **The InvestEU Portal**, which connects investors and project promoters through an EU-wide platform. It provides an accessible database of investment opportunities and facilitates matchmaking and networking between projects, companies and potential investors.

The InvestEU Programme supports sustainable investment, innovation and job creation in Europe. Through the EU budget guarantee provided to international and national promotional banks, the programme aims to mobilise significant private and public investment in areas aligned with EU policy priorities.

It provides the European Union with crucial long-term financing by leveraging private and public funds to support Europe's sustainable recovery. It helps mobilise investment for key EU priorities, including the **green and digital transitions, innovation, strategic projects, and social investment and skills**.

The programme also contributes to the implementation of the **REPowerEU Plan**, the Commission's response to the global energy market disruption caused by Russia's war of aggression against Ukraine.

By bringing together several previous EU financial instruments under a single framework, the InvestEU Programme simplifies access to finance and investment for European companies and projects.

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For more information, visit:

https://investeu.europa.eu/investeu-programme_en

8.7 INTERREG EUROPE

Interreg Europe is an interregional cooperation programme co-funded by the European Union. The EU aims to reduce disparities in development, growth and quality of life across Europe's regions. The programme contributes to this objective and runs during the **2021–2027 programming period**.

Interreg Europe helps regional and national public authorities improve their policies by creating opportunities to exchange experience and share solutions to regional development challenges. The programme has a **budget of €394 million from the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)**.

Interreg Europe provides support in several ways:

- **Financial support** – funding is available for interregional cooperation projects that can lead to long-term collaborations and partnerships.
- **Networking opportunities** – participants can connect with partners, stakeholders and experts across Europe to exchange knowledge and good practices.

Public institutions and **private non-profit organisations** from all regions in **36 European countries** can benefit from the programme's funding opportunities and policy learning services. Eligible beneficiaries include public authorities at national, regional and local levels, as well as organisations involved in regional development policies, such as business support organisations, environmental bodies, and education and research institutions.

For more information, visit:

<http://www.interregeurope.eu/>

8.8 EUREKA and Eurostars funding

The **Eurostars programme** is an international funding programme that supports collaborative research and development (R&D) projects led by innovative small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). It aims to support the development of innovative products, processes and services with strong commercial potential.

Eurostars is part of the **European Partnership on Innovative SMEs**, co-funded by the European Union through **Horizon Europe** and implemented by the **Eureka Network**. It is the largest international funding programme dedicated to SMEs wishing to collaborate on R&D projects with partners from other participating countries.

Projects must involve international collaboration. The consortium must include **at least one additional independent organisation from another Eurostars country**. Funding is provided by **national funding bodies** (ministries or funding agencies in each participating country or region), with support from the European Commission.

To be eligible for Eurostars funding, projects must meet the following criteria:

- The project consortium must be **led by an innovative SME** based in a Eurostars country.
- The consortium must include **at least two independent entities**.
- Participating organisations must come from **at least two Eurostars countries**, with at least one being an EU Member State or a Horizon Europe Associated Country.
- SMEs from Eurostars countries must account for **at least 50% of the total project budget** (excluding subcontracting costs).
- **No single participant or country may account for more than 70% of the total project budget**.
- The **project duration must not exceed 36 months**.
- The project must focus **exclusively on civil applications**.

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As the programme operates through a **decentralised funding model**, organisations receive public funding from their respective **national funding bodies**, rather than directly from the Eureka Network. Funding is awarded according to **national rules and procedures**.

For more information, visit:

<https://eurekanetwork.org/programmes/eurostars/>

8.1 Financial Support for Third Parties (FSTP)

Cascade Funding, also known as **Financial Support for Third Parties (FSTP)**, is a mechanism used by the European Commission to distribute public funding through EU-funded projects. It supports beneficiaries such as start-ups, scale-ups, SMEs and mid-caps in developing or adopting innovative solutions, particularly in areas such as digital innovation. When allowed under the call conditions, project consortia may launch **FSTP open calls** linked to their ongoing projects. These calls enable third parties to apply for funding and participate in specific project activities during the project's implementation.

Although the FSTP mechanism can be used across several EU programmes, the feature to publish cascade funding calls on the EU Funding & Tenders Portal is only enabled for topics where the call conditions explicitly allow financial support for third parties.

This funding approach aims to **simplify administrative procedures and create a more SME-friendly application process**, allowing EU-funded projects to organise open calls and distribute smaller grants to external innovators.

The mechanism is widely used in **Horizon Europe (2021–2027)**.

For more information, visit:

<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/spaces/IT/pages/25559615/Cascade+Funding+Calls+Financial+Support+for+Third+Parties+FSTP>

8.1 European Green Deal – Just Transition Mechanism

The **European Green Deal** is the European Union's strategy to transform the EU into a modern, competitive and resource-efficient economy. Introduced in 2019 by Ursula von der Leyen, it responds to citizens' growing demand—particularly from younger generations—for decisive climate action. The initiative sets out a comprehensive roadmap to transform Europe's economy, energy system, transport and industry towards a more sustainable future.

Its objectives include reducing greenhouse gas emissions by **at least 55% by 2030** and achieving **climate neutrality by 2050**, as established in the European Climate Law. The Green Deal promotes a clean transition that protects both people and the environment while remaining economically viable and socially fair.

By investing in innovation, clean technologies and green infrastructure, the Green Deal supports a **just transition** for the regions and communities most affected by the shift towards a climate-neutral economy. As a result, Europeans benefit from cleaner air, more energy-efficient homes and products, and increased use of renewable energy in everyday life.

The Just Transition Mechanism

The **Just Transition Mechanism (JTM)** is a key instrument designed to ensure that the transition towards a climate-neutral economy takes place in a fair and inclusive way, leaving no one behind. It provides targeted support to the regions most affected by the transition, helping to mobilise **around €55 billion during the 2021–2027 period** to mitigate its socio-economic impacts.

The Just Transition Mechanism consists of **three main sources of financing**:

Just Transition Fund (JTF)

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The Just Transition Fund, with **€19.7 billion in current prices**, is expected to mobilise around **€7.3 billion in national co-financing**, reaching a total of approximately **€27 billion**.

https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/find-funding/eu-funding-programmes/just-transition-fund_en

InvestEU “Just Transition” scheme

This scheme provides a budgetary guarantee under the InvestEU programme across its four policy windows, complemented by advisory support through the InvestEU Advisory Hub. It is expected to mobilise **€10–15 billion**, mainly in private sector investment.

Public Sector Loan Facility

This facility combines **€1.3 billion in EU grants** with **€6–8 billion in loans from the European Investment Bank**, aiming to mobilise **€13.3–15.3 billion in public investment**.

Territorial Just Transition Plans

Territorial Just Transition Plans define the regions where the Just Transition Fund will be implemented. Developed in dialogue between Member States and the European Commission, these plans identify the specific challenges of each territory and outline development needs and objectives to be achieved by **2030**.

They also describe the types of operations envisaged and the governance arrangements. Once approved, these plans enable access to dedicated financing under the other two pillars of the Just Transition Mechanism.

Just Transition Platform

The Just Transition Mechanism goes beyond financial support. Through the **Just Transition Platform**, it provides a **single access point and helpdesk** offering comprehensive technical and advisory assistance.

Authorities and beneficiaries can use the platform to access information on funding opportunities, regulatory developments and sector-specific initiatives. It also promotes the exchange of best practices among stakeholders through regular meetings and networking events.

Who benefits from the Mechanism

Support under the Just Transition Mechanism is available to **all EU Member States**, with a particular focus on **carbon-intensive regions and those heavily dependent on fossil fuels**.

Access to funding is granted through territorial just transition plans covering the period up to **2030**, which identify priority territories and define strategies to address social, economic and environmental challenges.

The mechanism supports:

- **Citizens**, through job creation, reskilling opportunities, energy-efficient housing and access to affordable clean energy.
- **Companies**, by supporting investments, innovation and the adoption of low-carbon technologies.
- **Regions**, by promoting green jobs, sustainable transport, renewable energy, digital connectivity and improved energy infrastructure.

For more information, visit: https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/finance-and-green-deal/just-transition-mechanism_en

8.2 European Institute of Technology and Innovation

EIT Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs) are Europe-wide networks focused on addressing major societal challenges, ranging from sustainable energy and climate change to healthy food systems and urban mobility. They bring together **higher education institutions, research organisations, businesses (including SMEs), investors, and public and private organisations**.

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Under the **European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT)**, Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs) are long-term partnerships that integrate **education, research and innovation**. Through the KICs, the EIT strengthens cooperation among businesses, higher education institutions and research organisations, forming dynamic pan-European partnerships and creating favourable environments for creative thinking and innovation to flourish.

These partnerships are known as **Innovation Communities**, and each is dedicated to developing solutions to a specific global challenge, such as climate change, sustainable energy, healthy living, and sustainable food systems.

The **EIT Community** is one of the largest innovation ecosystems in Europe. It consists of the **European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT)** and its thematic **Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs)**, which act as the Institute's operational arms. Working together, they use the strength of their network to boost innovation across Europe and collaborate with partners worldwide.

Currently, the EIT Community includes the following Innovation Communities:

- EIT Climate-KIC
- EIT Culture & Creativity
- EIT Digital
- EIT Food
- EIT Health
- EIT InnoEnergy
- EIT Manufacturing
- EIT RawMaterials
- EIT Urban Mobility

The **EIT Alumni** network connects graduates and participants from EIT programmes across all Innovation Communities.

For more information: <https://www.eit.europa.eu/>

8.3 Programme for the Environment and Climate Action (LIFE)

The **LIFE Programme** is the European Union's funding instrument for **environment and climate action**. The programme budget is divided into four sub-programmes:

- **Nature and Biodiversity**
- **Circular Economy and Quality of Life**
- **Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation**
- **Clean Energy Transition**

The programme supports **demonstration projects, best practice initiatives, coordination and support actions, capacity-building activities and governance projects**. It also funds large-scale **Strategic Integrated Projects** and **Strategic Nature Projects**, which support the implementation of environmental and climate strategies, plans and programmes developed at regional, multi-regional or national level.

- **Eligibility**

To apply to the LIFE Programme, applicants must be:

- **Public or private legal entities** registered in an EU Member State or in an overseas country or territory linked to it.
- **Legal entities established in a third country associated with the LIFE Programme.**
- **Legal entities created under EU law or international organisations.**

Natural persons are **not eligible** to apply.

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As an exception, legal entities established in **non-associated third countries** may participate where their involvement is necessary to achieve the objectives of a specific action and to ensure the effectiveness of interventions within the EU. In such cases, these entities are usually expected to **cover the costs of their participation**.

- **Objectives**

The LIFE Programme supports the implementation of EU legislation and policies related to the environment and climate action. This includes the transition to renewable energy and improved energy efficiency. The programme promotes **innovation and best practices**, strengthens governance and stakeholder capacity, supports the effective implementation of EU environmental legislation, and encourages the **large-scale deployment of successful solutions** through policy integration and investment mobilisation.

The total budget for the programme for the **2021–2027 period is €5.45 billion**.

For more information, visit:

https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/find-funding/eu-funding-programmes/programme-environment-and-climate-action-life_en

8.4 Innovfin – EU Finance for Innovators

InnovFin – EU Finance for Innovators is a joint initiative launched by the **European Investment Bank Group (EIB and EIF)** in cooperation with the **European Commission** under **Horizon 2020**. InnovFin aims to facilitate and accelerate **access to finance for innovative businesses and other innovative entities in Europe**.

InnovFin provides a range of **financial instruments tailored to different types of financing needs**.

Start-up and SME financing

- **InnovFin Equity** provides equity investments and co-investments to or alongside funds focusing on **early-stage financing of enterprises operating in innovative sectors** covered by Horizon 2020 and located or active in the EU or Horizon 2020 Associated Countries. InnovFin Equity is available through several facilities, including **InnovFin Technology Transfer, InnovFin Business Angels, InnovFin Venture Capital, and InnovFin Fund-of-Funds**.
- **InnovFin SME Guarantee** provides **guarantees and counter-guarantees on debt financing between EUR 2.000 and EUR 7.5 million**, improving access to loan finance for **innovative small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and small mid-caps (up to 499 employees)**.

Corporate finance

- **InnovFin Emerging Innovators** offers a range of tailored financing products supporting **research and innovation (R&I) activities by small, medium and large companies**, as well as promoters of research infrastructure. Financing may take the form of **loans or guarantees**, provided either directly by the EIB or indirectly through financial intermediaries.
- **InnovFin MidCap Guarantee** provides **guarantees and counter-guarantees on debt financing of up to EUR 50 million**, helping innovative **mid-caps (up to 3.000 employees)** that are not eligible under the InnovFin SME Guarantee to access financing.
- **InnovFin Corporate Research Equity** (in collaboration with the **European Fund for Strategic Investments – EFSI**) increases the supply of **equity-type financing** for large research and innovation programmes and for innovative **large mid-caps and SMEs**. It addresses the market gap for large investments through instruments such as **contingent loans**, typically with **mid- to long-term repayment profiles linked to product development cycles**.

Science

- **InnovFin Science** supports **research and innovation investments by research organisations, public or private research institutes and universities**, including the financing of **buildings and infrastructure directly related to R&I activities**. It provides different forms of **debt and equity-type financing**.

Thematic financing

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- **InnovFin Energy Demo Projects** provides **loans, loan guarantees or equity-type financing** to innovative **energy demonstration projects**, including renewable energy technologies, smart energy systems, energy storage, carbon capture and storage, and carbon capture and utilisation. The instrument helps bridge the gap **between demonstration and commercialisation** and is deployed directly by the **European Investment Bank**.
- **InnovFin Infectious Diseases** provides financial products ranging from **standard debt to equity-type financing**, typically between **EUR 7.5 million and EUR 75 million**, for organisations developing **innovative vaccines, medicines, medical and diagnostic devices, or research infrastructures** aimed at combating infectious diseases. The product is provided directly by the **European Investment Bank**.

For more information, see: <https://www.eib.org/en/products/blending/innovfin/index.htm>

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9 Annex 4 – Non-financial support

9.1 WiderAdvance Facility

The **WiderAdvance Facility** is a **Horizon Europe initiative** that strengthens the capacity of organisations in **Widening Countries and Outermost Regions** to effectively disseminate, exploit and valorise research and innovation results, thereby improving the sustainability and long-term impact of their activities.

To support this objective, the Facility provides a portfolio of **tailored services** combining advisory support, capacity building, networking and awareness-raising. These services are delivered **free of charge** to eligible beneficiaries, both online and on-site, with experts working directly with beneficiary organisations.

The support offer includes expert coaching on **dissemination and exploitation planning**, guidance on **follow-up funding opportunities and synergies**, support for **intellectual asset management and standardisation**, as well as **training programmes and academies** aimed at increasing the maturity of **Key Exploitable Results (KERs)**. Additional services include **matchmaking with industry and relevant stakeholders**, **awareness-raising webinars**, and **study visits and mutual learning activities**.

The Facility primarily targets beneficiaries of **Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe Widening actions**, including **research teams, research managers and administrators (RMAs)**, **technology transfer professionals working with KERs**, and **organisational leadership**. The supported KERs should originate from **Widening/WIDERA actions** or from projects in related thematic domains.

Access to the Facility's services is provided through a **simple application process** under an **open call with quarterly submission deadlines**.

For more information, see: <https://www.wideradvance.eu/>

9.2 IMPAC3T-IP - Improving outcoMes and imPact from scenArio based licensing: Classical_Crisis and Co-creaTed IP

IMPAC3T-IP provides a freely accessible **toolbox** composed of digital tools, guides, best practices and templates designed to help generate broader impact from the **licensing of research results**. The toolbox supports users in three key situations:

- **When dealing with non-traditional outputs or assets**, often originating from the **Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences (AHSS)**
- **When responding to crises**, whether predictable or unforeseen, where **equitable access** to research results is essential
- **When managing complex co-creation processes**, involving multiple stakeholders with different approaches, expectations and roles

The use of the toolbox is complemented by the **IMPAC3T-IP™ Academy**, which offers **training sessions** on how to leverage the licensing tools and associated know-how, as well as guidance on applying them in collaboration with colleagues and external partners.

For more information, see: <https://www.impact3tip.eu/>

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9.3 IAM4RE – Intellectual Asset Management for Research and Entrepreneurship

IAM4RE develops training resources and support tools to strengthen **knowledge valorisation, intellectual asset (IA) management, and the use of standardisation in research and innovation**. These resources are intended for **researchers, students and knowledge transfer professionals** seeking to improve how research results are translated into practical applications.

The initiative provides a range of **capacity-building resources**, including:

- **Training materials and MOOCs** on knowledge valorisation, intellectual asset management and standardisation
- **Capacity-building programmes** for researchers, students and knowledge transfer professionals
- **Train-the-trainer programmes** enabling technology and knowledge transfer offices to deliver their own training
- **Mentoring tools and service formats** supporting spin-off creation and the practical application of valorisation methodologies

For more information, see: <https://iam4re.eu/>

9.4 European Investment Project Portal (EIPP)

The **European Investment Project Portal (EIPP)** is the EU's **online matchmaking platform**, enabling EU-based project promoters — both public and private — to connect with potential investors worldwide.

The Portal is a **free service provided by the European Commission** and forms part of the EU's broader efforts to **mobilise investment, stimulate economic growth and create jobs across the European Union**.

For more information, see:

<https://ec.europa.eu/investeuportal/desktop/en/index.html>

9.5 Entrepreneurship and Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)

A **dedicated section of the European Commission portal provides comprehensive information on EU funding opportunities for SMEs**, as well as an overview of the EU's policies and initiatives supporting small and medium-sized enterprises:

<https://ec.europa.eu/growth/smes>

To determine whether a particular programme is relevant to your specific case, it is recommended that you **contact your local Enterprise Europe Network partner**, who can provide **tailored advice and support on accessing and applying for EU funding**.

Contact details for **Enterprise Europe Network members** are available at:

<http://een.ec.europa.eu/about/branches/>

9.6 Access to finance in Europe

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University Technology Transfer Offices (UTTOs) play an important role in transferring technology and commercialising innovations emerging from the **university sector** to the marketplace.

In addition, the following webpage provides information on how to **access loans and venture capital supported by the European Union**. By selecting your country, you can locate **banks and venture capital funds that offer EU-supported financing** for businesses.

For more information, see:

http://europa.eu/youreurope/business/funding-grants/access-to-finance/index_en.htm

9.7 Tenders Electronic Daily

TED (Tenders Electronic Daily) provides free access to **public procurement opportunities** from the **European Union, the European Economic Area and beyond**.

Every day, from **Tuesday to Saturday**, around **2.000 public procurement notices** are published on TED.

Users can **browse, search and filter procurement notices** by country, region, business sector and other criteria.

Information about each procurement notice is available in the **24 official EU languages**. Notices published by **EU institutions** are available in full in all these languages.

For more information, see: <http://ted.europa.eu/TED/search/search.do>

9.8 Innovaccess - Intellectual Property Portal

Innovaccess aims to enhance **intellectual property (IP) support services** for **small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)**, helping them to transform their **intellectual capital into commercial value and increased competitiveness**.

The portal provides guidance on **protecting intellectual property rights** and improving understanding of **IP protection and management practices**.

For more information, see: <http://www.innovaccess.eu/>

9.9 Seal of Excellence – EuroQuity Initiative

This initiative is dedicated to companies that have received the **Seal of Excellence** under the **EU Horizon 2020 SME Instrument**. Matchmaking activities and support services are provided to facilitate their **access to risk finance** and enhance their **visibility among investors**, through a dedicated **online community hosted on the EuroQuity platform**.

Through this community, **Seal of Excellence SMEs** gain immediate visibility among a wide range of stakeholders, including **European business angel networks, venture capital funds, corporate investors and potential business partners**. At the same time, investors benefit from an **additional level of assurance regarding the quality and innovation potential of the SMEs' projects**.

Participating companies can also benefit from several **free support services** aimed at supporting their growth at the **European level**, including:

- **Increased visibility and access to European investors**
- **Opportunities to pitch online to investors during dedicated e-pitch sessions**

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- **Connections with National Contact Points (NCPs) in their respective countries**

For more information, see: <https://www.euroquity.com/fr/community/Access4SMEs--Seal-of-Excellence-5bb56459-4f88-4d3c-a2eb-8e4b6e865ea5/>

9.10 Dealflow

Dealflow.eu is an initiative supported by the **European Commission** that helps **EU-funded innovations** raise investment, build ventures and expand their networks. The platform supports projects funded under **Horizon 2020** by providing targeted services to strengthen their commercialisation and investment readiness.

Three main types of support are offered:

- **Venture building** – tailored support on key business topics such as sales strategy, market sizing and market research, organisational structure, and pitching
- **Fundraising preparation** – assistance in preparing investor materials and facilitating access to investor networks
- **Networking** – introductions to industry experts, potential clients and new partners through the platform’s matchmaking tools, community and events

For more information, see: <https://dealflow.eu/>

9.11 Startup Europe – networking for tech and start ups

Startup Europe is an initiative of the **European Commission** that aims to connect **high-tech start-ups, scale-ups, investors, accelerators, corporate networks, universities and the media** across Europe.

The four main objectives of **Startup Europe** are to:

- **Connect people** within the European start-up ecosystem
- **Connect local start-up ecosystems** across Europe
- **Help start-ups establish themselves in new markets** (“soft-landing”)
- **Promote and celebrate entrepreneurial success**

For more information, see: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/startup-europe>

9.12 Accelerators and Incubators

If you are planning to create a **start-up or spin-off**, it is advisable to explore **accelerators and incubators operating in your region**. These organisations support early-stage companies by providing mentoring, training, networking opportunities, and sometimes seed funding.

Below is a **non-exhaustive list of international and pan-European accelerator and incubation initiatives**:

- **Startupbootcamp** – Founded in 2010, Startupbootcamp is a global network of industry-focused start-up accelerators offering intensive mentoring programmes, investor connections and access to international corporate partners.
- **Startup Weekend (Techstars)** – Startup Weekend events bring together developers, designers, entrepreneurs and innovators to collaborate and develop start-up ideas during intensive weekend workshops, typically lasting around 54 hours.
- **StartupBus** – StartupBus is an entrepreneurial competition in which participants (“buspreneurs”) collaborate to develop start-up ideas during a multi-day journey, culminating in presentations to investors and mentors.
- **Wayra** – Wayra is an open innovation platform and start-up accelerator backed by **Telefónica**, supporting technology start-ups through mentoring, corporate partnerships, investment opportunities and access to global markets.

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Across Europe, numerous **national and regional accelerators and incubators** support start-up creation and scale-up activities. Examples include:

- **Austria:** INiTS, i5invest
- **Belgium:** imec.istart, NEST'Up
- **Bulgaria:** Eleven Ventures, LAUNCHub Ventures
- **Croatia:** ZIP Zagreb Innovation Centre
- **Czech Republic:** StartupYard
- **Denmark:** Accelerace
- **Estonia:** Startup Wise Guys, Garage48
- **Finland:** Maria 01, Kiuas
- **France:** Station F, Numa
- **Germany:** hub:raum, Axel Springer Plug and Play
- **Greece:** Openfund
- **Italy:** H-Farm, LUISS EnLabs
- **Lithuania:** Startup Wise Guys Vilnius programmes
- **Netherlands:** Rockstart
- **Portugal:** Beta-i (Lisbon Challenge)
- **Spain:** SeedRocket, Tetuan Valley

These organisations provide **mentoring, access to investors, workspace, training programmes and networking opportunities**, helping start-ups accelerate their development and access international markets.

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7.5 Annex 5 Horizon Results Booster documentation (PATTERN)

BOOSTER

Characterisation table

KER name:	Input from the Beneficiary	Comment by the Expert
Description	Comprehensive mapping and gap analysis of more than 500 Open & Responsible Research and Innovation (Open RRI) training opportunities across Europe. Provides an evidence base to design curricula, prioritise investments, and update institutional strategies.	<i>Add a 1-page executive infographic and discipline-specific snapshots. Release a machine-readable dataset (CSV/JSON) with schema + CCO to enable reuse and benchmarking. Track KPIs: views, downloads, citations, and derivative works.</i>
Target market/end users	Researchers at all career stages; doctoral schools and research integrity/ethics offices; research managers and librarians; funders and policy bodies; training providers and EU projects.	<i>Segment by buyer/user: (i) decision-makers (deans, RDM leads), (ii) trainers, (iii) researchers. Tailor messages: policy briefs for leaders; short slide decks for trainers; search-friendly landing for researchers.</i>
End-users needs / problems	Hard to find a consolidated, up-to-date view of RRI training; limited time to compare quality and coverage; need to identify gaps to plan courses and budgets.	<i>Explicitly map needs to report sections and include recommended actions per audience. Add a 'Top 10 gaps by effort/impact' to make prioritisation easier.</i>
Competitive advantages	Pan-European scope; harmonised metadata; explicit gap/opportunity analysis; persistent identifiers (DOIs); open licence and reproducible methods.	<i>Strengthen by publishing codebook + methodology annex; ensure replicability for future updates; add crosswalks to EOSC skills frameworks.</i>
Use model	Open access report (CC-BY) on PATTERN site and Zenodo; dataset/metadata open (preferably CCO); referenced by PATTERN trainings and policy briefs.	<i>Add a versioning plan (12–18-month cadence) and changelog. Provide API-like CSV/JSON exports and a simple dashboard embedded in the website.</i>
Early Adopters	National OS coordinators; doctoral schools; OpenAIRE/EOSC nodes; EARMA training community; approach via webinars, newsletters, OpenAIRE channels, LinkedIn, EU events.	<i>Pilot 'co-hort' briefings with 5–8 institutions; collect MoUs for reuse. Offer office-hours for adopters in the first 3 months after release.</i>
Adopters' problems/needs	Benchmarking against peers; evidence to justify investment; which modules to adopt/retire first.	<i>Provide downloadable 'starter packs' per adopter type with slides, template memos, and suggested KPIs.</i>
Alternative solution	Ad-hoc web searches, local spreadsheets/surveys, vendor catalogues—fragmented and quickly outdated.	<i>Include a comparative table in the annex showing why the PATTERN mapping is more complete/maintainable.</i>

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Unique Value Proposition	Authoritative, pan-EU evidence base with machine-readable data and actionable gaps → decisions in weeks, not months.	<i>Add 3 user stories (doctoral school, RPO integrity office, funder) to illustrate time saved and improved decisions.</i>
Competitors	Isolated national portals, legacy project lists, commercial course directories.	<i>Name exemplars generically and position PATTERN on openness, coverage, and update plan. Keep tone collaborative and invite contributions.</i>
Timing	Immediate – public and citable; refreshed periodically.	<i>Publish a public roadmap with the next update window and scope.</i>
IP Strategy	Content under CC-BY; metadata under CCO; clear attribution and citation guidance; DOI via Zenodo.	<i>Add a licence matrix (report, figures, datasets) and a contributor agreement for future updates.</i>

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Characterisation table

[prepare a characterisation table for each selected KER]

KER name:	Input from the Beneficiary	Comment by the Expert
Description	Federated training ecosystem combining OpenPlato (LMS and catalogue), Projects (project-based learning), PATTERN website, and a unified login (SSO). Enables modular, multilingual, FAIR-aligned RRI learning with SCORM/xAPI and archiving via Zenodo.	<i>Clarify end-to-end learner journeys (discover → enrol → learn → credential → reuse). Publish a lightweight SLA, governance model, and data protection summary to build trust.</i>
Target market/end users	Researchers, trainers, data stewards, R&I support staff, doctoral schools, European projects and policy stakeholders needing reusable Open RRI assets.	<i>Prioritise 2–3 institutional archetypes (doctoral school; national node; RI). For each, document expected outcomes and success metrics.</i>
End-users needs / problems	Fragmented training sources; lack of SSO; poor interoperability; difficulty tracking reuse and completions across institutions.	<i>Add analytics definitions (active users, completions, badges issued, reuse events). Ensure exports for institutional reporting.</i>
Competitive advantages	Open-source stack; EU hosting & GDPR compliance; SCORM/xAPI compatibility; persistent archiving with DOIs; editorial oversight; multi-level sustainability (static access → active use → continuous improvement).	<i>Protect against single-points-of-failure: list critical plugins/services, replacement options, and upgrade windows. Document federation/onboarding steps.</i>
Use model	Open access for learners/trainers; federation with institutional spaces; content archived with DOIs; sustainability via OpenAIRE core funding, partnerships/memberships; optional certifications/badges and TTT pathways.	<i>Offer an institutional 'starter kit': SSO pilot guide, content-pack templates, and badge criteria. Publish pricing/effort bands for optional services (where applicable).</i>
Early Adopters	PATTERN pilot institutions; EOOSC and OpenAIRE nodes; EARMA/Eurodoc networks. Channels: SSO pilots, webinars, conference demos, MoUs.	<i>Secure 3–5 lighthouse integrations and publish case studies. Create a community call every quarter with a public backlog.</i>
Adopters' problems/needs	Need stable, compliant platform; integration with existing LMS; recognition/credentialing; predictable upkeep.	<i>Provide LTI/SSO integration guides; badge/credential templates; and a 5-year maintenance statement with responsibilities.</i>

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Alternative solution	Use of siloed institutional LMS, generic MOOCs, or ad-hoc repositories without federation, DOIs, or governance.	<i>Position as 'federated + open + persistent'. Show side-by-side comparison (interoperability, governance, sustainability).</i>
Unique Value Proposition	A European, federated, GDPR-compliant training commons with persistent archiving and editorial governance—built for reuse and institutional adoption.	<i>Back UVP with KPIs and 2–3 measurable commitments (e.g., uptime, support window for plugin upgrades).</i>
Competitors	Proprietary MOOC platforms; isolated institutional LMS; static resource portals.	<i>Acknowledge their reach/ease; differentiate on openness, federation, and sustainability commitments.</i>
Timing	Available now; roadmap delivered iteratively; partners committed to at least five years of basic maintenance post-grant.	<i>Add a public roadmap with dependencies and a deprecation policy.</i>
IP Strategy	Software/content mix: OpenPlato content under open licences (e.g., CC-BY); Projects platform components shared openly; metadata CC0, website content CC-BY.	<i>Include a licence registry per course and per platform component; clarify trademark/branding usage and contributor guidelines.</i>

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Characterisation table

KER name:		
	Input from the Beneficiary	Comment by the Expert
Description	Modular trainings across eight Open RRI/Open Science areas (Citizen Science, Science Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation, Gender & Inclusion, Mental Health & Leadership, Open Access, FAIR RDM, Research Integrity). Mix of self-paced, instructor-led and project-based formats; Train-the-Trainers components.	Package every module so it's immediately reusable. Each should include a trainer kit, a learner kit, and an interoperable bundle (SCORM/H5P), all deposited in Zenodo with a DOI for traceability. For the most requested topics, add a micro-credential version (bite-sized, assessable learning units that issue a recognised digital badge or credit), short, self-paced and badge-ready, to increase reach and completion.
Target market/end users	Doctoral/postdoctoral researchers; data stewards; research managers; policy and support staff; European project teams.	Distinguish clearly between doctoral schools (credit-oriented, curriculum-linked) and research offices or support staff (skills-focused, short courses). Map every module to EOSC and competency frameworks to make accreditation and institutional adoption easier.
End-users needs / problems	Need flexible, credible, and reusable training aligned with funder requirements; recognition/credits; language/local examples.	Include a translation and localisation plan so the content can be adapted easily to national contexts and languages. Provide a brief accreditation mapping guide (e.g., ECTS equivalence) so partners can integrate modules into their own systems without guessing.
Competitive advantages	Pilot-tested; interoperable formats (SCORM, PDF, H5P); multilingual pathways; strong integration with OpenAIRE/EOSC and persistent archiving; TtT for scale.	Strengthen your edge by publishing learning outcomes and assessment rubrics for each course, as this shows quality assurance. Add universal design and neurodiversity checklists to ensure accessibility and inclusiveness.
Use model	Open Educational Resources by default (CC-BY / CC-BY-NC); hosted on OpenPlato/Projects; archived on Zenodo; reusable by institutions; optional certification/badging.	Create re-use templates (slides, facilitation guide, evaluation form) that institutions can copy. Add a short LTI/LMS integration note so IT teams can import content easily into their own learning systems.
Early Adopters	EU doctoral schools; national OS nodes; research infrastructures; channels: partner networks, OpenAIRE/EOSC portals, conference workshops, webinars.	Offer a "first-run" package to about 10 early adopters with co-branding and joint evaluation. Collect feedback and testimonials early—these are powerful for credibility and scaling.
Adopters' problems/needs	Quality-assured content ready to deliver; minimal setup; evidence of impact; support for trainers.	Help adopters deliver confidently; publish a Train-the-Trainers calendar, provide office hours or help-desk etiquette, and share pre/post

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		evaluation templates with indicative effect sizes to show measurable learning impact.
Alternative solution	Institution-specific courses, generic MOOCs, vendor workshops; often limited reuse rights and no alignment with EOSC skills.	Clarify how your approach differs from MOOCs or vendor-led courses. Add a simple reuse decision tree (e.g., "Can I adapt this? What licence applies?") and show how your model aligns with funders' FAIR and Open Science requirements.
Unique Value Proposition	A curated, European OER catalogue with TtT and persistent DOIs—easy to adopt, adapt, and accredit.	Make the value tangible: highlight time saved and cost avoided compared to building courses in-house. As soon as pilots finish, include 2–3 quantitative examples (e.g., hours saved, number of adoptions).
Competitors	MOOC platforms; national training initiatives; thematic networks' materials (e.g., data stewardship communities).	Keep a collaborative tone and position your catalogue as an open, European space that invites contributions and translations. Emphasise your strengths: openness, federation, and complete packaging (materials + metadata + DOI).
Timing	Immediate for Cycle-1 modules; streamlined updates and TtT roll-outs May–Oct 2025; ongoing thereafter.	Publish a release and update calendar per module. Maintain a public changelog and a "What's new" banner in OpenPlato to keep users informed and confident that materials stay current.
IP Strategy	OER licences (CC-BY/CC-BY-NC); metadata CCO; contributor attribution; case-study credits; DOI via Zenodo.	Add a Contributor Licence Agreement and a licence matrix (for content, data, code, visuals). Define brand and logo-use guidelines so partners can promote co-branded materials without confusion.

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Exploitation intentions table

KER name: Report on the analysis of existing training activities and quality assessment	Input from the Beneficiary
Description	Comprehensive mapping and gap analysis of >500 Open and Responsible Research and Innovation training opportunities for researchers across Europe; establishes an evidence base for curriculum design and policy recommendations.
Target market/end users	Researchers at all career stages; research managers; doctoral schools; training providers; policy and funding bodies seeking the state-of-play on RRI training.
Competitive advantages	Pan-European coverage; structured metadata; clear identification of gaps and opportunities; actionable insights feeding infographics, factsheets, and program design; persistent availability through DOI and open repositories.
Use model	Open access report (CC-BY) hosted on the PATTERN website and Zenodo; can be reused, cited, and embedded in institutional training strategies and EU policy processes.
Partners	All consortium partners (lead WP1 team).
Timing	Immediate: already publicly available via PATTERN website/Knowledge Hub and Zenodo; updates can be issued on an annual/biennial cadence if needed.
IP status	Open content, CC-BY; underlying datasets/metadata to be shared with appropriate licensing (e.g., CC0 for metadata).

KER name: PATTERN Digital Ecosystem	Input from the Beneficiary
Description	Federated training and discovery ecosystem combining OpenPlato (Moodle-based LMS and catalogue), Projects (project-based learning platform), the PATTERN website, and a unified login (Keycloak-based SSO). Supports modular, multilingual, FAIR-aligned RRI learning, including SCORM/xAPI content and EOSC integration.
Target market/end users	Researchers, trainers, data stewards, R&I support staff, doctoral schools, policy stakeholders, and European projects needing reusable Open RRI training assets.
Competitive advantages	Robust governance (OpenAIRE & LPI), open-source stack, European hosting & GDPR compliance, interoperability (SCORM/xAPI), persistent archiving via Zenodo, editorial oversight, and multi-level sustainability (static access → active use → continuous improvement).
Use model	Open access for learners/trainers; federation with institutional spaces; content archived with DOIs; sustainability via OpenAIRE core funding, voluntary memberships/partnerships, integration into curricula; option for certifications/badges and Train-the-Trainers pathways.
Partners	OpenAIRE (OpenPlato), LPI (Projects & SSO), LOBA (website), plus thematic leaders.
Timing	Available now (platforms live); roadmap features delivered iteratively; partners committed to at least five years of basic maintenance post-grant.

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IP status	Software/content mix: Projects platform code available under CC-BY-NC-SA 4.0; OpenPlato content under open licences set by contributors (e.g., CC-BY; metadata CC0). Website content CC-BY.
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KER name: PATTERN Trainings	Input from the Beneficiary
Description	Personalised, modular training programmes across eight Open RRI/OS skill areas (Citizen Science, Science Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation, Gender & Inclusion, Mental Health & Leadership, Open Access, FAIR RDM, Research Integrity). Mixture of self-paced, instructor-led, and project-based learning with Train-the-Trainers components.
Target market/end users	Doctoral and postdoctoral researchers; early-career academics; data stewards; research managers; policy and support staff; European project teams.
Competitive advantages	Backed by a large pilot base and evaluation cycles; interoperable formats (SCORM, PDF, H5P); multilingual pathways; accreditation potential (e.g., ECTS in partner contexts); strong reuse and integration with EOSC/OpenAIRE ecosystem.
Use model	Open educational resources by default (CC-BY / CC-BY-NC); hosted on OpenPlato/Projects with persistent archiving on Zenodo; available for reuse/adaptation by institutions; optional certification/badging.
Partners	All thematic leaders and pilot institutions (e.g., AU, SISSA, APRE/LOBA, UniSR/ESF, SciLink, UMinho/OpenAIRE, DANS, EARMA).
Timing	Immediate for existing modules (Cycle 1 complete); updated/streamlined modules and TtT roll-outs from May–October 2025; ongoing updates thereafter through editorial governance.
IP status	Open content – primarily CC-BY or CC-BY-NC; metadata under CC0; case studies credited to contributors.

Comments & Remarks by KER

KER 1 – D1.1 Report

- Prioritise a short executive infographic and discipline-specific snapshots to drive adoption.
- Track KPIs (views, downloads, citations, derivative works) and refresh every 12–18 months focusing on fast-changing areas.
- Offer a machine-readable dataset (CSV/JSON) with clear schema and CC0 to enable reuse by national nodes. This would allow publishing the underlying data from the D1.1 analysis in a simple format that computers can read and other teams can plug into their systems.
- Map findings directly to course updates and policy briefs to complete the evidence → action loop.

KER 2 – Digital Ecosystem

- Lock in governance: publish a lightweight SLA and an editorial calendar; document ownership of each subsystem. Write down who owns what, what level of service you promise, and when content/updates go out. Universities won't integrate or rely on a platform unless roles, uptime, and support are crystal clear.

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- SLA uptime target (e.g., 99.5%), backups/restore policy, incident response time, support channel & hours, planned maintenance window.
- Editorial calendar: a simple month-by-month schedule for content drops (e.g., “1st week: publish 2 modules; 3rd week: bug-fix release; last week: news post”).
- Ownership table: list each subsystem and its owner/backup.
- De-risk dependencies: maintain a list of critical plugins/services with replacement options and upgrade windows. Keep a short “bill of materials” for all critical plugins/services, plus what you’ll do if one breaks, and when you’ll upgrade.
- Strengthen institutional buy-in via SSO pilots and credit/badge recognition; propose a voluntary membership tiering. Make it easy for a university to connect with Single Sign-On, give learners portable recognition (badges/credits), and offer an optional “membership” for institutions that want support and visibility.
- Define success metrics: active users, course completions, TtT certifications, reuse events, external institutional adoptions.

KER 3 – Trainings

- Package each course with: (i) trainer kit, (ii) learner kit, (iii) SCORM/H5P bundle, (iv) Zenodo record with DOI. Ship every module as a ready-to-teach bundle so other teams can adopt it without emailing you.
- Convert high-demand modules to self-paced micro-credentials; align with EOSS skills frameworks. Turn the most requested topics into short, self-paced units (30–60 minutes) that award a digital badge or credit.
- Rotate and refresh real-world examples so none go stale, and make it easy for partners to contribute new ones. Credit contributors visibly.
- Create a small, active group of trainers who share tips, co-create fixes, and keep quality high as you scale.

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The exploitation roadmap for KER 1 Report on the analysis of existing training activities and quality assessment

Exploitation roadmap for KER [title of the KER]	Input by the Beneficiary	Comment by the Expert
Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Release machine-readable dataset (CSV/JSON) under CCO with DOI on Zenodo; add simple API/CSV exports on the PATTERN site. - Establish an update governance note (owners, cadence 12-18 months, changelog) and a licence matrix (report/data/figures). - Webinars targeting doctoral schools, RI/ethics offices, and funders. Collect MoUs for reuse. - Embed key findings into PATTERN policy briefs and course refresh backlog. - Create a dashboard (views, downloads, citations, reuse signals) embedded on the website. 	<p><i>Make the roadmap feel like a living product, not a static report. Add a visible timeline page on the website showing when the next version and dataset refresh will happen — this helps external users plan reuse. Include a concise “evidence → action” checklist tailored to key audiences (leaders, trainers, researchers) so each group can see what to do with the findings. This turns insights into practical guidance and supports measurable adoption.</i></p>
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lead: WP1 lead institution (custodian of the report and dataset). - Supporting: Thematic partners for domain snapshots; LOBA for web updates; Partner(s) hosting Zenodo records; OpenAIRE channel amplification. - Advisory: Editorial board to validate scope of updates. 	<p><i>Clarity of ownership builds confidence. Explicitly name a single custodian for the DOI and dataset (responsible for updates and metadata). Publish short contributor guidelines explaining how partners can propose new data or corrections — include the metadata schema and codebook. This avoids confusion and ensures consistent quality as others start to reuse or cite the dataset.</i></p>
Milestones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - M+3 (Sep 2026): governance note and licence matrix live. - M+4 (Oct 2026): dataset + DOI + website dashboard online. - M+6 (Dec 2026): 2 webinars; 5–8 institutional MoUs. KPIs Y1 post-project: ≥1,500 report views; ≥600 dataset downloads; ≥10 institutional adoptions; ≥3 citations/mentions in policy/training docs. 	<p><i>Go beyond listing dates: add a “Top 10 gaps by impact/effort” summary in the next release to help users prioritise where to act first. Include a mechanism to track derivative works (for example, forks, translated reports, or analyses built on the dataset). This gives you real evidence of reuse and strengthens the case for ongoing support or funding.</i></p>

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Costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Year 1: €10–15k (editorial, design of infographic, dashboard and maintenance). - 3-year cumulative: €30–40k (two refresh cycles + comms). 	<p><i>The proposed range is realistic. Add a small translation/localisation reserve (€3–5 k over three years) to ensure the infographic and snapshots can be adapted to local contexts and languages. This relatively minor cost often yields a major increase in visibility and uptake.</i></p>
Revenues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct revenues: none (public good under CC-BY/CC0). - Indirect value: project reuse, policy uptake, visibility for partners. 	<p><i>Keep all materials fully open and accessible to maintain trust and visibility. Focus on indirect value (policy citations, invitations to new proposals, institutional reuse agreements). Build a simple tracker for these so you can quantify impact in future reporting.</i></p>
Other sources of coverage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Partners’ in-kind effort; - Future EU/national calls (Open Science capacity, EOSC skills); - Sponsorship for infographics/events. Timing: secure at M+2 to hit the Oct 2026 release window. 	<p><i>Identify at least two specific EU or national funding calls aligned with Open Science or EOSC skills, and prepare short concept notes early. This lets you move quickly when calls open and ensures sustainability beyond the project’s lifetime.</i></p>

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The exploitation roadmap

Fill in the template thinking at what happens when your current project will finish.

Exploitation roadmap for KER <i>(title of the KER)</i>	Input by the Beneficiary	Comment by the Expert
Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Publish SLA (uptime, upgrade windows) and governance model; confirm 5-year basic maintenance commitments (OpenAIRE OpenPlato; LPI Projects). - Finalise plugin/risk register and deprecation policy; document federation/onboarding steps. - Run 3 SSO pilots with institutions; package 'starter kit' (LTI/SSO guides, content packs, badge criteria). - Launch a voluntary membership/sponsorship programme; publish public roadmap and editorial calendar. - EOSCAAI alignment steps documented; KPI taxonomy and analytics exports agreed. - Website rationalisation decision (merge vs keep) and redirect plan. 	<p><i>Begin with a realistic operational goal ("Level-2" = stable active use) before expanding toward "Level-3" (continuous improvement). This helps avoid over-promising while still demonstrating a credible path for growth once new funding or memberships arrive. Clarify what "active use" entails (uptime, content update frequency, user support) and show how the team will evolve the platform from basic maintenance to active product development. This staged approach builds trust among partners and funders.</i></p>
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lead ops: OpenAIRE (OpenPlato), LPI (Projects); LOBA (website). - Governance: editorial board + platform owners; institutions piloting SSO. - Finance: OpenAIRE core ops; LPI grants; membership manager (rotating). 	<p><i>Assign a clear product owner for each subsystem (OpenPlato, Projects, website, SSO). This ensures accountability for quality, updates, and bug resolution. Create a single intake channel for feature requests (e.g., a shared form or GitHub board) so requests can be prioritised transparently. These two steps keep governance lightweight but professional, avoiding confusion and duplicated work once the project ends.</i></p>
Milestones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - M+3 (Sep 2026): SLA and governance published; risk register live. 	<p><i>Pair your quantitative KPIs with practical service indicators. In addition to tracking users, completions, and DOIs, monitor reuse events (e.g.,</i></p>

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - M+4 (Oct 2026): 3 SSO pilots completed; membership programme launched. - M+6 (Dec 2026): 10 institutional adoptions; analytics dashboard live. - KPIs Y1 post-project: ≥2,000 active users; ≥500 course completions; ≥50 DOIs minted for archived training assets; ≥10 badges issued; ≥10 member orgs. 	<p><i>Imports of content into external LMSs) and support resolution time (e.g., closing 90% of tickets within 10 working days). This shows that the platform isn't just online, but actively helping institutions deliver learning. Regular reporting against these indicators will make the ecosystem's performance visible and fundable.</i></p>
Costs	<p>Aligned to D2.3 scenarios:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Level-2 (active use): ~€20k/year baseline. - Level-3 (continuous improvement): ~€120k/year (feature dev, integrations, UX). - 3-year outlook: €60k (L2) to €360k (L3), depending on ambition. 	<p><i>Make the operational "Level-2 vs Level-3" model more concrete by explaining what each level includes (scope of maintenance, SLAs, community support). Be transparent about which services are optional add-ons (e.g., analytics, credentialing, custom integration) so partners and sponsors can see where their contributions make a difference. This clarity helps justify costs and attract co-funding.</i></p>
Revenues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Voluntary membership/sponsorship: €20–50k in Year 1; €60–120k by Year 3. - Optional certification/badging fees: €5–15k Y1; €20–45k Y3. - Service packages (integration, content curation): pilot €10–20k Y1; €30–60k Y3. - Assumptions: 10–25 member orgs; modest badge uptake; 3–6 service engagements. 	<p><i>Support your revenue targets with storytelling and transparency. Publish a simple pricing and benefits page that shows what members receive at each tier (visibility, analytics reports, co-branding, priority support). Add 2–3 "lighthouse" case studies from early adopters (concrete stories showing institutional benefits) to accelerate membership uptake. Evidence of real-world value convinces others to join.</i></p>
Other sources of coverage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OpenAIRE core budget (OpenPlato ops); - LPI multi-sponsor and grant mix (Projects); - EU and national/regional grants; - Foundation sponsorships. - Timing: secure Y1 runway by M+3; multi-year grants by M+6. 	<p><i>To maintain independence and resilience, diversify funding streams. Stage funding commitments (e.g., Year-1 runway first, multi-year grants later) so that no single sponsor controls operations. Keep procurement-ready documentation (SLA, Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), and a data map) so you can quickly comply with funder or institutional procurement rules when scaling. This readiness is often the difference between a smooth transition and a funding gap.</i></p>

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The exploitation roadmap

Fill in the template thinking at what happens when your current project will finish.

Exploitation roadmap for KER [title of the KER]	Input by the Beneficiary	Comment by the Expert
Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Package 8 thematic trainings as reusable kits: trainer kit, learner kit, SCORM/HSP bundle, LTI notes, Zenodo DOI. - Launch Train-the-Trainers cadence and micro-credential pilots (badge criteria, assessment rubrics). - Localisation pipeline (translations) and accessibility checks; publish licence matrix and contributor guidance. - Publish annual release calendar and evaluation loop; outreach to 10 early adopters with 'first-run' bundle. 	<i>Prioritise 3 modules for micro-credentials (demand-driven) and publish measurable learning outcomes.</i>
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thematic leads: AU (Citizen Science), SISSA (SciComm), APRE/LOBA (D&E), UniSR/ESF (GN), SciLink (Mental Health & Leadership), UMinho/OpenAIRE (Open Access), DANS (FAIR RDM), EARMA/AU/UniSR (Research Integrity). - Platform: OpenAIRE (OpenPlato), LPI (Projects). 	<i>Nominate a packaging 'editor' to enforce consistency across modules (format, metadata, QA).</i>
Milestones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - M+3 (Sep 2026): 4 modules fully packaged with DOIs and kits. - M+5 (Nov 2026): launch TTT wave #1; start 2 micro-credential pilots. - M+6 (Dec 2026): 8 institutional adoptions; ≥300 completions across modules. - KPIs Y1 post-project: ≥12 institutional adoptions; ≥1,000 completions; ≥6 TTT sessions; ≥20 reuse events (imports to external LMS). 	<i>Publish adoption stories and keep an open improvement backlog; align outcomes with EOSC/competency frameworks.</i>

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Costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Year 1: €25–40k (packaging, localisation, QA, trainer time). - 3-year cumulative: €75–120k (refreshes, TTT cadence, accessibility). 	<i>Reserve budget for translations and accessibility audits; use templates to lower per-module costs over time.</i>
Revenues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Institutional training/service packages and co-branded runs: €15–25k Y1; €60–90k Y3. - Badges/micro-credentials: €3–10k Y1; €10–30k Y3. - Sponsorships for themed cohorts/events: €5–15k Y1; €15–30k Y3. 	<i>Bundle services (customisation + evaluation) to improve margins; keep core content OER.</i>
Other sources of coverage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Erasmus+/national skills programmes; - University professional development budgets; - Thematic foundations; - Sister-project synergies. - Timing: pre-agree 2–3 co-branded runs by M+4. 	<i>Use MoUs to secure in-kind trainer time and local venues/communications support.</i>

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KER 1 –EU RRI training mapping
and gap analysis

04-11-2025
Iteration #1

Problem <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fragmented, outdated view of RRI/OS trainings across Europe Time-consuming desk research; hard to compare quality/coverage Lack of machine-readable data & clear licensing for reuse Difficult to justify investments and plan curricula Alternative Solutions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ad-hoc web searches and national portals Internal surveys/spreadsheets maintained locally Commercial course directories/MOOCs with partial coverage 	Solution <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open report + machine-readable dataset with DOI Executive infographic and discipline snapshots; methodology annex Website dashboard with KPIs; Policy briefs, webinars, and adopter 'starter pack' 	Unique Value Proposition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Authoritative, pan-EU evidence base with CCO data and actionable gaps Decisions in weeks, not months; persistent DOIs and reproducible method 	Unfair Advantage <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consortium reach (OpenAIRE/EOSC) and harmonised metadata schema Governance and update plan; unique CCO dataset + comparative tables 	Customer Segments & Early adopters <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Customer Segments: Institutional training decision-makers; funders/policy officers; training providers Early adopters: National OS coordinators; OpenAIRE nodes; EARMA community
	Key Metrics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Report views/downloads; dataset downloads; Institutional adoptions/MoUs; reuse events Newsletter/webinar engagement; dashboard traffic 		Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> OpenAIRE/EOSC channels, newsletters, and website Webinars and policy briefs; EU events; LinkedIn; partner networks Targeted briefings for doctoral schools and national nodes 	
Cost Structure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> People: editorial & analysis; comms & webinars R&D/Engineering: dashboard setup & maintenance Marketing: infographic design; outreach Translations/localisation reserve Hosting/DOIs & repository curation 			Revenue Streams <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Core: public good (no direct sales) Indirect: sponsored infographics/events; invited talks/consulting Grants for updates via EU/national calls 	
PRODUCT			MARKET	

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The Value Proposition Canvas

KER 3 – PATTERN Trainings

Customer Segment

- Doctoral and postdoctoral researchers

The Value Proposition Canvas

KER 2 – PATTERN Digital Ecosystem

Customer Segment

- Institutional training owners (doctoral schools, RIs, national OS nodes) seeking a federated platform

The Value Proposition Canvas

KER 1 –EU RRI training mapping and gap analysis)

Customer Segment

- Doctoral schools and Research Integrity/Ethics offices at universities/RPOs (decision-makers)

The Lean Canvas

KER 1 – D1.1 Report (EU RRI
training mapping & gap analysis)

04-11-2025
Iteration #1

<p>Problem</p> <p>Siloed LMSs; lack of federation/SSO; integration friction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited analytics & credential tracking across institutions GDPR/compliance uncertainty; unclear maintenance commitments No persistent archiving/DOIs for training assets <p>Alternative Solutions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local LMS only (Moodle/Canvas) without federation Proprietary MOOCs or static repositories Ad-hoc portals 	<p>Solution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> OpenPlato LMS + Project workspace with Keycloak SSO/LTI SLA & governance; risk register & deprecation policy Analytics dashboard & exports; KPI taxonomy Zenodo archiving with DOIs; membership & badges <p>Key Metrics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Active users; course completions; badges issued Institutional adoptions; reuse events (imports) DOIs minted; uptime & support response time 	<p>Unique Value Proposition</p> <p>European, federated, GDPR-compliant training commons</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Persistent DOIs + editorial governance; built for reuse and scale 	<p>Unfair Advantage</p> <p>OpenAIRE infrastructure & brand trust; EOSC alignment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Onboarding starter kit; public roadmap & community calls <p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SSO/LTI pilots; lighthouse case studies Membership programme; conferences & webinars Open backlog/community calls; partner/EOSC networks 	<p>Customer Segments & Early adopters</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Customer Segments: Institutional training owners (doctoral schools, RIs, national nodes) and platform admins Early adopters: PATTERN pilot institutions; OpenAIRE/EOSC nodes
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> People: product owners, devops, support, editorial board Engineering: hosting, plugin upgrades, security, analytics Marketing: case studies, documentation, community Compliance: DPIA, data maps, SLA upkeep Baseline ops ~€20k/yr (Level-2); improvements up to ~€120k/yr (Level-3) 		<p>Revenue Streams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Membership/sponsorship contributions Certification/badging fees Services: integration, content curation, analytics add-ons 		

PRODUCT

MARKET

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The Lean Canvas

KER 1 – D1.1 Report (EU RRI
training mapping & gap analysis)

04-11-2025
Iteration #1

<p>Problem</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Need credible, flexible OS/RRI training with recognition Language/accessibility gaps; uneven quality Friction importing content into local LMS; limited trainer capacity <p>Alternative Solutions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Institutional seminars/workshops; generic MOOCs Self-study via guidelines/blogs/videos Vendor workshops focused on tools 	<p>Solution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 8 modular trainings (self-paced & ILT) with trainer/learner kits SCORM/H5P bundles + LTI notes; translations & accessibility checks TtT cadence & community of practice; micro-credentials/badges <p>Key Metrics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Institutional adoptions; completions; TtT sessions Badges issued; reuse events (imports to LMS) Learner satisfaction & pre/post learning gains 	<p>Unique Value Proposition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Curated European OER catalogue with TtT and DOIs—easy to adopt, adapt, and accredit Complete packaging (kits + bundles) and EOSC/competency alignment 	<p>Unfair Advantage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consortium of thematic leaders and pilot evidence Integration with OpenAIRE/EOSC; standardised packaging template <p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partner networks; OpenAIRE/EOSC portals Conference workshops & webinars; 'first-run' co-branded bundles Testimonials and case studies 	<p>Customer Segments & Early adopters</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Customer Segments: Doctoral/postdoctoral researchers; data stewards; research managers; EU project teams Early adopters: EU doctoral schools; national OS nodes; research infrastructures
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> People: trainer time, coordination, evaluation R&D: packaging, localisation, QA, accessibility audits Marketing: outreach materials, case studies Hosting/DOIs for assets 		<p>Revenue Streams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Institutional service packages/co-branded runs Badges/micro-credential fees (where applicable) Sponsorships for themed cohorts/events 		

PRODUCT

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PATTERN.

Empowering Open and Responsible
Research and Innovation

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